

Interaction Possibilities in VR Conceptual Modeling

Development and Implementation of Different Prototypes

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Abstract

Diving into an immersive, virtual world is a natural and intuitive possibility to create conceptual models. This thesis deals with the question of how the interaction with conceptual models in virtual reality (VR) can look like, especially how the representation of knowledge in conceptual models can be enabled. Therefore, different interaction possibilities were analyzed to enable conceptual modeling in virtual reality. This includes interaction methods such as using one's own voice, gesture recognition, or a three-dimensional (3D) mouse. To analyze the different forms of interaction for the representation of knowledge in two-dimensional (2D) conceptual modeling, some sub-areas were analyzed first. These include knowledge representation, conceptual modeling itself, and the different interaction possibilities in Human Computer Interaction (HCI).

After a further analysis of the state-of-the-art VR technologies and their properties, a systematic transfer of the necessary modeling functions from 2D to virtual reality could be performed. Following the derivation of several concepts for interaction in VR, three of them were implemented in a prototype. These concepts can be used quite well for conceptual modeling in VR. They could, however, be improved by further development and by further combinations of other interaction concepts. Based on these results, further possibilities are presented how conceptual modeling in VR could be extended, and thus be used by a broader audience.

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Finally, I must express my very profound gratitude to my parents, who made my studies possible through their support and always had an open ear for me.

Acronyms

2D two-dimensional. ii

3D three-dimensional. ii

API Application-Programming-Interface. 56

AR Augmented Reality. 24

CAVE Cave Automatic Virtual Environment. 27

CUBE Computer-driven Upper Body Environment. 27

DM Direct Manipulation. 7

DOF degree of freedom. 33

GUI Graphical User Interface. 23

HCI Human Computer Interaction. ii

HMD Head-Mounted Display. 22

HTML Hypertext Markup Language. 56

UI User Interface. 6

VR virtual reality. ii

VRD virtual retinal display. 30

WIMP Windows, Icons, Menus and Pointers. 8

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1 Motivation

Since the beginnings of virtual reality, various text input interfaces have been developed and investigated that aim at seamless and user-friendly typing in virtual environments. Previous researchers have investigated a variety of interaction methods for VR input, such as portable gloves, specialized controls, head/glass direction, pen and tablet keyboards, virtual keyboards, touch screen keyboards, advanced virtual keyboards, voice-to-text and hand/finger gestures (Boletsis and Kongsvik, 2019).

Immersive and interactive three-dimensional virtual reality applications allow users to participate in experiences that are either very difficult or impossible in real life. For example, a microscopic world, a fantasy world, a distant planet, or an expedition into an erupting volcano. Through these applications, users can enter a virtual environment that can be manipulated to varying degrees and explored in real-time. To enable this interaction, these applications use special devices that address the basic senses (e.g. seeing, hearing, and touching). Because of their potential to augment and complement the learning process, these applications are, therefore, increasingly being used in many contexts (Mütterlein, 2018).

Those 3D applications key features are immersion, interactivity, and involvement. Immersion attracts the attention of the user. Many immersive tools, such as 3D stereoscopic displays and motion detection devices, may be used for achieving high degrees of immersion. Interaction in virtual reality is often described as the ability of the user to move within the virtual world and to interact with the objects of the virtual world. If the user can explore the virtual world and move objects within, the environment is interactive. Involvement has to do with engaging the user's interest in the underlying activity and it can be achieved by providing engaging challenges to the user (de Paiva Guimarães et al., 2016).

In the early years, 3D applications needed significant computational power, and therefore the need for high-end supercomputers. Due to the low-level software platforms available at the time, the production of those applications was further complicated. However, in recent years, such applications have become more affordable, despite the developments in computer hardware, software, and network (Nalbant and Boton, 2016).

Nowadays, it is possible to use high-level libraries such as Unity 3D or Ogre3D. However, portability is still a problem. This problem has led to the development of HTML5 support for graphical applications, such as the WebGL standard (Angel et al., 2018) and the asm.js standard to improve the performance of interpreters and others. Due to this development, the browser-based use of virtual reality is becoming more and more widespread and has found acceptance in many areas (de Paiva Guimarães et al., 2016). For example, in the modeling of computer models in predefined conceptual modeling languages such as BPMN, UML, or approaches for design thinking. When such models become extremely large, visualization in two-dimensional space is relatively difficult. The creation and visualization of such models in virtual reality can

create great added value for the user in certain applications.

Many aspects of interaction in browser-based virtual reality models have already been clarified. A big problem, however, is the input of knowledge in a 3D model. In the virtual environment, a possibility must be created to assign attributes to objects. This is often done by assigning text-based attributes. In browser-based solutions such as the three.js library (Angel et al., 2018), there are several approaches for text input via mouse and keyboard. As soon as you no longer use a screen, but additional hardware, like virtual reality glasses, input with mouse and keyboard becomes difficult. Therefore, implementations that allow the input of text by virtual means are needed. Based on the lack of such input possibilities in browser-based virtual reality environments for 3D conceptual modeling, the thesis will include the implementation of three different input prototypes in the JavaScript library three.js.

These three prototypes are based on a broad analysis of the input possibilities in 2D modeling environments. The intention is to transfer existing concepts to the three-dimensional world and to develop new concepts.

2 Current Forms of Interaction for the Representation of Knowledge in Conceptual Modeling

This chapter aims to explain the current forms of interaction for conceptual modeling. Conceptual modeling concerns the creation of information models at the level of a technical concept, which is strongly oriented towards the business problem and the common technical language, while at the same time abstracting the real world. It is, therefore, a question of presenting and storing any kind of knowledge in a simplified form using a model. But what is *knowledge*? How can this knowledge be represented in an information system and what forms of interaction can be used to do this? The answers to these questions are discussed in this chapter. The first section explains knowledge in general and *knowledge representation* in information systems. This is followed by a section on conceptual modeling and a section on the different styles of interaction in conventional computer programs. Finally, this information is used in section 2.4 to discuss which interaction styles have been used in conceptual modeling so far.

2.1 Knowledge

There is no single definition for the concept of knowledge. Since the old times, various meanings from different backgrounds and viewpoints were proposed. Many definitions complement one another, and others prove more useful in practical terms. In the following the concepts of explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge, suggested by Michael Polanyi (Polanyi, 1966) and Nonaka and Takeuchi (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995) are referred. This is important to distinguish at this point because not all types of knowledge are relevant to knowledge representation in conceptual modeling.

When someone wants to remember information, this is often called *memorizing* or *learning by heart*. You can then say that this person has acquired knowledge. Another form of knowledge arises as a result of understanding a given piece of information and using this information to gain knowledge about how to solve a problem. Knowledge can, therefore, be interpreted in different ways. Either as acquiring and remembering different facts or as using information to solve a specific problem.

The first type is called *explicit knowledge*. This is the knowledge that you can simply pass on. Usually, this happens in the form of stored media such as encyclopedias or books, but nowadays also through computer models or entire information systems. Simplified, one can assume that explicit knowledge is information that can be written down and passed on.

The second part of knowledge is called *implicit* or *tacit* knowledge. In Polanyi's classification system (Polanyi, 1966, p. 1-25), implicit knowledge represents that part of knowledge which

is not or cannot be fully expressed in words. It includes knowledge and skills. The implicit knowledge has a twofold basic structure, which applies to both cognitive and physical skills. It consists of the *central* consciousness and the *supporting* consciousness. In apparently automated activities, the implicit form of knowledge manifests itself, which is mute at the moment of action, and the result of which only becomes conscious in retrospect. For example, writing a computer program, cooking, playing an instrument, or operating a complicated machine requires not only explicit knowledge such as instructions but above all implicit knowledge, which one must acquire.

Nonaka and Takeuchi (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995, p. 70-109) further deepened this approach and defined four transitions from knowledge to knowledge in the field of knowledge management:

- From the *implicit knowledge* of one person to the *implicit knowledge* of another person (**socialization**).
- From *implicit knowledge* of a person to *explicit knowledge*. For example, by writing down knowledge/skills. However, this can lead to problems since implicit knowledge usually cannot be translated exactly (**externalization**).
- From the *explicit knowledge* of a person to *implicit knowledge*. This can be achieved by learning, for example (**internalization**).
- From *explicit knowledge* to *explicit knowledge* (**combination**).

2.1.1 Representation of Knowledge in an Information System

Socialization is a proven method in knowledge management. However, it cannot be applied in knowledge representation and information systems since knowledge is transferred directly between people and is not preserved in a system. The same applies to *internalization*, although the acquisition of implicit knowledge is partly possible through explicit knowledge from information systems. Knowledge representation, therefore, finds its application mainly in *externalization* and in *combination*. In combination, person-independent, explicit knowledge is preserved and presented in its objective contexts. Externalization, however, is clearly limited by the implicit knowledge (Stock and Stock, 2014, p. 20-50). For this reason, the two fields of externalization and combination are the most important concerning knowledge representation in information systems.

As earlier defined by Alfred Kobsa (Kobsa, 1982, p. 20-47) knowledge representation can be described as follows: Knowledge (K) is fixed in *documents*, which we always break down into equal units. Document is understood here very broadly. This includes textual entities as well as non-textual entities such as spoken language, music, pictures, videos, or other facts. (S) stands for *system*, in general digital, which represents the *knowledge* (K) as *surrogates* (X). These surrogates can be of different nature. It is about the representation of knowledge by language, more precisely by concepts and statements, regardless of whether these are of a textual or non-textual nature. In short, one could say that the use of information systems is primarily about the representation of knowledge. Through some interaction (section 2.3), information is stored in an information system. Since conceptual modeling takes place for the most part on a computer, i.e. in information systems, the types of knowledge representation described are also relevant to conceptual modeling.

To represent knowledge in an information system, especially in conceptual modeling, it needs its language, which like every language has its lexicon and rules. How to define these rules and why they are important in conceptual modeling, we will see in the next section.

2.2 Conceptual Modeling

The field of conceptual modeling aims at the development of *concepts*, *tools* and *techniques* for the creation of computer models, which are used to better understand a context and to communicate through it. The same could be said for knowledge representation described in the previous section. The difference is, however, that in conceptual modeling these models are clearly used to support the design of databases, software, business processes, etc., whereas knowledge representation is much more general. This chapter deals with conceptual modeling in general and with the properties of conceptual models, especially concerning knowledge representation and -processing.

An advantage of conceptual models is, that they can capture the semantics of an application with the help of formal notation. In order to make this possible, the key component of each conceptual modeling approach is a *conceptual modeling language*. Examples of such languages are the ER modeling language, UML or BPMN (Guizzardi and Mylopoulos, 2019).

According to Robinson (Robinson, 2008) conceptual modeling languages consist of three important facets.

1. The conceptual model is non-software specific. Considerations on what to model and what not to model should not be influenced by the software that is or will be used.
2. The conceptual model does not describe the real world exactly. It describes the abstracted model from the understanding of the real world. In some cases, this abstraction can be far away from the real world.
3. The conceptual model is made up of a collection of components. The model's objectives, content, assumptions, and simplifications. The modeling objectives explain the model's purpose. The content of the model is comprised of the components represented in the model and their relations. Assumptions are made either when there is doubt or a belief about the real world. The model integrates simplifications to allow faster model creation and usage, and to increase model transparency.

Further, Robinson (Robinson, 2008) describes the advantages of conceptual modeling as follows:

- It can reduce the probability of incomplete, undefined, contradictory, and incorrect specifications.
- It helps create the model's integrity.
- It guides the computer model creation.
- It forms the basis for verification of the model and directs validation of the model.

- It provides the basis for documenting the model.
- When required it can serve as an aid for independent verification and validation.

However, it is necessary to differentiate, that an interactive system's conceptual model is not the User Interface (UI). It is not about what the software looks like or how it feels like. Keystrokes and mouse movements, screen graphics and layout, commands, navigation schemes, dialog boxes, controls, data presentation, or error messages are not specified here. It just explains what people should or could do with the system and what principles they need to learn and understand to run it. So, the conceptual model refers only to objects of the task-domain, the attributes, and the actions (Johnson and Henderson, 2002).

The creation of a valid model depends on a modeling method. As Karagiannis defines (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002), three components are important for the composition of a modeling method (see figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Components of modeling methods. (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002)

First, there is the *modeling language*, which is defined by syntax, semantics, and notation. The syntax defines the rules and elements for creating a model and thus to represent knowledge. The semantics describe the meaning of a modeling language. A distinction can be made between the semantic domain and the semantic schema. In the semantic domain, the meaning is described by ontologies or mathematical expressions. The semantic schema, on the other hand, connects the syntactic construct with its meaning. The notation is used to visualize the modeling language. This is achieved by graphical representations. The *modeling procedure* defines how a user handles the defined modeling language and the *mechanisms and algorithms* define the model processing functionality. The importance of the different components in relation to knowledge representation in conceptual modeling is discussed in section 2.4.

As described in this section, conceptual modeling is about the representation of a more or less abstract model of reality. For this purpose, an attempt is made to represent the state of reality by abstraction and definition of a modeling language through a computer model. Thus, one wants to represent and store implicit or explicit knowledge (section 2.1) by conceptual modeling.

However, a conceptual model is not fixed and unchangeable after its creation. The creator's knowledge or interpretation of the knowledge can change. This can be reflected in a conceptual model. To represent knowledge in a conceptual model, system components are needed that allow the creator to manipulate the properties of the model, i.e. the entities, attributes, relations, etc. On the one hand, knowledge in a conceptual model can, therefore, be created or modified by a visual representation of objects and attributes, or, on the other hand, by attributes in the background, mechanisms or algorithms, which are not visible to the User.

The next section deals with those components of a system that are not part of the conceptual model but the computer system. Nevertheless, they are extremely important for any software and in the context of this thesis of the highest importance.

2.3 Human Computer Interaction and Interaction Styles

Looking at all these different computer systems, there do not seem to be many specific similarities on which to base a comparison of use. The most common part of any of these applications is the user. Most systems are designed for one reason. Help the user learn a system quickly, and then become very effective with a program-based system when performing tasks, or interactions. Even games and other entertainment apps are still trying to make it easy for the user to know how to use the app so that as soon as possible the user can start playing and get enjoyment from the program. By doing so, they seek to minimize the distance between the expectations of the user and the interactions required to insert them into the system. Each system has a subset of permitted interactions the user can perform. Interaction is what the user does to accomplish a purpose in the program, while a task is the objective the user tries to achieve by conducting an interaction, or a sequence of interactions (Christou and Jacob, 2003). You can distinguish different types of interaction. One of them is Direct Manipulation (DM). DM is an interaction type in which users use physical, incremental, and reversible actions to act on displayed objects of interest, whose effects are immediately visible on the screen (Shneiderman, 1983). Because this type of interaction is the most important concerning conceptual modeling software, only *Direct Manipulation* will be discussed in the following. Interaction can be seen as a conversation between the user and the machine. The selection of the interface style can have a profound influence on the nature of the dialogue.

But what is needed for a dialog between a human being and a computer? It needs a human being who can feel sensory perceptions and thus receive signals from the computer. On the other hand, it needs a computer that can send such signals to a person. But it must also be able to receive and interpret signals from a human being so that interaction between a human being and a machine can work. The classical five senses of a human are the sense of *sight*, the sense of *hearing*, the sense of *touch*, the sense of *taste* and the sense of *smell*. These senses can be used to interpret the information the computer sends or to send the information to the computer. The most important aspects of the classical interaction between humans and computers are the senses of sight, hearing, and touch. As a result, most computer work is done on a screen through which the user is exposed to visual stimuli. Besides, the user's sense of hearing may be addressed by sound stimuli or even by the sense of touch, for example with a haptic feedback from a device. These stimuli are then interpreted by the user and the user can respond in a variety of ways. In the vast majority of cases in classical HCI, this is done using

a mouse and a keyboard that requires the user to use a combination of touch, hearing, and vision.

In the following sections, the most common interface types and their effects on the interaction are introduced. As described by Alan Dix (Dix et al., 2003, p. 123-164) a variety of common interface styles are possible, including:

- **Command Line Interface**
- **Menus**
- **Natural Language**
- **Question/Answer and Query Dialog**
- **Form-Fills and Spreadsheets**
- **Windows, Icons, Menus and Pointers (WIMP)**
- **Point-And-Click**
- **Three-Dimensional Interfaces**

2.3.1 Command Line Interface

The *command line interface* (see figure 2.2) was the first frequently used interactive dialog type, and it is still widely used given the availability of menu-driven interfaces. It provides a way to explicitly communicate instructions to the computer, using function keys, single characters, abbreviations, or entire-word commands. For certain systems, the command line is the only way to communicate with the device, especially when using systems for remote access. In general, it is today similar to menu-driven interfaces and allows experienced users quick access to the system's functions.


```
Windows PowerShell
Copyright (c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

Try the new cross-platform PowerShell https://aka.ms/pscore6

PS C:\Users\> ssh
usage: ssh [-6AaCfGgKtWmqstTVvXxy] [-B bind_interface]
          [-b bind_address] [-c cipher_spec] [-D [bind_address]:port]
          [-E log_file] [-e escape_char] [-F configfile] [-I pkcs11]
          [-i identity_file] [-j] [user@]host[:port] [-L address]
          [-l login_name] [-m mac_spec] [-O rtt_end] [-o option] [-p port]
          [-Q query_option] [-R address] [-S ctl_path] [-W host:port]
          [-w local_tun[:remote_tun]] destination [command]
PS C:\Users\> ssh wcidocom@wcido.com -p 2298
Corrupted MAC on input.
ssh_dispatch_run_fatal: Connection to 193.70.44.153 port 2298: message authentication code incorrect
PS C:\Users\> ssh wcidocom@yberling.com -p 2298
ssh: connect to host yberling.com port 2298: connection timed out
PS C:\Users\>
```

Figure 2.2: Example of a command line interface. (<https://www.yberling.com/en/blog-web-install-windows-ssh-client-powershell>, visited on 07.05.2020)

2.3.2 Menu-Driven Interface

The range of choices available to the user will be displayed on the screen in a *menu-driven interface* (see figure 2.3), and selected using the mouse, numeric, or alphabetic keys. Because the options are visible, they are less demanding on the user, who relies more on recognition than memory. Menu options however still need to be meaningful and logically grouped in order to help recognition. Menus are often ordered hierarchically, and the required option is not available in the top layer of the hierarchy. The grouping and naming of menu options would then provide the user with the only cue to locate the choice needed. Such menus can be either purely text-based or graphically displayed. Depending on how the menu is displayed, various other interaction styles are required.

Figure 2.3: Example of a menu-driven interface. (Abdur et al., 2017)

2.3.3 Natural Language

Perhaps the most attractive means of communication with computers is *natural language*, at least at first glance. Users who cannot remember a command or are lost in a menu hierarchy may long for a computer that can understand instructions expressed in normal words. Natural language comprehension, both spoken and written, is a topic of great interest and study. Unfortunately, the complexity of natural language makes it very difficult for a computer to understand. In some ways vocabulary is vague. First, it may not be clear what a sentence's syntax or structure is. Even if a sentence's form is clear we can find ambiguity in the context of the used words. To further complicate matters, the use of pronouns and relative words leads to confusion. Given these problems, it seems unlikely that a perfect language interface will be available for some time. However, in the past years, there have been huge improvements in the usage of language-based interaction. Within a defined and restricted environment, sufficient knowledge may be given to interpret words and sentences in the right context.

2.3.4 Question and Answer Dialog

The *question-answer dialog* is an easy way to provide input for an application in a specific context. The user can be asked several questions (mainly yes/no answers, codes, or multiple choice). This guides the user step by step through the interaction. *Web questionnaires* (see figure 2.4) are an example of this. The use of such interfaces is easy to learn and use, but their functionality and possibilities are limited. As such, they are suitable for limited areas, especially information systems, for beginners or occasional users.

Website Design Request
Fill out the form to request a design

Name
First Name Last Name

E-mail

Phone Number -
Area Code Phone Number

Company

Type of Business

Type of Website You Need?

Choose Items for the Navigation Bar About FAQ

Figure 2.4: Example of a web questionnaire. (<https://www.jotform.com/form-templates/category/web-design-forms>, visited on 07.05.2020)

2.3.5 Form-Filling Interfaces

Form-filling interfaces (see figure 2.5) are mostly used for the input of data and information, but can also be useful in data retrieval. The user is presented a window with slots for data input. This display usually resembles a paper form, which makes it easier for the user because such a form seems familiar. The user can work through the form as he or she wishes. The data is then entered at the appropriate point in the application. Most form-filling interfaces allow for easy movement inside the form and allow some components to be left untouched if they are not mandatory. They also allow correction possibilities, as users can change their minds or want to correct errors afterward. This dialog method is especially useful for data entry programs. Because it is easy to learn and use, forms are also useful for inexperienced users. However, if one adopts a design that allows flexible input of information, form-filling is also suitable for experienced users and can be of great value.

A screenshot of a form-filling interface. It features six text input fields stacked vertically, each with a label above it: 'First name', 'Last name', 'Phone number', 'Email', 'Password', and 'Confirm password'. At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: a blue 'Create account' button and a white 'Cancel' button with a blue border.

Figure 2.5: Example of a form-filling interface. (<https://medium.com/design-with-figma/ui-designers-guide-to-creating-forms-inputs-b6516f366a93>, visited on 07.05.2020)

2.3.6 Spreadsheets

Spreadsheets represent an alternate form-filling version (see figure 2.6). The worksheet is made up of a cell grid. Each cell can contain a value or a formula. The formula can contain other cell values. The user can enter and change the values and formulas in any order. The system maintains continuity between the displayed values and ensures compliance with all formulas. Thus, the user can modify values to see the results of various parameters.

2.3.7 WIMP

Most interactive computing environments are examples of the *WIMP interface style*, also simply called windowing systems. WIMP means *windows, icons, menus, and pointers* or sometimes windows, icons, mice, and pull-down menus. It is the default interface design for most interactive computer systems currently in use. WIMP includes also *buttons, palettes, toolbars and dialog boxes* (see figure 2.7). Since WIMP is a very common interaction style, we will take a closer look at the individual components in the following.

1. *Windows* are screen areas that function as though they were stand-alone terminals. A window can contain text or images, which can be resized and transferred around the screen. Several windows can be placed simultaneously on one screen, so various tasks are available at the same time. When users switch from one working thread to another, they will concentrate their attention on the different windows. Windows are normally associated with different things that increase their usability. For instance, scroll bars. This is an extension that allows the user to transfer the window contents up and down, or from one side to another. This makes the window behave like a not limited canvas.

Item Name	Date	Time	Quantity	Price	Amount	Discount
Casual Shoes	2/14/2014	11:34:32 AM	10	\$20.00	\$200.00	\$1.00
Sports Shoes	6/11/2014	5:56:32 AM	20	\$30.00	\$600.00	\$5.00
Formal Shoes	7/27/2014	3:32:44 AM	20	\$15.00	\$300.00	\$7.00
Sandals & Floaters	11/21/2014	6:23:54 AM	15	\$20.00	\$300.00	\$11.00
Flip- Flops & Slippers	6/23/2014	12:43:59 AM	30	\$10.00	\$300.00	\$10.00
Sneakers	7/22/2014	10:55:53 AM	40	\$20.00	\$800.00	\$13.00
Running Shoes	2/4/2014	3:44:34 AM	20	\$10.00	\$200.00	\$3.00
Loafers	11/30/2014	3:12:52 AM	31	\$10.00	\$310.00	\$6.00
Cricket Shoes	7/9/2014	11:32:14 AM	41	\$30.00	\$1,210.00	\$12.00
T-Shirts	10/31/2014	12:01:44 AM	50	\$10.00	\$500.00	\$9.00

Figure 2.6: Example of a spreadsheet in Microsoft Excel. (<https://www.syncfusion.com/jquery/php-ui-controls/spreadsheet>, visited on 30.04.2020)

Figure 2.7: Example of a WIMP interface. (<https://sstam95314.weebly.com/section-1—types-and-components/interfaces>, visited on 30.04.2020)

2. Windows can be closed and lost, or they can be shrunk to some very tiny representation. An *icon* can be used to represent a closed window. This is a very small representation of a picture. In having icons, several windows can be opened simultaneously on the screen, ready to be extended to their maximum size by clicking on the icon. Icons may also be used to reflect certain elements of the system, such as a wastebasket for throwing unwanted items into, or various user-accessible programs or functions.
3. The *pointer* is an essential component of the WIMP interface, since WIMP relies heavily on pointing and selecting items like Icons. The mouse offers an input tool capable of these

tasks while other alternatives are joysticks and trackballs. A cursor is displayed on the screen to the user, which is controlled by the input device. With help of this pointer, the user can click on buttons, select menu entries, icons, toolbar elements, or even select and drag elements.

4. The last key feature of windowing systems is the menu, a technique of interaction also widespread in many non-windowing systems. A *menu* offers a set of operations or services that the machine can perform at a given time. Menus provide cues of information in the form of an ordered list of available operations. It means the names used in the menu for the commands will be descriptive and clear. The pointing device is used to show the software the desired option. As the pointer moves to the location of a menu item, the item is usually highlighted to show that it is the possible selection candidate. Typically selection requires some extra user intervention, such as pressing a button on the mouse to control the cursor on the screen or pressing a special key on the keyboard.
5. After the four key features of a windowing system, there are some other important features that extend the interaction possibilities of WIMP. *Buttons* are independent and isolated regions within a display that the user can select to trigger a specific function of the system. These regions are referred to as buttons because they are meant to imitate the push buttons on a control panel that you might find in real-life situations. To push a button invokes an order whose objective is typically indicated by a text label or a small symbol. Buttons can also be used to switch between two states. These toggle buttons can be grouped to allow a user to choose one function from a collection of options that are mutually exclusive, such as the size of current font points. Most devices have a series of small buttons, each with icons, located at the top or side of the window and providing functions commonly used. The *toolbar*'s function is similar to a menu bar except that the icons are smaller than the corresponding text. This allows to displayed more functions simultaneously. Interaction can reach one of many modes in most software programs. The defining feature of modes is that the manner actions are interpreted varies as the mode varies. That could be keystrokes or gestures with the mouse. Using the standard UNIX text editor vi, for example, keyboard strokes can be interpreted either as operations to insert characters into the file (*insert mode*) or as operations to control the file (*command mode*). This is called a *palette* and it is typically a set of icons symbolic of the function for the different modes. *Dialog boxes* are information windows that the system uses to bring any important information to the user's awareness. This could be an error or an alert that is used to avoid a potential mistake. Additionally, they are used to activate a sub dialog for a very specific task between user and system, which would usually be contained within some larger task. For example, if the file must be saved by the user or program, a dialog box may be used to allow the user to name the file and indicate where it should be stored inside the filing system.

2.3.8 Point-And-Click Interfaces

Nearly all multimedia systems require only a single click of the mouse button to trigger an action. You can point to a picture in a gallery and the system shows you information about the picture when you click it. You may point to a word in a text and see a definition of the word. This *point-and-click interface* method is closely related to WIMP style. It overlaps button use but can contain other WIMP elements as well. The theory, however, is simpler and more closely

related to principles of hypertext. Additionally, the point-and-click approach is not only related to mouse-based interfaces but also commonly used in touchscreen applications. Often this is paired with a menu-driven interface.

2.3.9 Three-Dimensional Interfaces

Three-dimensional effects are increasingly being used in the user interfaces. The most obvious example is virtual reality, which will be discussed in more detail later in this paper. But VR is just a part of the 3D techniques available. The simplest technique is where ordinary WIMP components, buttons, scroll bars, etc., are given a shading 3D appearance (see figure 2.7). This gives the components a sense of three-dimensionality.

2.4 Interactions Needed for Computer-Based Conceptual Modeling

As described in section 2.3, a modeling method consists of three points. The *modeling language*, the *modeling procedure*, and *mechanisms and algorithms*. As this section deals with the different styles of interaction in conceptual modeling, in the following, we will limit ourselves to the use of the modeling language to achieve the desired result in the modeling procedure. One could also say with which means of interaction the user can achieve the desired goal. If the term “achieving the desired goal” is used, in the context of this thesis the creation of a conceptual model is meant, i.e. to represent and make accessible implicit or explicit knowledge by modeling with the help of software. Thereby, the focus is on the two forms of knowledge representation, *externalization*, and *combination* (section 2.1). This means that the user is trying to express his or her implicit or explicit knowledge through the model.

Conceptual modeling in the traditional sense of the term is usually done on a computer (Johnson and Henderson, 2002). For this purpose, modeling software is used. In most cases, this software allows the user to interact with the software using a mouse and keyboard. Many of the interaction styles explained in section 2.3 are used to interact with such a program. The usage and importance of these interaction methods in 2D modeling is discussed below.

A modeling software consists of several components that ensure the functionality of the software in the background. However, since this section deals with visualization and interaction to achieve this visualization, i.e. knowledge representation, we will focus on the core functions for model manipulation, particularly the *visualization core* (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013). This is about how the user can interact with the software and how the model is presented to the user on the screen. Functions such as user access management, model management, database management, etc. are not part of this discussion.

Before we go into the specific points of interaction, let us look at the possibilities of modeling on a higher level. Which functions must be given to create a conceptual model? Certainly, there is a need for classes that represent the different objects. In ER-modeling, for example, these could be the possibility to create instances of the classes entity, relation, and attribute (see figure 2.8). These classes must be placed, moved, or deleted in the model. Another function in conceptual modeling is the attribution of an object. For example, an object in figure 2.8 could

be directly assigned attributes, which are then stored in the model. For instance, clicking on an object could open a window that would allow additional information to be entered. Another and no less important possibility is to connect the different objects, either by a visual connection as in figure 2.8, or by a specific order of the objects in the model.

Figure 2.8: Example of an ER-model.

In traditional conceptual modeling, this is achieved by the user using the mouse or keyboard. If you look at the interaction methods described in section 2.3, you can see that this includes several interaction styles. Usually, the options available for creating instantiated elements are visible in a *menu-based interface* (section 2.3.2). The individual menu items or buttons can then be selected and the according elements placed by a *point-and-click* interaction (section 2.3.8) of the input device (figure 2.9). This applies not only to the creation of instantiated objects but also to the placement or deletion of objects and the creation of relations between the instantiated objects.

Figure 2.9: Example of a menu-driven and point-and-click interface.

The representation and manipulation of attributes is mainly concerned with the definition

and adaptation of attributes to instantiated objects of classes, or relations of the model. In some cases, this is possible directly in the representation of the model like in figure 2.8, where the round objects already represent an attribute in themselves. As soon as the individual classes or relations allow multiple attributes, usually, an additional window is required to define these attributes. This can be achieved, for example, by selecting the element for which attributes are to be defined. A new window appears, which allows the user to define different attributes by *point-and-click* and by keyboard input (figure 2.10). Because the available attributes are usually predefined by the definition of the conceptual model, this procedure is a typical case of the interaction style *form-filling interface* (section 2.3.5). This ensures that exactly the required information is provided (see figure 2.5). In cases where the attributes are not clearly specified or there is an undefined number of association options, *spreadsheets* (section 2.3.6) may be used. This enables the definition and representation of any number of attributes or relationships. Spreadsheets are not always independent but can also be integrated into the form-filling interfaces.

Figure 2.10: Example of a form-filling interface.

To put different objects in relation to each other, often visual connections are used. These can simply connect instantiated objects, or they can also contain attributes themselves. Most of the time this is possible by a combination of point-and-click. These relations are usually controlled by logic in the background to ensure the validity of a model (see figure 2.11). However, since this has nothing to do with the actual interaction, we will not go into this further here.

Several other important functions must be present in conceptual modeling. These are briefly summarized here. If the model is not to be created or adapted by drag-and-drop in the visual representation, the *grid visualization* provides the possibility to define and attribute the model in a table. The *spreadsheet* interaction style can also be used for this purpose, as the model's elements can be entered in a table and linked to each other. The creation of graphical files is often a function that can be triggered by a simple *point-and-click* on a button or icon in a

Figure 2.11: Example of an invalid relation.

toolbar or menu. The last important point in the user interface of a modeling software is the navigation through the model and the user interface. This includes *zooming* and moving the position inside the model. This function is usually achieved by *point-and-click* on buttons or icons, or by combining various keyboard commands or alternative input devices.

Although Dix (Dix et al., 2003, p. 123-164) does not mention the keyboard as an interaction style in its own, it is clear that in all modeling software, the keyboard is a common and almost indispensable means of providing the model with the information it needs. There are different approaches to replace the keyboard with interaction styles, such as *natural language*, for example with a voice assistant. However, this technology has not yet been developed to the extent that it would be an equivalent replacement for a keyboard.

By analyzing the different interaction styles, a modeling software for conceptual modeling is typically a classic *WIMP* (section 2.3.7) software. Of course, not all conceptual modeling platforms are built the same, but for the most part the keyboard and the mouse are essential parts of these platforms. The different functions that must be given in conceptual modeling and the interaction styles used are summarized in the table below (figure 2.12).

<i>Interaction Style</i> <i>Modeling Function</i>	Command Line Interface	Menus	Natural Language	Question/Answer and Query Dialog	Form-Fills and Spreadsheets	Point and Click	WIMP
Create Object		x				x	x
Move Object		x				x	x
Delete Object		x				x	x
Add Attribute of Object				x	x	x	x
Modify Attribute of Object				x	x	x	x
Delete Attribute of Object				x	x	x	x
Create Relationship						x	x
Modify Relationship						x	x
Delete Relationship						x	x
Zooming and Moving						x	x

Figure 2.12: Comparison of the use of the different interaction styles.

Since this thesis deals with interaction possibilities in virtual reality and mouse and keyboard are difficult to replace, this raises some major challenges for interaction, in particular for conceptual modeling in virtual reality.

3 Properties and Possibilities of VR

This chapter is about virtual reality. More precisely, it is about what VR is and what features and possibilities virtual reality offers. To understand virtual reality, first, we must make a detour into how humans perceive their environment. Then we will see an approach to the definition of virtual reality and what possibilities virtual reality brings with it. In the end, we will take a closer look at the different interaction methods in virtual reality and the current input and output devices.

3.1 Perception of Reality

People perceive the world by means of sensory impressions. For example, if light is reflected from a real object, such as a car, and enters a person's eye, photochemical processes are triggered in special sensory cells located in the retina. The light acts as a stimulus for these sensory cells. The light stimuli lead to nerve impulses, which are modified via complex interconnected nerve cells and transmitted to the brain. The processes in the brain can be divided into several stages. First, a rapid *parallel processing* of the visual sensory impressions takes place, in which, for example, the differently colored surfaces, as well as the possible pattern on the car, are identified. This is followed by a slower *sequential processing*, e.g. the assembly of the colored surfaces into sub-objects, such as the wheels or windows of the car, using memory. If a person has already seen a car, this can lead to recognition. The whole apparatus, from the sensory cells to the optic nerves and the visual centers in the brain, is called the *human visual system* (Sczepek, 2011, p. 12-35). In our example, the human being sees the car thanks to his visual system and can conclude about reality, e.g. that there is a car in front of him and that you can use it to get from point A to point B.

The connection between reality and what people perceive about it through their visual system is anything but simple. The same reality can cause different perceptions in different people. For example, about 9% of all men and about 1% of all women do not have the same perception of colors as most of humanity. Color, a term used by people to describe visual perception, is thus not a term that objectively describes reality. Color is not a physical property of an object but stands for a subjective sensation that is indirectly triggered by an object through reflected light. Even in a single individual, there is no simple connection between reality and visual perception of reality (Sczepek, 2011, p. 60-89).

This can be well illustrated using a Hermann grid. If you look at figure 3.1, you can see black squares arranged on a grid. At the intersections of the grid, you can see alternating, partly flickering dark and light points. But this does not correspond to the properties of the grid points in reality. All grid points are identical and always reflect the light in the same way. The same stimuli can, therefore, lead to different perceptions in the same individual at different times.

Figure 3.1: A Hermann-Grid: Although in reality all grid intersections always reflect light to the same extent, a person sometimes perceives dark spots. The dark spots disappear as soon as you try to look at them directly (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 3).

There is, hence, no fixed, unambiguous, and objectifiable connection between reality on the one hand, and the visual perception of the human being of this reality on the other. This creates wiggle room for manipulating the human visual perception of reality. A simple way is to replace a stimulus emanating from a real object with a similar, artificial stimulus. If the human visual system, stimulated by this artificial stimulus, comes to a similar perception as it would have done with a real object, the human being may even be under the mistaken impression that this object exists in reality.

Images are a typical example of this approach. If you want to evoke the visual perception of a car in a person, you must not have a real car. You can also show the person a photo of a car. Of course, this is not the same, it is just a piece of paper that reflects the light differently with the help of color pigments. This is fundamentally different from a car made of tin, metal, and rubber. But both have something in common. They similarly reflect light, stimulate the visual system in a similar way, and evoke similar visual perceptions in humans. Normally, a person would not be so easily fooled as to mistake a photo of a car for a real car. Let us assume, that by using an interface to the brain, different sensory impressions could be brought in in such a way that the body could no longer distinguish between real and artificial sensory impressions. Besides seeing, these could be impressions such as *hearing*, *smelling*, *feeling*, *tasting*, the sense of *balance*, *body sensation*, *temperature sensation* or *pain sensation*. So, if the stimuli emanating from a car could be calculated and reproduced in such a way that they could no longer be distinguished from reality, a perfect illusion of reality could be created (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 1-9).

Whether this perfect illusion of reality is a goal to be striven for, and whether this would also

be ethically justifiable, is another question, which will not be dealt with further here.

3.2 Definitions of Virtual Reality

As described by Dörner (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 12-20) the generation of the stimuli is only one task on the way to virtual reality. People in virtual reality do not only want to look and feel the world but also to interact with the world. For example, if there is a punching bag in a virtual world, the user might want to hit it or avoid it. This requires a virtual world that is simulated. The actions of the human being must be known to the simulation to let his actions flow into the simulation. This simulation, in turn, influences the stimuli that are perceived in the virtual world. If you move in the real world, this change of position must also be considered in the generation of stimuli. The calculations of this stimulus generation can be done by a computer. Not only simulations in connection with a human action can be generated. It is also possible to simulate changes in the virtual world that are independent of human actions. For example, light can be changed by simulating daylight or the weather.

The goal can be to make virtual reality as close as possible to reality. So, if the human being would hit the punching bag, it would move like in the real world. However, in virtual reality, one is not bound to the physical laws. You can let the punching bag fly away supernaturally or even explode. Or it could turn into an elephant. This makes it possible to create fantastic virtual worlds, which are either completely unreal or simply show a past or future world. Scenarios for this would be for example the representation of the populated planet Mars or the reproduction of a battle scene in World War II.

Dörner (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 7) summarizes a VR system as follows: A VR system is what we call a computer system that consists of appropriate hardware and software to create the idea of a virtual reality. We call the content represented by the VR system a virtual world. The virtual world includes, for example, models of objects, their behavioral description for the simulation model, and their arrangement in space. If a virtual world is represented with a VR system, we speak of a virtual environment for one or more users.

Even though the first approaches to virtual reality were already developed at the beginning of the last century, they have only come into the focus of science in recent years. This is especially true since its further development is strongly driven by rapid development in the underlying hardware. This is also the reason why there is still no clear and generally accepted definition of VR. Nevertheless, there are some characteristics of VR which are widely accepted. In the following, we will discuss two different approaches to define virtual reality. One is a technological characterization and the other is the characterization of VR as a new form of interaction in HCI.

3.2.1 Technical Definition of Virtual Reality

“The ultimate display would, of course, be a room within which the computer can control the existence of matter. A chair displayed in such a room would be good enough to sit in. Handcuffs displayed in such a room would be confining, and a bullet displayed in such a room would be fatal. With appropriate programming such a display could literally be the Wonderland into which Alice walked.” (Sutherland, 1965, p. 2)

The specific type of content input or output is probably a clear feature that all designs of VR systems have in common. For example, a helmet with integrated screens on the user's head, special stereo glasses, data gloves, or even an entire room with displays that completely surround the user. This creates the possibility of defining VR from a technological point of view. It should be noted, however, that the definition does not focus too much on the individual input and output devices, as they can very quickly become technically obsolete and a definition would, therefore, no longer be appropriate. Future-proof VR definitions should also be compatible with visionary ideas such as Sutherland's *ultimate display* from the beginning of this section. VR can most simply be characterized as a differentiation from traditional computer graphics. Thus, VR is an extension of the 3D content of computer graphics, particularly in real-time computer graphics. In combination with these 3D graphics, three-dimensional displays are used. For example, with classic VR glasses, this is achieved by stereoscopic methods. Often it is not only about the visual sense, but the presentation of the content is multi-sensory, by also addressing the sense of hearing or touch. In many cases, 3D interaction devices that can be tracked in 3D space are used. Such interaction methods will be discussed in a later section. All these aspects have the goal to surround the user with the virtual world. This has already been nicely summarized in a statement by Steve Bryson in 1993.

“Virtual reality (VR) refers to the use of three-dimensional displays and interaction devices to explore real-time computer-generated environments.” (Steve Bryson, Call for Participation 1993 IEEE Symposium on Research Frontiers in virtual reality)

Based on this enclosure of the user in the virtual world, immersion is most often referred to in literature as a central feature of distinguishing VR from other human-computer interfaces. The objective is to allow the sensory impressions of the user to be addressed as comprehensively as possible by one or more output devices. According to Slater and Wilbur (Slater and Wilbur, 1997) immersion is based on four technical characteristics of output devices:

- Human sensory impressions should be generated by the computer as exclusively as possible, i.e. the user should be isolated from the real environment as far as possible.
- As many senses as possible need to be addressed.
- Output devices should completely surround the user instead of offering a narrow field of view only.
- In addition, the output devices should offer a living representation, e.g. through high resolution and quality of color representation.

Thus, immersion is not simply given or not given but can be carried out in different degrees. For example, a conventional Head-Mounted Display (HMD) can have a larger or smaller screen with better or worse resolution. It is more or less immersive, therefore. Complete immersion is a vision at present that cannot be realized by the current state-of-the-art. However, a high degree of immersion can already be achieved through HMD or rooms equipped with displays (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 27-28).

3.2.2 Definition of Virtual Reality as Form of HCI

“An intuitive interface between man and machine is one which requires little training ... and proffers a working style most like that used by the human being to interact

with environments and objects in his day-to-day life. In other words, the human interacts with elements of his task by looking, holding, manipulating, speaking, listening, and moving, using as many of his natural skills as are appropriate, or can reasonably be expected to be applied to a task.” (Earnshaw et al., 1993, p. 183)

Another way to describe VR is to emphasize the aim of developing human-computer interfaces that allow a particularly natural or intuitive interaction with the 3D virtual world compared to conventional UI. Graphical User Interface (GUI), e.g. WIMP interfaces (see section 2.3.7) are a paradigm of HCI that has been dominant for decades. Pointing refers to a pointer tool, typically a computer mouse. The WIMP model, originally designed for document processing tasks, proves to be very inefficient for manipulating 3D content. For example, if an object needs to be repositioned in 3D space, this could be achieved naturally in VR by capturing and moving the object. In the classic WIMP interaction style, however, this is not so easy. If an object only needs to be moved in 2D space, this is not a problem. But as soon as an object must be moved in 3D space, it becomes relatively difficult with a conventional mouse. This means that an object can be moved on both the x- and y-axis as well as on the z-axis. Since a standard input device such as a mouse is not designed for such interactions, they are not readily applicable to them. In this case, it would be necessary to change the mode of interaction for the same input device for different actions, which increases cognitive effort for the user and makes the system anything but intuitive. Furthermore, the use of such an input device is not comparable to the everyday experiences of a human being and, therefore, must be learned.

Virtual reality is an example of a so-called *post-WIMP* interface, along with other innovative forms of HCI. Post-WIMP interfaces are based on the use of interaction techniques that rely heavily on the user’s prior knowledge from his everyday life when interacting with objects. For instance, a human being knows from his day-to-day experience how to use his body to control objects, and he has expectations of how such objects will typically behave as a result of this interaction. With this previous experience, the learning effort and much more mental effort of natural interaction techniques is substantially decreased relative to WIMP techniques. This Post-WIMP approach was clarified quite well in the quote from R.J Stone in his introduction to the intuitive user interface at the beginning of the section. Of course, this form of interaction is not perfect yet either. For example, when capturing an object in VR, tactile sensations are very difficult to implement. However, compared to conventional mouse interactions, the interaction methods implemented to date are already much more intuitive in VR than in 2D.

Another important aspect in the design of HCI interfaces is *metaphors*. They serve to make the user familiar with a concept by analogy to his everyday world. In the classic WIMP interaction style, the desktop of a computer is a metaphor for the real desk. This includes folders, a recycle bin, or even functionalities to edit documents, like cutting and pasting. Such a metaphor also represents virtual reality. This is based on the analogy to the *real world*, the everyday life of the user. As a result, the VR metaphor attempts to simulate a user-friendly world that allows analogous forms of interaction to those in everyday life. The user should experience this world from the inside, and not from the outside, as by looking at the screen in the traditional WIMP interaction style. This can be achieved by a *perfect immersive system* (see section 3.2.1). The user is constantly cut off from the outside world and his sensory impressions are calculated by the VR environment and passed on to the user through one or multiple output devices. As already mentioned, this perfect immersive system is only theoretically strictly applicable, although it is

becoming more and more feasible (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 29-31).

3.3 Reasons for Using Virtual Reality

What is the point of all this? Why would you want to build a virtual reality at all and put people into it? What is the point of dealing with virtual realities? There are many answers to these questions. Some of them we will consider in the following.

As described by Dörner (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 1-20), these questions can be of different nature. What do you have to consider when you want to put people into a virtual world? What makes it credible? What effort is required for this in a particular application area? How is the transmission of different stimuli from a VR technically realized? Which devices are there to make it easier for a person to immerse himself or herself in virtual reality? How is a computer system structured that generates the corresponding stimuli, e.g. generates images from a VR close to reality? What is the system architecture of a VR system? Which interfaces are there, which norms and standards? How do you build simulation models for the world simulation of VR? How does the simulation get information about the actions of the persons? How can people move in a virtual world? Which algorithms are used in VR? What is the runtime of these algorithms? How can the VR system meet real-time requirements?

We have already answered some of these questions and we will answer some more. In the following, however, we do not want to concentrate on the technical questions of VR, but rather on what advantages VR has in general and why it makes sense to use VR in certain situations.

The idea that perception can be changed artificially is not new. In the past, artists, inventors, and magicians have created many fascinating illusions that deceive the human eye and mind. As early as 1870, the German physiologist Ludimar Hermann (Hermann, 1870) published the Hermann grid discussed in Section 3.1. Another example is a painting by M. C. Escher from the 1920s, which depicted impossible scenes such as rising water.

What Hermann, Escher, and many others have known is that the brain can be persuaded to believe things that do not exist or are not inherently true. As early as the 1930s, inventors started experimenting with stereoscopes using lenses and mirrors to create a 3D image of objects. The View-Master company developed the idea in 1939 when it pioneered a portable stereoscopic display. But the idea of virtual reality has only evolved since the advent of digital data processing, as we know today. Virtual reality technologies allow us to go beyond the limits of the physical world and visit places reserved to the imagination in the past. Today VR and Augmented Reality (AR) exist in all kinds of situations and locations. They can be used in movies, game consoles, smartphones, cars, glasses, and HMDs. VR occurs in research laboratories and industrial environments that generate ultra-realistic experiences using goggles, audio signals, haptic gloves, and other sensory equipment. Those systems will change countless jobs, procedures, and industries over the next decade and beyond (Greengard, 2019, p. 17-37).

It may be a meeting of business associates spread all over the globe. Or maybe it is a parachute jump, a roller coaster ride, or a rafting trip in the white water of a roaring river. But VR is more than just the feeling of being in another location or a different time. Complex effects

and computer simulations can be visualized directly in a virtual environment. For example, measuring how air will flow through a newly built vehicle. In the virtual world, engineers and designers may work together to develop aesthetically pleasing vehicle body shapes which avoid air turbulence and reduce the air resistance of the vehicle. In a virtual reality, even complete abstract data can be visualized. In this way, it is possible to transport an analyst to a virtual world of financial data or blockchain. Besides gaining scientific knowledge, virtual worlds can also deliver a very realistic use with measurable financial benefits. Today hardly any car is built without using virtual reality methods. For example, designs can be more accurately visualized, and prototypes can be more cost-effectively produced than in conventional model making. How the robots in automotive production lines are adapted to a new airplane model can be replicated in a virtual environment before production starts. Thereby, it can be presented to the involved people in a VR environment. It is much easier to evaluate planning and reduce preparation errors in a virtual plant or a virtual factory, so it generates less expense than in the real world. Other VR applications can be found in airplane, bus, tram, train, and truck employee training. Often VR can be seen in the entertainment field. In adventure games, players can experience adventures in fantastic worlds. Tourists can experience historical cities such as ancient Rome very close to reality, by visiting them in a virtual reality environment. Museums can make history a sensual experience. Artists make use of virtual reality for their installations. VR stimulates excitement and can act as an eye-catcher, for example, it provides marketing opportunities at an exhibition stand. There are possible applications in the field of training in medicine. Doctors can practice and plan operations in virtual reality without any risk to patients. Nursing staff can train in the treatment of patients. Virtual reality may even be used for treatment. For example, a claustrophobic patient can be treated safely with VR by exposing the person to particularly constricting situations. The range of possible applications of virtual reality can be significantly expanded by trying not to completely cut off people from reality and to place them in an alternative virtual world. Instead, one can try to integrate parts of a virtual world into reality. Thus, in a room completely surrounded by displays, one could still see one's own body, which would enhance the experience (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 1-20).

There are many reasons and motivations for dealing with VR and realizing the corresponding virtual worlds. The use of VR in conceptual modeling is a very interesting possibility, which is of great importance concerning this work. There are many situations where the use of virtual environments in conceptual modeling can be useful. For instance, extremely large models that would not be visibly displayed on the 2D screen can be easily displayed in a virtual environment. Movement within these models may also be simplified. Many models become extremely large and confusing when shown in 2D. With a 3D representation, processes and procedures can be displayed more clearly and unambiguously. But not only representation is a key point in conceptual modeling. It is also important that the user, who wants to create a model, can transfer his knowledge to a model without much additional cognitive effort. In a conventional WIMP environment, this is mostly not possible, and the user must first learn how to use the various interaction options to perform the tasks required. This can be made much easier in virtual reality by using the mentioned *post-WIMP* interfaces (section 3.2.2).

Which possibilities there are for interaction in VR will be discussed in the next section.

3.4 State-Of-The-Art VR Interaction

There is already a variety of input and output devices that can be used in the context of VR usage. Not all of these devices are of equal importance for interaction in conceptual modeling. Nevertheless, in the following sections, we try to achieve a broad view of this area. The two sections on input and output devices in VR follow the explanations of Joseph J. LaViola (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 126-236).

3.4.1 Output Devices in Virtual Reality

A required component of any VR environment is the hardware which gives the user information. Such hardware tools, called *display tools* (or output devices), transmit information through the system to one or more of the user's senses. As mentioned in section 2.3, most of them concentrate on stimulating the visual, audible, or haptic senses. Of course, these output devices need a computer to produce the information through rendering, modeling, and sampling techniques. The machines then turn the output into a human mode of perception. So, we can think of displays as basically consisting of physical devices and computer systems used to produce material represented by physical devices. Display devices need to be included in the design, implementation, and use of various interaction techniques in VR user interfaces since certain interaction techniques are better suited to some displays than others.

In the following sections, we will distinguish between *visual displays*, *auditory displays*, and *haptic display* devices in the field of virtual reality. We discuss different examples and, the advantages and disadvantages of each type of display regarding VR interaction will be described.

Visual Displays

Visual displays provide the user with information about the human visual system. Visual screens are by far the most used input displays in VR user interfaces. Real-time computer graphics rendering techniques are used for visual display devices in VR UIs to generate the images which the display device presents to the user.

- **Single-Screen Display**

Single screens are often used for several different forms of 3D and VR applications. Those include video games as well as the presentation in science and knowledge representation. Here, though, more in the traditional sense of adapted WIMP interfaces. Such screens include standard monitors, high-quality televisions, and projectors where a wall or panel is used as a projection surface. Smartphone and tablet screens for use in mobile VR applications are also included in this category.

Such displays are inexpensive compared to other, more complex displays and can still provide in-depth detail. Stereoscopy can also be accomplished with a basic monitor and some extra equipment such as stereo glasses. But, there are also *single-screen* displays that do not need any special stereoscopy hardware (see figure 3.2). Such devices are of an autostereoscopic design. These displays can be used to display a 3D environment. However, in many cases, this type of VR is only slightly immersive, since the user is looking at the screen. In certain cases, however, such as cinema screens, this configuration may

be extremely immersive. In addition, this configuration provides a range of input devices, and the user can use established input devices such as the mouse or keyboard since he can see the real world around him (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 133-135).

Figure 3.2: Example of an autostereoscopic display in a Nintendo 3DS.

(<https://www.forbes.com/sites/johngaudiosi/2011/04/06/nintendo-3ds-gets-3d-gaming-competition-from-lg-and-htc-3d-smartphones-2/#27e43f3e12d6>, visited on 30.04.2020)

- **Surround-Screen and Multiscreen Displays**

A *surround-screen display* is a visual output device that surrounds the user, or a group of users, thus increasing the immersion considerably. This can be achieved for example by six surfaces of displays in the form of a cube, or by round displays in a sphere. The concept of such a system is to enclose the user partially or completely and thus isolate him or her from the outside world. One of the first such devices was the so-called Cave Automatic Virtual Environment (CAVE) (figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Example of a CAVE. (Tcha-Tokey et al., 2017, p. 5)

However, there are also less immersive variants such as the Computer-driven Upper Body Environment (CUBE), in which only the upper body of the user is enclosed by screens.

Another possibility for surround-screen displays would be a collection of screens placed in front of the user (figure 3.4). It can be summarized that the more the user is surrounded by the screen, the higher the immersion of the system (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 136-142).

Figure 3.4: A surround-screen display using a collection of display panels (Photograph courtesy of Chris North, Department of Computer Science, Virginia Tech).

- **Workbenches and Tabletop Displays**

Another type of display is like a *workbench* or *tabletop*. These displays are mostly designed to enhance simulations and interactions that take place on a table. Because they are tied to an external screen, the immersion of such devices is not extremely high. However, in combination with other 3D devices such as HMDs (described later in this chapter), or stereo glasses, these devices can create very interactive and immersive environments. Figure 3.5 shows an example of a table-based display that supports tracked 3D stereo and interaction (LaViola et al., 2017, p.142-144).

Figure 3.5: A personalized workbench display that supports tracked 3D stereo and interaction. (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 143)

- **Head-Worn Displays**

Up to now, our discussion has focused mainly on stationary devices, i.e. devices that cannot be moved by the user. In this section, however, we are dealing with visual displays

that are fixed to the user, more precisely to the user's head. This *HMDs* are also called *headsets* or *glasses*. The purpose of such HMDs is to place an image directly in front of the user's eyes. In most cases, this is achieved by specially developed devices (figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6: Example of a HMD. (<https://vive.com>, visited on 20.04.2020)

However, there are also approaches in which high-resolution smartphone screens can be attached to the user's head in special, most cheaper devices (figure 3.7).

Depending on the optical technique used, a combination of mirrors or refractive lenses is used to display and, if necessary, enlarge the images shown on the screens. We will not go into the technical functionality of such devices at this point. Due to technical progress in the development of high-resolution displays, these output devices are becoming better and more affordable. By allowing the user to wear the device right in front of the eyes and thus isolating him or her from the outside world, HMDs have a very high level of immersion. At the same time, the isolation is so high that some applications can become

Figure 3.7: Example of a smartphone-based HMD. (<https://arvr.google.com>, visited on 20.04.202)

difficult. For example, when I need to see my legs, HMDs are often not suitable for this purpose (Dörner et al., 2019, p. 183-186).

There are also other types of *head-worn displays* that go a step further and not only project an image in front of the user's eye but directly into the user's retina. These devices are called virtual retinal display (VRD). A VRD is no longer a pure VR device, but rather an AR device because the user is no longer shown a purely virtual world, but a combination of the real and virtual world. In this AR area, there are a lot of other developments, like glasses with transparent screens (figure 3.8), which allow a combination of the real and virtual world. However, since this work is mainly about VR, we will not go into such devices in more detail at this point.

Figure 3.8: A use case example of the Microsoft HoloLens. (<https://microsoft.com>, visited on 17.04.2020)

- **Arbitrary Surface Displays**

So far, we have looked at displays that used flat or curved screens. However, another approach is to project images directly onto *arbitrary surfaces*. This approach involves many challenges and the complexity depends on the difficulty of the geometry of the target object. How to deal with shadows? Is stereoscopy desired? Usually, such problems are solved with two or more projectors. An advantage of such projections on 3D objects is the support of depth. A 3D object already has the given properties by nature and, therefore, does not need to be generated artificially (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 152-155). A well-known example of this technology is the *Rendez-vous Bundesplatz* (figure 3.9), that takes place annually in Switzerland.

Auditory Displays

Other possibilities of VR output devices are *auditory displays*. They are often underestimated but can be of great importance for the perception in the virtual world. One of the major goals of auditory displays is the generation and output of 3D sound. Through the sense of hearing the user can perceive and interpret these sounds. For example, the localization skills of the user can be addressed. Auditory displays and 3D sounds are huge areas and a detailed analysis of these areas is outside the perimeter of this work. In total, however, it can be summarized in

Figure 3.9: A photo from the *rendez-vous Bundesplatz* 2015. (<https://rendezvousbundesplatz.ch>, visited on 30.04.2020)

a nutshell that five different types of audio output can be used in VR (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 156-160).

- **Localization:** This includes the creation of important audio depth clues that allow the user to experience the 3D environment in sound.
- **Sonification:** This is the process of converting information into audio sounds. It is the audio counterpart to visualization.
- **Ambient Effects:** This can give the user an increased sense of reality. For example, bird sounds, or the sound of wind can give the user a more realistic feeling in virtual reality.
- **Sensory Substitution and Feedback:** This is a way to replace sensory feelings with audio output. It can be very powerful if the haptic feedback is missing in an environment. For example, when touching an object in VR, a sound can be generated to signal the touch.
- **Annotation and Help:** Recorded or generated voice output can play a role in collaborative applications such as model viewers. It should help the user if the interaction in the 3D environment is unclear. For example, the user can be informed if he navigates in the wrong direction.

Haptic Displays

The last type of display device we will look at in this chapter is the *haptic display*. Haptic displays provide the user with a sense of touch by simulating the physical interaction between

the virtual objects and the user. Depending on the type of output device, a haptic display can give the user a sensation of *force*, *touch*, *vibration*, *temperature*, or a *combination* of all of these. Often these devices are combined with input devices (discussed in the next section). This allows the user's movements to be quickly analyzed and haptic feedback can be used to respond to them. A very fast feedback loop is of utmost importance for haptic feedback because a delay would quickly make the experience unrealistic (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 161-171). Figure 3.10 and figure 3.11 show two possibilities of such haptic displays.

Figure 3.10: Example of a haptic glove to feel size, weight, and impact in VR.
(<https://haptx.com>, visited on 12.04.2020)

Figure 3.11: A prototype of a artificial skin developed at the EPFL to create a feeling of touch.
(Sonar et al., 2020)

3.4.2 Input Devices in Virtual Reality

As we have seen in the previous section, the choice of output devices in VR is very important because they are the main way to present the virtual world to the user. Equally important is the choice of the right input devices because they allow the user to communicate with the application. For example, if we want to track the position of the user, or if the user wants to communicate with the VR environment by voice.

In this chapter, we will look at the different input devices for interacting with the VR environment in general. It is not about discussing the best devices in relation to conceptual modeling in the VR field. We will only discuss some currently available and representative input devices for VR environments.

One of the most important characteristics of an input device is the degree of freedom (DOF). This is a simple, specific, and independent way of how a body can move in space. An input device can typically capture three values for position. *X*, *Y*, and *Z*, and three other values for orientation in space which are *yaw*, *pitch*, and *roll*, which gives a total of six DOF.

Furthermore, devices can be classified according to whether they use active or passive sensors. Active sensors must be worn on the user's body and they send data to the application regularly. These are all input devices that are relatively useless for the application as long as the user does not manipulate them in any way. This can be, for example, by moving the device, or by pressing a button on the device itself. Devices with passive sensors, on the other hand, do not need to be manipulated by the user. They are independent of the user. A classic example of such a device would be a video camera. However, it should be considered that a video camera attached to a user could also be an active input device under certain circumstances. So, the main difference between active and passive sensors is the degree of manipulation. Active sensors require manipulation of the user to provide usable data. Passive sensors do not. There are also other classification possibilities, such as the type of use, or the frequency with which they generate data and transmit it to the application.

In the following sections, we will look at different input devices. We will divide them into three categories. *Traditional input devices* as we know them from 2D applications, *spatial input devices* and finally *nonspatial input devices* like speech input (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 189-236).

Traditional Input Devices

There are many input devices that were designed for use in classic 2D UIs. However, many of these devices can also be used in VR environments. This requires the mapping of the functions of the device to the 3D functions. Some of these devices are more suitable for use in VR and others cannot be used at all, depending on the immersion of the VR environment. In the following, we will look at keyboards, 2D mice, trackballs, joysticks, and desktop 6-DOF devices (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 190-197).

- **Keyboard:** The keyboard is a classic input device, which can be used in 2D applications as well as in desktop-based 3D applications. It is very useful for entering text, but also for navigation. However, depending on the degree of immersion, using a keyboard can be difficult because the user needs to see the keyboard to locate and use it. There are

approaches that make the keyboard no longer desktop-bound (figure 3.12), but this does not solve the problem of keyboard visibility.

Figure 3.12: Example of a portable miniature keyboard. (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 192)

- **2D Mice and Trackballs:** 2D mice and trackballs are the second category of classic WIMP input devices. The mouse is one of the most used input devices for computer interaction worldwide. The trackball is almost like a 2D mouse, but unlike the mouse, the trackball is not moved over a surface but is controlled by a built-in ball. Mice and trackballs have the same problem as the classic keyboard. They are mostly tabletop and not designed to be integrated into immersive environments. Because mice usually must be placed on a flat surface, this is usually not compatible with the characteristics of immersive, virtual environments. However, there are possibilities where, for example, a trackball is integrated into a position-independent controller and thus becomes more usable in immersive environments (figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13: Example of a handheld wireless trackball device. (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 195)

- **Joysticks:** Joysticks are another way to interact. They are mostly used in traditional desktop applications or in video games (figure 3.14). They usually consist of a combination of buttons and handles. Joysticks alone are not very useful in immersive environments. However, in combination with buttons like on game controllers, they can be a relatively good interaction method for virtual environments. However, since these controls are usually not tracked, and therefore, no position data is available, the use of such devices is usually not sufficient for VR environments.

Figure 3.14: Example of a Sony DUALSHOCK 4 Wireless-Controller.
(<https://playstation.com>, visited on 17.04.2020)

- **Desktop 6-DOF Input Devices:** 6-DOF input devices have been developed from a joystick derivation. They use isometric forces to generate 3D positions and orientation data (figure 3.15). Most of the time, however, these devices are explicitly designed for use in 3D desktop applications. Thus, they offer most of the possibilities needed for orientation in 3D space and manipulation of objects. But their use is limited by the lack of a possibility to collect tracking data for real-time movement in 3D space. Moreover, the use of such devices is difficult at the beginning and must be learned, which increases the cognitive effort (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 190-197).

Figure 3.15: Example of a 6-DOF desktop input device.
(<https://3dconnexion.de>, visited on 12.04.2020)

3D Spatial Input Devices

In many virtual environments, it is important to have information about the position of the user or a physical object. For example, some applications need the position of the user's head to calculate the user's viewing angle correctly and to adjust all other output devices to this position. Other UIs may require the position of the user's hand or even fingertips to interact with objects. This information then supports important tasks such as real-time rendering for a real representation of the environment. There are many ways such devices collect their data, like magnetic sensing, or optical sensing. However, we will not discuss the specific technology of these devices in the following, but the different devices themselves (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 198-217).

- **Tracking the Body for 3D User Interfaces:** When one speaks of body, in this case, it means head, hands, limbs, fingers, eyes, or the whole body as a unit. There are different methods to track these parts in VR. In this section, we will look at some of these devices.

The tracking of these different parts of the body can be done with either active or passive sensors. With active sensors, usually, a small device such as ultrasonic sensors or infrared sensors is placed on the desired body part. Often these sensors are also installed directly in another input- or output device, such as a HMD for head tracking. If many sensors are needed, as in the case of whole-body tracking, whole-body suits are often used (figure 3.16). This ensures that all sensors remain in the right place.

Figure 3.16: Example of a whole-body suit. (<https://teslasuit.io>, visited on 13.04.2020)

Another possibility is the use of *marker-based* external sensors for head, hand, or body tracking. In this approach, different markers are attached to the location to be tracked and

can then be interpreted by a camera. These two approaches can be cumbersome because the user must wear the sensors or markers.

Passive sensors such as depth cameras offer an alternative approach for tracking objects. The user only has to interact in front of the passive sensor, which interprets the movements with the help of an interpretation component. For example, skeletal images of the user's head, hands, and other parts of the body can be extracted. These can then be used in the 3D representation of the application (figure 3.17). Since these passive sensors are usually fixed in one place, the mobility of the user is usually limited to the range of the sensor, which is a disadvantage of this approach.

Figure 3.17: Example of hand tracking with a Leap Motion device.
(<https://virtualrealitytimes.com>, visited on 30.04.2020)

Figure 3.18: A data glove that uses accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers to capture information about each finger. (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 210)

In some cases, it can be useful to have exact tracking information about the user's fingers. This information can be collected with both active and passive sensors. A data glove (figure 3.18) is often used for this purpose. This would be an example of an active approach (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 198-217).

From the point of view of 3D UIs, these data gloves are mostly used to detect hand gestures and hand positions. These can then be used for a variety of interactions. For example, pointing a finger at an object could mean that the user wants to select that object. Many data gloves have been developed in the past. Most of the time, however, the problem is that they must be worn. In this case, a passive approach with depth sensors is an alternative. An example is the radar sensor project Soli from Google (figure 3.19), which allows very accurate tracking of hand and fingers.

Figure 3.19: Example of the radar sensor project Soli from Google, where the user adjusts a slider with small gestures of his fingers. (<https://atap.google.com/soli>, visited on 29.04.2020)

Eye trackers are input devices that are primarily used to find out where the user is looking. They are mostly based on optical scanning. This means that the device tracks the pupils of the user and can thus interpret where the user is looking. Since these devices are usually worn on glasses or attached to a screen, they are usually passive.

- **Combining Spatial Tracking with Physical Device Components:** In the last section, we considered approaches in which the positioning of the body itself rather than the positioning of devices is to be pursued. In many situations, however, it is not only about knowing and tracking the position of the user, but also about the user being able to use other device components such as *buttons*, *sliders*, *joysticks*, or *touchpads* to enable powerful functionality for entering information. In the following, we refer to these devices as 3D mice in the sense of user held or carried input devices that combine position-, orientation- and motion-tracking with physical device components. Due to their versatility, *3D mice* are often the primary interaction technique for interacting with virtual worlds.

A commonly used design approach of 3D mice is to place a motion tracker inside a housing, which the user then holds in his hands. These housings can then be equipped with various additional functions. Some of them are merely extensions of the well-known 2D mouse with position trackers and do not have many other additional functions. Other wireless 3D mice are more designed for the gaming market or the VR market and combine position tracking with various buttons and analog controllers (figure 3.20). Regardless of their shape and additional functions, all these 3D mice aim to provide *position-*, *orientation-*, and *motion data* in 3D space and to provide the function to initiate and end 3D interactions by pressing a button.

Figure 3.20: Examples of modern 3D mice that make use of optical and inertial sensing to produce 3D position-, orientation-, and motion data. (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 217)

Another approach of 3D mice is that the user does not have to hold a device in his hand, but can wear it on his hand. Assuming that the device is light and small enough that the user can wear it on the hand or a finger. The user does not have to concentrate on the device (figure 3.21). A disadvantage of these devices, however, is that their minimalistic design does not support many other functions except position tracking. For example, the number of buttons is limited.

There are almost no limits to the design of these 3D mice. For example, they can be so small that they can be hidden in a simple finger ring. Here, however, it must always be considered whether the device should be as small as possible and thus not disturb the user, or whether the device should support as many additional functions as possible to cover as many interaction functions as possible.

- **Complementary Input for VR:** The last two sections were about entering information with the help of the position of body parts or input devices. There are, however, other ways of entering information into the system. In the following, we will discuss one of these ways because it will be of great importance in the context of this work.

Figure 3.21: Example of a finger-worn 3D mouse. (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 218)

The tracking and recognition of *human speech* is a very powerful way to interact with VR environments. The signals, more precisely the speech, are captured by an acoustic sensing device and then analyzed by speech recognition software. The interpreted input signals can then be reacted to if necessary. This is a natural way to communicate with an application. It can be a very good possibility, especially if both hands of the user are already used for other tasks. Besides the right choice of recognition software, there are other important points. One of them is where to place the microphone. Ideally, one should use a microphone that can cover as large an area as possible. But then the problem arises that sounds from other people or machines in the room are also picked up. This leads to the problem that one must tell the computer when to listen to the user's voice and when not.

An easy way to solve this problem is the *push-to-talk* method, which allows the user to press a button as soon as he wants to have his voice recognized. If the button is not pressed, voice recognition is inactive. In order not to increase the cognitive effort of such a button for the user, it is usually implicitly linked to other interactions, so that the user mostly does not notice that it triggers an additional function (LaViola et al., 2017, p. 218-219).

In recent years, speech recognition software has become better and better and it is now possible to circumvent such problems. It is possible to integrate special commands that activate the speech assistant. The system then always listens, but only activates as soon as one of the keywords is recognized.

4 Concepts for Interactions With Conceptual Models in VR

In the last section, we discussed different interaction possibilities in VR. Some of them are better suited for interaction with conceptual models than others. In this chapter, the different possibilities are categorically analyzed. From this analysis, different combinations of the individual interaction possibilities can be derived. The most useful combinations for conceptual modeling are identified in the last section of this chapter.

4.1 Interaction Using Physical Devices

In this section, we will look at the different ways of interacting with physical devices in VR. This is not yet about a combination of different possibilities, but only about the interaction with conceptual models in VR and the respective input devices. Afterward, a comparison of the different possibilities can be made. This comparison is visualized in figure 4.9 of section 4.3.

4.1.1 Keyboard-Based Interaction

As described in the last chapter, the *keyboard* is one of the most important input devices in state-of-the-art computer programs. This also includes modeling software. Using a keyboard in VR is basically unproblematic and the functions of the keyboard can be integrated into the virtual environment through the software interface. But as mentioned earlier, using a keyboard is difficult once you are in a highly immersive virtual environment. In this case, you cannot see your hands or the keyboard itself. This makes interaction with a keyboard very difficult, or even impossible. In addition, a keyboard is usually tied to a desk, which strongly limits the freedom of movement in the virtual environment.

If we take the matrix from section 2.4 again, we can redesign it to show the different interaction categories in the top row. The keyboard can be used to cover all functions that are necessary for interaction with a conceptual model in VR (figure 4.9). However, since the keys on a keyboard are mostly predefined and cannot be extended arbitrarily, a multitude of key combinations must be defined for a standalone interaction with the keyboard. Learning and using these combinations is a cognitive extra effort for the user and does not make the application very intuitive. This is, hence, not perfectly compatible with the goal of VR and post-WIMP interfaces (see section 3.2.2), namely, to provide interaction possibilities that are as close as possible to the natural movements of the user.

4.1.2 Mouse-based Interaction

The same is true when using the *2D mouse*. It is designed for 2D environments. When using a normal 2D mouse, one is typically dependent on a screen. The mouse pointer is a kind of

interface between the screen and the position in the GUI. The position of the mouse pointer is always also the position in 2D space. It is possible to integrate a 2D mouse into a 3D environment. The mouse pointer is a vector in the extension of the field of view, which can collide with objects in the 3D environment (figure 4.1). Thereby, one can interact with objects, buttons, etc. This form of interaction still requires working on a conventional 2D screen. As soon as you are in an immersive VR environment, interaction with the mouse is more difficult, because you must find a way to move the mouse pointer in 3D space. There is not an unchangeable window available like on a normal screen. The fact that the mouse is usually tied to a desk and has to be seen to work with it, further complicating the input with a conventional 2D mouse in an immersive VR environment.

Figure 4.1: Visual explanation of a 3D interaction with a 2D mouse. (<https://godotengine.org/qa/25922/how-to-get-3d-position-of-the-mouse-cursor>, visited on 22.04.2020)

Since a 2D mouse usually has only a few buttons, it is of limited use as the sole interaction device. There are possibilities like virtual keyboards, which can extend the possibilities of the mouse. However, in the context of this analysis, this would have to be considered as a separate input device. As shown in figure 4.9, the 2D mouse alone offers only limited interaction possibilities for immersive VR environments.

4.1.3 3D Mouse-Based Interaction

This section is about *3D mice*. They are mostly designed for interaction in 3D space, and therefore, solve many of the problems of a 2D mouse. For example, the 3D mouse can be tracked at any time by position tracking. Thus, a 3D mouse supports six DOF. 3D mice can be replicated in the virtual environment through accurate position tracking, and therefore, do not need to be physically seen. This brings many possibilities for the use of 3D mice in very immersive environments. For example, 3D mice can be used to point at objects (figure 4.2) and attached buttons can be used to select objects, start, or stop functions. Furthermore, many 3D mice offer

not only buttons but also touch-sensitive touch-fields. This allows functions to be supported that cannot be achieved with simple buttons.

Figure 4.2: Example of a controller raycast to select objects in VR. (<https://circuitstream.com/blog/htc-vive-tutorial-raycasting>, visited on 06.05.2020)

Still, the input of text attributes is problematic with 3D mice. One possibility would be to use a virtual keyboard. With the help of a pointer, you could write on such a virtual keyboard. As already described for the 2D mouse, this would not be an integrated variant, but more a combination of input options. Another possibility would be the navigation via a keyboard using the touch-field of a 3D mouse. Since such a keyboard would be directly integrated in the virtual replicate of the 3D mouse, this can be seen as a function of the 3D mouse and not as a separate interaction option (figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3: Example of an integrated touch-navigated keyboard. (<https://medium.com/aaronn/vr-text-input-split-keyboard-e5bf3fd87a4c>, visited on 06.05.2020)

Thus, 3D mice support most of the functions needed for conceptual modeling in immersive VR environments (figure 4.9). Since the 3D mouse must combine many functions in a small space, the 3D mouse as a standalone input device is not very intuitive, but certainly better suited than a 2D mouse. In combination with other interaction methods, the 3D mouse can be a very powerful option.

4.1.4 Headset-Based Interaction

The *headset-based interaction* is, as the name suggests, mostly based on a HMD. In most VR applications this is a headset that completely encloses the user's field of view and, thus, has a very high degree of immersion. There are also AR headsets that do not shield the user's field of view, but only extend it. However, in this analysis, we assume a HMD that completely encloses the user's field of view. State-of-the-art HMDs offer six DOF, as mentioned in section 3.4.1. This means that they offer the user the possibility to move freely in space. This alone does not offer any real advantages for interaction with a conceptual model, except that movement in a model is already possible in this way.

Some HMDs have built-in buttons that can be used to interact with a model, like those of a 3D mouse. Most of the time the number of available buttons is small, and therefore, a HMD does not offer an optimal interaction possibility via buttons.

Another way to interact is through the perspective. For example, a HMD can use a so-called raycast. Due to position tracking and the tilt angle of the HMD, this works similar to a 3D mouse pointer (figure 4.4). By calculating a vector based on the user's position and angle of view, a targeted object can be identified. Predefined functions can then be used to interact with the VR environment or the object. These functions can be triggered by pressing a button on the HMD, by how long the user looks at the object, or by performing a specific, predefined movement.

Figure 4.4: Example of a gaze-based interaction in VR. (Piotrowski and Nowosielski, 2019, p. 4)

As summarized in figure 4.9, a HMD alone is not suitable to conduct all the necessary interactions with a conceptual model. Nevertheless, by providing six DOF, it can contribute significantly to intuitive interaction with conceptual models in VR.

4.1.5 Other Device-Based Interaction Types

As described in section 3.4.2, several other devices can be used to interact with conceptual models in VR. However, small or function-specific devices are used more in combination with other input devices and not as stand-alone interaction possibilities. For example, a small finger ring is useful for position tracking, but not for other interactions with a conceptual model. Therefore, we will not discuss such specialized devices further here.

4.2 Device-Less Interaction

In this section, we will look at the different ways to interact with conceptual models in VR without using a physical input device. In particular, we discuss the possibilities of *voice control*, *gesture-based* interaction and *eye-tracking*.

4.2.1 Voice-Based Interaction

Voice-based interaction is a type of interaction that has become a useful option in VR environments due to constantly improving technology in recent years. Thus, by using a suitable microphone and speech recognition software, a powerful tool for interaction with conceptual models can be created. An example of the functions of such a speech assistant is the “Google Assistant” (Bhanuabhiram et al., 2019). This allows to recognize spoken language and to react to it by means of artificial intelligence.

Such voice-based interactions enable many of the functions required for the modeling of conceptual models in VR. For this purpose, certain keywords must be defined in the software, which trigger the different interactions. For example, objects, relations, or attributes can be created, manipulated, or deleted. In addition, all other functions that are needed are conceivable, if the function has been implemented and can be formulated by a voice command.

One problem that occurs during speech recognition is the interpretation of the speech by the software (see section 2.3.3). The language is interpreted by a machine. This is done with algorithms defined in the implementation of the speech recognition software. However, it is currently not easily possible to interpret the context of a speech statement contextually correctly. Hence, only functions implemented by the developer of the software can be interpreted. Technically, as shown in figure 4.9, all interaction possibilities necessary for conceptual modeling are available with voice-based interaction.

4.2.2 Gesture-Based Interaction

An interaction possibility, which we have already seen in section 3.4.2 is the *gesture-based* interaction. Here again, no input device in the conventional sense is used. It is rather about interpreting gestures of the hands, or in some cases other parts of the body, and thereby inter-

acting with the VR environment.

In conceptual modeling in 3D, such gestures can be used to manipulate a model. As shown in figure 4.9, all essential interaction possibilities are available. A big advantage of gesture-based interactions is that they are usually very intuitive since movements can be used which the user needs in his daily life. For example, as in figure 3.17, an object can be grabbed and manipulated. Furthermore, gestures can be used to point at objects or to move in space. Other functions can also be carried out by pre-defined movements or gestures. For example, by touching a virtual button, an object can be selected, moved, inserted, deleted, or attributed (figure 4.5).

Figure 4.5: Example of a possible gesture-based attribution. (<http://blog.leapmotion.com/6-principles-of-interaction-design>, visited on 30.04.2020)

A general problem in VR is the attribution of objects by text attributes. As we will see in the further process of this thesis, a combination of a virtual keyboard and gesture-based interaction is possible. Since we have, in the past, not considered the virtual keyboard as an interaction possibility that can be integrated, text input with gesture-based interaction alone is not possible. The virtual keyboard is analyzed in section 4.2.4 as an independent interaction possibility.

4.2.3 Eye-Tracking-Based Interaction

Another, very similar way to headset-based interaction is by using *eye-tracking*. For that, a device must be worn on the user's head. This is usually achieved in combination with a HMD if it supports this function. A camera inside the HMD is used to film the eyes and it can be calculated where the user is looking. Since it is about the movements of the eyes, we do not consider eye-tracking as device-based interaction. The functionalities are the same as with ray-casting, which was described in section 4.1.4. In this case, not the viewing angle of the HMD is used, but the viewing direction of the eyes themselves.

The interaction possibilities of eye-tracking are relatively limited without combination with other interaction methods. It is possible that other functions can be performed in the VR environment in addition to the targeted object. For example, specific movements of the eyes or blinking can trigger different interactions. However, this is not very intuitive and especially not comfortable for the user. As you can see in figure 4.9, eye-tracked interaction alone is at best only useful for creating, moving, or deleting objects.

Figure 4.6 shows an example of how eye-tracking in VR can be used for analysis purposes. Analogous to this, an interaction could be triggered by gazing at an object.

Figure 4.6: Example of using eye-tracking in VR to analyze where the user has looked most. (<http://www.vrml.ch/virtual-reality-gaze-tracking-durch-augen-anwenderschauen>, visited on 30.04.2020)

4.2.4 Virtual-Keyboard-Based Interaction

In the previous sections, we have often talked about the possibility of assigning text attributes to objects. Unfortunately, this is mostly not possible with the standard input devices that we have seen so far. In most cases, a keyboard is used to enable the user to enter text. Since in an immersive virtual environment one does usually not see the real environment, the use of a physical keyboard is often difficult. In such cases, a *virtual keyboard* can provide the solution.

Such a virtual keyboard can have different forms. It is possible that the virtual keyboard is an image of a physical keyboard (figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7: Example of a virtual keyboard in VR. (<https://github.com/zz85/keyboard.js>, visited on 22.04.2020)

However, this is not necessarily the case. Since the virtual keyboard need not be physically implemented, new possibilities of composing or using such a keyboard arise. For example, it is possible to use a virtual keyboard which does not interpret typing movements, but only small up and down movements of the fingers. Another well-known possibility is to use the design of a conventional keyboard, but not to type with the fingers, but to select the different keys with the help of an already mentioned raycast, thus enabling a typing substitute for the fingers (figure 4.8).

One problem of such virtual keyboards, however, is exactly this typing substitute. A virtual keyboard is not physical. That means there is no natural, haptic feedback. This is unusual and not natural for the user. Therefore, a feedback is needed when typing. This can be both visual feedback and audio feedback. With the output devices mentioned earlier in section 3.4.2, even an artificial haptic feedback would be possible.

As mentioned in the sections above, we treat the keyboard as a stand-alone input possibility. But, as shown in figure 4.9, we do not treat the virtual keyboard as a way to communicate alone with a virtual environment. Rather, the virtual keyboard is an additional interface that can be used in combination with one of the methods discussed above.

Figure 4.8: Example of a virtual keyboard in VR using a raycast for typing. (<https://github.com/rjth/>, visited on 22.04.2020)

4.3 Comparison of the Interaction Possibilities of the Different Concepts

In the previous sections of chapter 4 we have seen different concepts of how to interact with conceptual models in VR and which forms of interaction are supported. Figure 4.9 shows a summary of the different interaction concepts. It is visible which interaction concepts support which modeling function.

Interaction Concept / Modeling Function	Keyboard-based Interaction	Mouse-based Interaction	3D Mouse-based Interaction	Headset-based Interaction	Voice-based Interaction	Gesture-based Interaction	Eye-Tracking-based Interaction
Create Object	x		x	x	x	x	x
Move Object	x	(x)	x	x	x	x	x
Delete Object	x	(x)	x	x	x	x	x
Add Attribute of Object	x		x		x	x	
Modify Attribute of Object	x		x		x	x	
Delete Attribute of Object	x		x		x	x	
Create Relationship	x	(x)	x		x	x	
Modify Relationship	x	(x)	x		x	x	
Delete Relationship	x	(x)	x		x	x	
Zooming and Moving	x	x	x	x	x	x	

x = in immersive and non-immersive environments
 (x) = in non-immersive environments only

Figure 4.9: Comparison of the interaction possibilities of the different concepts.

You can see, that there are four interaction concepts, that can be used to cover all functionalities necessary for interacting with conceptual models in VR themselves. Some of the concepts

are only suitable for specific tasks and some of them are only suitable for non-immersive environments. As already mentioned in the analysis of the individual concepts, in some cases it is not ideal to implement all interactions with only one concept. Often the interaction in such a case becomes tedious and is no longer intuitive. For this reason, it is sometimes useful to combine different concepts. In this way, the most intuitive components of the various concepts can be combined, making interaction easier and more intuitive for the user.

In the following sections, the combination of the presented concepts from section 4.1 and section 4.2 will be analyzed and discussed.

4.4 Combination of Interaction Concepts

In this section, we will look at the different combinations of concepts. In section 4.4.1 we will first look at the different possible combinations. For each of these possibilities we will discuss whether it makes sense to combine the concepts. In the following sections, we will then go into the useful combinations in more detail.

4.4.1 Theoretical Matrix of the Combination of Interaction Concepts

As visible in figure 4.10, there are 21 possibilities to combine two different interaction concepts. This is independent of whether the concepts are device-based or device-less. Eventually, it is conceivable that two concepts from the same category can be combined effectively. It is also possible that there are useful combinations of more than 2 concepts. At this point, we will focus primarily on the combination of two concepts.

	Keyboard-based Interaction	Mouse-based Interaction	3D Mouse-based Interaction	Headset-based Interaction	Voice-based Interaction	Gesture-based Interaction	Eye-Tracking-based Interaction
Keyboard-based Interaction	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
Mouse-based Interaction	-	-	X	X	X	X	X
3D Mouse-based Interaction	-	-	-	X	X	X	X
Headset-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	X	X	X
Voice-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	-	X	X
Gesture-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Eye-Tracking-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

X = possible combination

Figure 4.10: Theoretical matrix for the combination of the different interaction concepts.

In the following, the various combinations are briefly explained, and the reasons are given whether or not they make sense. Afterward, the useful combinations are examined in more detail.

- **Keyboard-based Interaction - Mouse-based Interaction:**

This is probably the best-known combination of interaction concepts. As described above, the mouse is mostly only applicable in non-immersive environments, so this combination is not suitable for the given case of interaction with conceptual models in immersive environments.
- **Keyboard-based Interaction - 3D Mouse-based Interaction:**

This combination can be useful under certain circumstances. Nevertheless, it must be remembered that these are both interaction methods for which the hands are needed. This means that the user may have to put down one interaction device at a time to work with the second interaction device. This can be tedious and a combination of these two concepts is not ideal.
- **Keyboard-based Interaction - Headset-based Interaction:**

There are no problems when combining these two concepts, except when the user must press any buttons on the headset with his hands. Again, the problem would be that the user needs his hands for both concepts. However, if this is not the case, a combination of these two concepts can be quite useful.
- **Keyboard-based Interaction - Voice-based Interaction:**

This combination makes sense as well. There are no problems when using these two concepts at the same time because the voice-based interaction is not based on a physical input device. Thus, the best interaction possibilities can be used from both concepts.
- **Keyboard-based Interaction - Gesture-based Interaction:**

This combination can cause problems because in most cases the hands are needed for both concepts. It can be problematic to switch back and forth between the different interaction methods. However, if the position of the keyboard in the immersive environment can be easily located by the user, this combination can be useful.
- **Keyboard-based Interaction - Eye-Tracking-based Interaction:**

Since these two concepts require different body regions for interaction, a combination of the two concepts is unproblematic. Since the interaction with the eyes is limited, it does not represent an extreme added value for the interaction.
- **Mouse-based Interaction - 3D Mouse-based Interaction:**

The combination of these two interaction concepts must be considered rather useless. This is because the 3D mouse is an evolution of the traditional 2D mouse. Thus, the use of the 2D mouse in virtual environments is pointless if there is the possibility to use a 3D mouse.
- **Mouse-based Interaction - Headset-based Interaction:**

A combination of these two concepts is likewise not to be described as useful. Since the 2D mouse is used almost exclusively in non-immersive environments, and a HMD has as its most important feature the creation of immersion, these two concepts are contradictory.
- **Mouse-based Interaction - Voice-based Interaction:**

Interaction with speech recognition covers all important functionalities required for interaction with conceptual models in VR. As the 2D mouse with its limited possibilities in immersive environments does not add value, a combination of these two concepts is not useful.

- **Mouse-based Interaction - Gesture-based Interaction:**

A combination of a 2D mouse with gestures is only partially useful. Like in combination with the voice, there is no real added value to be achieved, additional to the interaction provided by gestures, when the two concepts are combined.

- **Mouse-based Interaction - Eye-Tracking-based Interaction:**

Since the two concepts on their own both have very limited possibilities, the combination of these two concepts does not enable full interaction with conceptual models in VR. That is why this combination is not reasonable.

- **3D Mouse-based Interaction - Headset-based Interaction:**

The combination of a 3D mouse and the HMD is a possible way to interact in VR. Most of the functionalities for conceptual modeling in VR are provided by a 3D mouse. By combining it with headset-based interaction, these functions can be partially extended. However, due to the limited possibilities for interaction via HMD, the combination does not bring a significant simplification of the interaction.

- **3D Mouse-based Interaction - Voice-based Interaction:**

These two interaction concepts are both very powerful and they both cover the main functions of conceptual modeling in VR. As these two concepts do not interfere with each other and are completely independent, a combination of these two concepts can enable a very intuitive and useful interaction.

- **3D Mouse-based Interaction - Gesture-based Interaction:**

Both of these two concepts are very powerful in their interaction. However, both concepts require the use of hands for interaction with the VR environment. Since it is not easy to switch between the two forms of interaction, this combination is not very suitable for the interaction with conceptual models in VR.

- **3D Mouse-based Interaction - Eye-Tracking-based Interaction:**

The combination of these two concepts is very similar to the combination between the 3D mouse and the HMD. New interaction possibilities may arise, but the added value of the combination of eye-tracking and 3D mouse is questionable.

- **Headset-based Interaction - Voice-based Interaction:**

A disadvantage of interaction with the help of a HMD is the lack of manipulation possibilities. To solve this problem, voice-based interaction can be used to add missing functionalities for interaction. For this reason, this is a reasonable combination. Yet, the question arises why one should completely abandon the use of hands if one had them available.

- **Headset-based Interaction - Gesture-based Interaction:**

This combination can be quite useful. Nonetheless, it should be noted that the most intuitive function of the two concepts is probably the function of selecting objects. For example, by pointing at an object with your finger, or by looking at an object for a longer time. These two concepts have the same focus, which is why they do not complement each other ideally.

- **Headset-based Interaction - Eye-Tracking-based Interaction:**

These two concepts generally support the same functions for interaction with conceptual models in VR. These functions are very limited, why this combination is not useful.

• **Voice-based Interaction - Gesture-based Interaction:**

These are both full-fledged concepts for interaction with models in VR. Furthermore, they do not restrict each other. That is why this is a very useful combination of two concepts. Thus, a combination of both concepts allows using the better functionality of both, which in the end allows a more intuitive and easier interaction.

• **Voice-based Interaction - Eye-Tracking-based Interaction:**

Speech-based interaction offers very good possibilities for interaction in VR. A disadvantage of voice control is that you must describe exactly what you want to achieve by means of the language. For example, it is difficult to select an object. This can be simplified in certain areas by a combination with eye-tracking. These two concepts eliminate the mutual weaknesses of the other concept. A combination is, consequently, quite useful. Again, the question arises why one should not use hands.

• **Gesture-based Interaction - Eye-Tracking-based Interaction:**

The combination of these two concepts is basically the same as the combination of gesture-based interaction and interaction via HMD. A combination is feasible but not very useful.

4.4.2 Useful Combinations

It is visible in figure 4.11, the above analysis results in eight useful combinations consisting of two different interaction concepts.

	Keyboard-based Interaction	Mouse-based Interaction	3D Mouse-based Interaction	Headset-based Interaction	Voice-based Interaction	Gesture-based Interaction	Eye-Tracking-based Interaction
Keyboard-based Interaction	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
Mouse-based Interaction	-	-	X	X	X	X	X
3D Mouse-based Interaction	-	-	-	X	X	X	X
Headset-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	X	X	X
Voice-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	-	X	X
Gesture-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Eye-Tracking-based Interaction	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

X = possible combination
 useful combination

Figure 4.11: Visualization of useful combinations of the different concepts.

These combinations are:

- **Keyboard-based Interaction with Headset-based Interaction**
- **Keyboard-based Interaction with Voice-based Interaction**
- **Keyboard-based Interaction with Gesture-based Interaction**
- **3D Mouse-based Interaction with Voice-based Interaction**
- **Headset-based Interaction with Voice-based Interaction**

- **Headset-based Interaction with Gesture-based Interaction**
- **Voice-based Interaction with Gesture-based Interaction**
- **Voice-based Interaction with Eye-tracking-based Interaction**

This does not mean that these combinations have ever been implemented in the context of VR, or in particular for conceptual modeling in VR. Rather, this analysis is intended to show how, through a general consideration of the various concepts and their possibilities, new and perhaps better concepts can be derived. The goal of this thesis is to identify good interaction concepts for conceptual modeling in VR and to implement some of these concepts.

Conceptual modeling in VR is an area for which not many implementations exist yet. In the following section, three concepts of interaction are considered in detail and their implementation is described. These implementations are not necessarily combinations of different concepts, but can also be stand-alone concepts, which are interesting in the context of conceptual modeling in VR.

5 Implementation and Evaluation of Selected Concepts

This chapter deals with the implementation of three prototypes for interaction with conceptual models in VR. In the first step, the VR environment and technologies used for this purpose are described. In a second step, the individual prototypes are analyzed in detail. In each case, we will go into the components used, the implementation, and some specific examples are presented. Finally, the individual concepts are evaluated.

5.1 Selected Concepts

Since not all concepts discussed could be implemented, the selection was limited to three concepts. These three concepts were implemented in the context of this thesis. These are not only conceptual implementations for illustration purposes but also functional prototypes.

As the analysis of the different concepts has shown that some stand-alone concepts are already very well suited for interaction with conceptual models in VR, two stand-alone concepts and one combination of two concepts have been implemented. Those are the following:

- **Prototype with Keyboard-based Interaction**
- **Prototype with Gesture-based Interaction**
- **Prototype with a Combination of 3D Mouse-based Interaction and Voice-based Interaction**

As can be seen in figure 4.9 from chapter 4, these are all concepts that support all required functions for interaction with conceptual models in VR. This is the reason why these three concepts can be considered as very promising and why they have been identified in this thesis as the three most important concepts. This is why they were selected for the implementation of a prototype.

5.2 Selected VR Environment

For the implementation of these three prototypes, an environment was required which offers as many possibilities for VR development as possible, but also must be very resource-efficient. Three.js offers this possibility. Three.js is an easy to use, lightweight, 3D library with a default WebGL renderer (Angel et al., 2018). According to the developers of WebGL, the KhronosGroup, WebGL is described as follows:

“WebGL is a cross-platform, royalty-free web standard for a low-level 3D graphics API based on OpenGL ES, exposed to ECMAScript via the HTML5 Canvas element. WebGL brings plugin-free 3D to the web, implemented right into the browser.”¹

Three.js is often confused with *WebGL*, because *three.js* almost exclusively uses WebGL to draw 3D content. WebGL is a very low-level system that uses only points, lines, and triangles. Usually, a lot of code is required to create anything useful with WebGL. This is exactly where *three.js* comes into play. *Three.js* provides an interface to WebGL. It takes over tasks like scenes, lights, shadows, materials, textures, 3D math, and many other things one would have to write yourself if one would use WebGL directly. The biggest advantage of *three.js* and WebGL is that one only needs a computer and a web browser. All 3D content is displayed directly in the browser. Another advantage is that one can display very complex 3D content with inexpensive hardware. This is mostly not possible with other 3D environments, because they use much more resources than WebGL (Dirksen, 2014, p.20-41).

Three.js can display 3D content on a standard 2D screen as, well as transfer it to VR devices. For the use of immersive VR devices, an additional Application-Programming-Interface (API) is required. This is the “WebXR Device API” and it is described in the *MDN Web Docs* as follows:

“WebXR is a group of standards which are used together to support rendering 3D scenes to hardware designed for presenting virtual worlds (virtual reality, or VR), or for adding graphical imagery to the real world, (augmented reality, or AR). The WebXR Device API implements the core of the WebXR feature set, managing the selection of output devices, render the 3D scene to the chosen device at the appropriate frame rate, and manage motion vectors created using input controllers.”²

A *HMD* set was used to display these *three.js* contents via the “WebXR Device API”. This is from the manufacturer HTC and it is called “HTC Vive Pro”. It can be seen in figure 5.1. The main components of this set are the *HMD* and the *3D controllers*. In addition, the set requires at least one *bluetooth base station* to support six DOF.

The 3D controllers are an interaction concept in themselves, which is why we do not call them a basic component of the VR environment here. Figure 5.2 shows the structure of the VR environment and its components. In summary, we can say that for the development of the different prototypes the 3D renderer of WegGL was used as basis. Using the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) and the scripting language *JavaScript*, the specific components of the VR environment were programmed based on *three.js*. This environment can then be rendered with the API WebXR over a HMD, in this case, the HTC Vive Pro.

5.2.1 Selected Development Approach

For the implementation of the VR environment on a technical level, a generic structure was used. For the development, a *local web server* was chosen. The code was written in a HTML document and the JavaScript code was embedded directly in this document. To use the *three.js*

¹<https://www.khronos.org/webgl>, visited on 30.04.2020

²<https://wiki.developer.mozilla.org/>, visited on 30.04.2020

Figure 5.1: HTC Vive Pro Kit. (<https://vive.com>, visited on 29.04.2020)

Figure 5.2: Graphical representation of the environment.

library, the latest repository of the library was stored in the root folder of the local web server. There is also a folder with all additional JavaScript libraries and a folder for the 3D models that were created for use in the VR environment. Figure 5.3 shows this generic folder structure for the development of the three prototypes.

```

|
|   index.html
|
+---js
|   anyyang.min.js
|   keyboard.js
|   leap-1.0.0.js
|   leap-plugins-0.1.11pre.js
|   leap-plugins-0.1.12.js
|   leap-widgets-0.1.0.js
|   stats.min.js
|   VRKeyboard.js
|
+---models
|   Attribute.glb
|   Entity.glb
|   Relation.glb
|
\---three
|
|   +---build
|   |   three.js
|   |   three.min.js
|   |   three.module.js
|   |
|   +---...

```

Figure 5.3: Generic folder structure for the development of the three prototypes.

5.2.2 Standard Use Case

A standard use case was defined for all three prototypes. This represents a VR environment in which it is possible to create ER diagrams. In this environment, you are in an infinite space, like the universe. In front of the user, a flat hovers, above which the respective objects are displayed. The standard use case, thus, consists of a space with objects of type entity, relation, and attribute. Figure 5.4 shows this standard environment, which can be perceived by the user via the HMD in 3D representation. All three prototypes have this standard environment as their starting point. This standard use case was defined in the index file (see section 5.2.1) and could be used for all three prototypes.

Figure 5.4: Representation of the standard use case. All objects are always facing the user.

5.2.3 Implementation of Standard Functionalities

For the development of the specific prototypes, some basic functionalities had to be given. The functions that allow interaction with the ER model had to be implemented first. This aspect is not specific for a prototype and an attempt was made, to design the functions in such a way, that they could be used as the basis for all prototypes. These are mainly the functions which are necessary for interaction with conceptual models in VR. These functionalities were already discussed in chapter 2.4. Here we will go into detail about the different functionalities and how they were implemented for the interaction in VR.

- **Create Object:** To create an object, a file with the format GLTF was created for each class. This is a 3D format, which is supported by three.js, and therefore, can be integrated into the VR environment. For each class, a function was implemented, which adds the corresponding object to the environment when called.
- **Move Object:** To move an object, a function had to be implemented which changes the 3D positions of the respective object by the desired parameter. Which interaction is used to access this function is a question of the interaction concept.
- **Delete Object:** To delete an object, it simply must be removed from the scene. This function can easily be called from the respective interaction concept.
- **Add Attribute of Object:** For the three prototypes, we will limit the attribution to text attributes. This is probably the most difficult attribute type to implement, compared to 2D modeling, where this can be achieved by using the normal keyboard. Several functions were implemented to achieve this feature. The user must provide a string and the desired object when calling the function. A 3D object of the text is then created in the background and attached to the source object. It must be checked in each case whether the selected object already has an attribute. If this is the case, it is deleted and replaced by the new attribute.
- **Modify or Delete Attribute of Object:** To modify or delete a text attribute, the same function is used as when an attribute is assigned. This attribute will be overwritten as

explained in the last step. If one wants to delete the attribute, it is replaced by an empty string.

- **Create Relationship:** A line is used to connect two objects. *WebGL*, or more precisely, *three.js* provides a function to draw a line between two points. Additionally, a function had to be implemented which draws such a line between two given objects, i.e. calculates the points of the line to be drawn.
- **Modify Relationship:** It also had to be ensured that a line is updated as soon as the associated objects are moved. For the three prototypes, there is no other way to modify a relationship.
- **Delete Relationship:** To delete a relationship, a function was needed which checks if there is a relationship between two objects. If so, it can be removed from the scene when the function is called with the given parameters.
- **Zooming and Moving:** For moving within a scene, *three.js* offers several possibilities. These are mostly designed for the use of a 2D mouse and a normal screen. Since the three prototypes use a HMD that supports six DOF, the functionality for moving within a scene is already given naturally.

The functions just described form the core of the implementation along with the standard use case (figure 5.4) described above. This core remains generally the same for all three prototypes and is only slightly modified if the interaction methods for a specific concept require it. The complete code is attached in the appendix.

5.3 Implementation of Concept 1: Keyboard-Based Interaction

The implementation of the first concept is about keyboard-based interaction. This means that all interactions in the VR environment can be achieved using a keyboard. As mentioned before, one of the main problems with keyboard interaction in immersive VR environments is the isolation of the user from the outside world. The keyboard is part of this environment, and therefore, had to be made accessible to the user somehow. To understand this process, we must first look at the components used.

5.3.1 Used Components

For the implementation of this prototype, other components were needed besides the VR environment (see section 5.2). The goal was to integrate an image of the physical keyboard into the VR environment. This was achieved by video recording the keyboard from a bird's eye view. To implement this, a keyboard, a camera tripod, and a webcam had to be used in addition to the standard hardware. Figure 5.5 shows the setup as it was used for this prototype.

5.3.2 Implementation

For the image of the keyboard in the VR environment, a *three.js* object of a surface was created, which is always positioned at the same distance from the user at the lower edge of the field of

Figure 5.5: Used components for the prototype for keyboard-based interaction.

view. Finally, the video stream of the webcam was projected onto this cube, giving the impression that the keyboard is also integrated into the virtual environment.

In addition to displaying the video in the VR environment, all functionalities described in section 5.2.2 had to be accessible via the keyboard. For that reason, different keys were defined as triggers for the respective functionalities. Figure 5.6 shows the different key combinations and the corresponding functions.

Key Combination	Function
Delete	show all possible key combinations
Esc	show / hide the log window
Alt + 1	delete selected object
Alt + 2	insert entity object
Alt + 3	insert attribute object
Alt + 4	insert relation object
Right Key	change selection of first object (next)
Left Key	change selection of first object (previous)
ctrl	change selection of second object
Enter	set text attribute
TAB + Arrow	move selected object (x and y axis only)
Down Key	connect two selected objects
Up Key	disconnect two selected objects
backspace	delete last character
all other keys	to write a text attribute

Figure 5.6: Possible key combinations for the prototype for keyboard-based interaction.

5.3.3 Examples

In this section, some examples from the VR environment are illustrated and briefly described.

Figure 5.7 shows the initial screen that the user sees when starting a project. This includes the standard use case, as well as the video object with the image of the physical keyboard. Above the keyboard, there is an area that represents the log of the application and shows the user the interaction possibilities.

Figure 5.7: Example of the initial screen. The standard use case is visible, as is the keyboard.

Figure 5.8 shows how the selection of different objects works. The primary object is always the red object. All primary functions such as the attribution or movement of an object are related to the primary object. The purple object is always the second object selected. It is mainly used to create or delete connections between two objects.

Figure 5.9 is an example of the attribution of an object. On the left side, you can see what an object looks like that has been given the text attribute “Duck”. On the right side, you can see how the log window renders the written text in real-time, so you can see what you wrote.

5.3.4 Evaluation

In this section, the prototype is evaluated based on three categories: *Usability and intuitiveness*, *performance*, and *accuracy*. This evaluation refers to the interaction with the VR environment.

Figure 5.8: Example of the first selected object (red) and the second selected object (purple).

Figure 5.9: Example of an attributed object (left) and the log window that shows what you are writing (right).

Usability and Intuitiveness

For most users of modeling software, the keyboard is probably a familiar way of interacting with a program. Thus, even when VR modeling with a physical keyboard, many of the workflows are like those in 2D modeling environments.

A disadvantage of integrating an image of the physical keyboard is the lack of a third dimension. The entire environment is in 3D, except for the video projection. This can be confusing and sometimes it is difficult to find the right position of the fingers on the keyboard. In addition, the projection of the keyboard in the VR environment is always in the same place, relative to

the user. When the user moves around in the VR environment, the physical keyboard is not always in the same position relative to the user. This makes it difficult for the user to find the keyboard, and ideally, the user must always sit in front of the keyboard.

An advantage of this method compared to a completely virtual image of a physical keyboard is that the user can see his own hands in the video and thus has at least a rough idea of the position of his fingers. With a fully virtual image, this would not be the case and the user would have to rely much more on his sense of touch.

In summary, it can be said that this prototype has a good usability due to the already known way of using a keyboard. Since the non-3D image of the keyboard can cause confusion in the VR environment and the finger position is not always clear at first sight, this prototype cannot be described as highly intuitive.

Performance

If one knows the keyboard well and is familiar with touch typing, one can work very quickly with a physical keyboard. At the beginning of use, one will certainly have to get used to some of the key combinations, because normally not all tasks are performed with the keyboard. After a short period of getting used to it, one can work quite quickly. That is why the performance of this prototype can be described as very good.

Accuracy

By physically pressing a key on a keyboard, the keyboard causes no interpretation difficulties for the VR environment. Either a key is pressed or not. This approach is very accurate, which is why the prototype can be described as highly accurate.

5.4 Implementation of Concept 2: Gesture-Based Interaction

The second prototype is about gesture-based interaction. This prototype is not a combination of several interaction concepts, but only an implementation of one concept. This concept was already described in section 4.2.2.

The aim of this is to allow the user to interact with the VR environment and the conceptual model without any input devices. This possibility of interaction is extremely intuitive because the user can take all necessary movements directly from daily life. The components necessary to implement this concept are presented below.

5.4.1 Used Components

In this case, exactly one additional device was required for gesture-based interaction in VR. This device is called “Leap Motion Controller” (Nandy, 2016). The device is a hand tracking device and can detect the movements of the hands very precisely. It requires little power, has a wide field of view, and almost no latency. This allows human interactions in the digital world to be implemented naturally and intuitively.

Since this concept is about interaction in VR, one goal was to restrict the user as little as possible when moving around in the virtual environment. The Leap Motion Controller is usually placed on the desk in front of the user, so the user's gestures can be recorded and analyzed from below. Since the user is wearing a HMD in this case, the Leap Motion Controller could be attached directly to the user's HMD, allowing for full freedom of movement. Figure 5.10 shows how the Leap Motion Controller setup was used in combination with the HTC Vive Pro. Yet, using the Leap Motion Controller is not just about interpreting user gestures. An image of the hands can also be visualized. An example of such a visualization of hands was already shown in section 3.4.2 in figure 3.17.

Figure 5.10: Setup of the Leap Motion Controller in combination with the HTC Vive Pro. (<https://ultraleap.com>, visited on 15.04.2020)

Apart from the Leap Motion Controller and the HMD, no other components were needed to implement this concept.

5.4.2 Implementation

During the implementation of this concept, some challenges arose. In contrast to the first prototype, which uses a physical keyboard, this concept has no physical input devices that the user can use. All interactions had to be done by gestures via the Leap Motion Controller. An approach was followed in which all interactions are performed by pressing a virtual button or key with one of the index fingers.

In addition to the buttons for direct manipulation of the model, a way had to be created to assign text attributes to the individual objects of the element. Since there is no physical keyboard in this virtual environment, an alternative had to be found. As this alternative, a virtual keyboard was used. This was developed in three.js and was used in its original form to click on the corresponding keys on a 2D screen with the mouse. Since the 2D mouse was not available for this prototype, the interaction with this keyboard had to be extended.

Two extensions were made for this purpose. The position of the index fingers always had to be known to determine if one of the fingers collided with a key or button. The standard functionality of the Leap Motion Controller is not designed for use in three.js, so an extension

had to be implemented. Since the position of the fingers was always known through the interface to the Leap Motion Controller, an invisible three.js object was attached to each of the two index fingers. This object was used for the second extension. For this purpose, a function was implemented that constantly checks whether one of the objects on the fingers collides with a button or a key in the VR environment. If this is the case, the corresponding interaction can be triggered. Figure 5.11 shows all interaction possibilities to interact with the conceptual model in this prototype.

Button to press	Function
keyboar F12	show all possible key combinations
on / off button	show / hide the log window
delete button	delete selected object
add entity button	insert entity object
add attribute button	insert attribute object
add relation button	insert relation object
next button	change selection of first object (next)
prev button	change selection of first object (previous)
2. obj button	change selection of second object
return key	set text attribute
up / right / down / left button	move selected object (x and y axis only)
connect button	connect two selected objects
disconnect button	disconnect two selected objects
delete button	delete last character
keyboard character key	to write a text attribute

Figure 5.11: Possible buttons to press for interaction in prototype 2.

5.4.3 Examples

In this section, we will look at some examples of interaction with a conceptual model from the second prototype.

Figure 5.12 shows on the left side how the scene looks like when the user starts a project. By default, the keyboard and the log are shown. On the right side, you can see what the scene looks like when the user clicks the “off” button. Then the keyboard and the log disappear, and the user sees the default use case, as well as all buttons necessary for interaction with the conceptual model.

In figure 5.13 we see two further interaction possibilities. On the left side, we see how the user can select an object. To do this he must press the button “next” or “prev”. A selected object becomes red and is, thereby, distinguishable from the objects which are not selected. On

Figure 5.12: Initial screen with keyboard and log enabled (left) or disabled (right).

the right side, we see the situation where the user has inserted a new object by clicking on “add attribute”. By pressing the “up” button, the object is moved up. This function is available for all directions of the x- and y-axis

Figure 5.13: Selection of an object (left) or move a new object (right).

The last example is about assigning a text attribute to an object. To do this, the user must type in the desired text attribute as shown in figure 5.14 on the left side. By clicking on the “return” button, the text attribute is assigned to the selected object. The result of the interaction is shown on the right side.

5.4.4 Evaluation

This section is about evaluating the prototype for gesture-based interaction. As with the first prototype, we will evaluate the *usability and intuitiveness*, *performance*, and *accuracy* of the prototype.

Figure 5.14: Write on the virtual keyboard (left) or view after the attribute was set to the object (right).

Usability and Intuitiveness

Since the user does not need an additional input device compared to almost all common interaction methods, this concept is very extraordinary. It is amazing how intuitive the movements of the virtual hands feel in the VR environment. Also, the distance of the hands relative to the body can be estimated very well. Therefore, one can certainly say that this prototype is very intuitive and user friendly.

Performance

If you look at the performance of this prototype, it performs relatively poorly compared to other concepts. The problem with this concept is that there is no haptic feedback for the virtual hands in 3D space. This makes it extremely difficult for the user to judge whether the desired button or key has already been pressed or not. As a result, not every attempt at input works the first time, which significantly reduces the performance of the interaction.

Accuracy

There are some problems with the accuracy of this prototype. Since the interactions of the buttons and keys are triggered by a function that checks all elements for a collision of the index fingers, delays sometimes occur. This is because this function is constantly retriggered to check for collisions again. If one configures this interval of checking too short, the handling of the interaction is very difficult. This is comparable to the touch time of a physical keyboard. If one presses the same key for too long, the interaction is triggered several times. The opposite is also not optimal, because if the collision check is too infrequent, some interactions may not be triggered at all. Since the implementation is a prototype, not much time was spent on optimizing the processes.

It is worth mentioning that by optimizing the already mentioned functions, both the performance and the accuracy of this prototype could be significantly improved. In this case, the interaction with this concept would be a very intuitive, as well as a performant and accurate way to interact with conceptual models in VR.

5.5 Implementation of Concept 3: Voice Control and 3D Mouse

This prototype is the only prototype that combines two different concepts from chapter 4. These are the concepts of *3D mouse-based* interaction and *voice-based* interaction. As can be seen in figure 4.9 from Chapter 4, these two concepts are full-fledged concepts for interacting with conceptual models in VR. These two concepts, as described in section 4.4.1, do not limit each other, and therefore, complement each other very well. Therefore, they were chosen for the implementation of the third prototype.

As in the sections for the previous prototypes, the following sections describe the used components, explain the challenges of the implementation, illustrate some examples of the prototype, and provide an evaluation.

5.5.1 Used Components

To implement this prototype, the standard environment with the HTC Vive HMD was used again. In addition to this HMD, the HTC Vive kit also contains two *3D mice* (see figure 5.1). Since these 3D mice represent a concept of their own for interaction in VR, they were not counted among the standard components of the VR environment. However, in this prototype, they were used for the concept of *3D mouse-based interaction*.

To implement a speech assistant, as described in section 3.4.2, one only needs a microphone. The HTC Vive HMD has a microphone built-in by default. This turned out to be too bad. Therefore, the webcam used in the first prototype was used for the recording of speech. The built-in microphone of the webcam provided a good recording quality even at longer distances. So, it did not have to be worn by the user. Nevertheless, a microphone worn directly by the user would be better for even more accurate audio recording.

Apart from these components, no other equipment was required for the implementation of this prototype.

5.5.2 Implementation

The implementation of the third prototype consists of two main parts. One is the implementation of the functions for the interaction with the 3D mouse and the other is the implementation for voice-based interaction. Figure 5.15 shows which of the interactions required for conceptual modeling are covered by which concept. The focus of this prototype is mainly on voice-based interaction. Since the HMD already supports movement in the VR environment, this function is not covered by either concept in this prototype.

For the interaction with the 3D mouse, a WebXR integration of the 3D mouse was used. This represents an image of the 3D mouse in the VR environment. This image can be positioned correctly in the VR environment by the different sensors on the 3D mouse. For the interaction with objects in the VR environment, more precisely for the selection and manipulation of objects, a raycaster was used. This interaction was already described in section 4.1.3. A vector is calculated starting from the 3D mouse, which is visually represented by a line. An event listener can be used to monitor, whether this vector overlaps with an object in the scene. If this is

Interaction Concept \ Modeling Function	3D Mouse-based Interaction	Voice-based Interaction
Create Object		X
Move Object	X	
Delete Object		X
Add Attribute of Object		X
Modify Attribute of Object		X
Delete Attribute of Object		X
Create Relationship		X
Modify Relationship		X
Delete Relationship		X
Zooming and Moving		

x = concept needed for modeling function

Figure 5.15: Modeling functions covered by the two interaction concepts 3D mouse-based interaction and voice-based interaction.

the case, the corresponding object can be selected by pressing a button on the 3D mouse. By holding the button, the object can be moved, like the drag-and-drop function of a 2D mouse. Figure 5.16 shows a code snippet for the initialization of the 3D mice.

```
//init controller1 and add to user
controller1 = renderer.xr.getController(0);
controller1.addEventListener('selectstart', onSelectStart);
controller1.addEventListener('selectend', onSelectEnd);
user.add(controller1);

//init controller2 and add to user
controller2 = renderer.xr.getController(1);
controller2.addEventListener('selectstart', onSelectStart);
controller2.addEventListener('selectend', onSelectEnd);
user.add(controller2);

controllerModelFactory = new XRControllerModelFactory();

//add visual representation of controller 1 to scene
controllerGrip1 = renderer.xr.getControllerGrip(0);
controllerGrip1.add(controllerModelFactory.createControllerModel(controllerGrip1));
user.add(controllerGrip1);

//add visual representation of controller 2 to scene
controllerGrip2 = renderer.xr.getControllerGrip(1);
controllerGrip2.add(controllerModelFactory.createControllerModel(controllerGrip2));
user.add(controllerGrip2);

//create vector for raycaster line
geometry = new THREE.BufferGeometry().setFromPoints([new THREE.Vector3(0, 0, 0), new THREE.Vector3(0, 0, -100)]);
line = new THREE.Line(geometry);
line.name = 'line';
line.scale.z = 5;

//add raycaster lines to controllers
controller1.add(line.clone());
controller2.add(line.clone());

raycasterForController = new THREE.Raycaster();
tempMatrix = new THREE.Matrix4();
```

Figure 5.16: Code snippet for the initialization of the 3D mice in the VR environment.

The second part of the implementation of this prototype consists of implementing the language assistant. For this, the open-source speech recognition API “annyang!” from talater was used.³ A JavaScript library from talater was integrated into the code. This allows configuring a language assistant with only a few lines of code. You can define your functions that respond to defined keywords or sentences in the desired way. For example, a function was defined which reacts to the sentence “set name to”. As soon as this sentence is recognized, a function is triggered, which has a string as input parameter. This string contains everything that is said after the command “set name to”. A more specific example is explained in the next section.

As can be seen in figure 5.17, most of the interactions of this prototype are triggered by speech recognition. For most of the functions, all that was needed was to implement how the interaction is triggered. Most of the basic functions could be taken from the implementation described in section 5.2.3. Major adjustments had to be made to move objects with the 3D mouse. The challenge was that the new position of the object had to be calculated and displayed in real-time. Otherwise, the user would not see where he is moving the object. This was achieved by calculating the position and orientation of the object in real-time and visualizing it in the scene. Although an object is recalculated and rendered several times per second, the minimalistic implementation in three.js kept the workload low.

Interaction	Function
say: help	show all possible key combinations
say: delete	delete selected object
say: insert entity	insert entity object
say: insert attribute	insert attribute object
say: insert relation	insert relation object
select with 3D Mouse	selection of first object
select with 3D Mouse	selection of second object
say: set name to (*)	set text attribute
push button at 3D Mouse	move selected object
say: connect	connect two selected objects
say: disconnect	disconnect two selected objects

* represents spoken words

Figure 5.17: Possible functions supported by the third prototype.

5.5.3 Examples

In this section, some examples of the third prototype are illustrated.

In figure 5.18, the scene is visible as it appears when a project is started. In the upper right corner of the user’s field of view, there is a log window that always remains visible to the user. It shows how the spoken language is interpreted and which functions are triggered by it. By

³<https://github.com/TalAter/annyang>, visited on 07.05.2020

default, all available voice commands are listed at the beginning. These commands can be listed at any time with the voice command “help”. Also visible in this figure are the two 3D mice and their raycast lines. In this example, the user has already pointed to an object and selected it by pressing the button on the back of the 3D mouse. The last two selected objects appear in red, to show which objects are selected.

Figure 5.18: Standard scene which the user sees when he starts a project.

Figure 5.19 shows how an object can be given a text attribute. First, as shown on the left side, an object must be selected. This is done by pressing the button on the back of one of the 3D mice. The voice command “set name to duck” sets the attribute “duck” in this example. On the right side of the figure, you can see that the attribute has changed and that a new entry appears in the log window. This entry lists five different interpretations of the audio recording. If there is a match with one of the defined commands, the corresponding function is executed. In this case this was the function “set name to (*)” and the additional string was “duck”. Therefore, the attribute was changed from “Entity 2” to “duck”.

Objects cannot only be selected. They can also be moved. This is done by holding the button on the back of the 3D mouse. In this case, the object is moved at the intersection of the vector of the 3D mouse and the object. This allows an object to be moved, in contrast to the previous prototypes, in all three dimensions. An example of this interaction is shown in figure 5.20 on the left. The selected object is moved to the bottom left by moving the 3D mouse accordingly. An example of how to connect two objects is illustrated on the right side. Two selected objects can be connected by the voice command “connect”. In the log window, you can see, after the executed interaction, what exactly was done. In this example, the objects “Entity 1” and “Duck” were connected.

Figure 5.19: Selection of an object (left) and an example of the scene after the attribution of an object (right).

Figure 5.20: Example of how to move an object (left) or how to connect two objects (right).

The other functions (figure 5.17) for interacting with conceptual models in the third prototype work similarly or identically to these examples.

5.5.4 Evaluation

As with the first and second prototypes, an evaluation of the third prototype is made in the following section. The points *usability and intuitiveness*, *performance*, and *accuracy* will be addressed.

Usability and Intuitiveness

The third prototype combines two independent concepts for interaction with conceptual models in VR. These two concepts both offer a high degree of intuitiveness. When interacting with the 3D mouse, a physical device can be used to point at, and interact with objects as if extend-

ing one's arm. This works very intuitively and does not require a long period of getting used to it.

The second concept is linked to the ability of the user to express what he wants to achieve through his voice by means of voice input. It is not possible for the user to freely choose how he wants to interact. He must follow the given pattern, more precisely the given commands, to interact with the VR environment by voice command. Nevertheless, this form of interaction is very intuitive and does not require any increased cognitive effort.

Overall, it can be said that the combination of these two concepts has led to a new, very intuitive, and usable concept.

Performance

The performance of this new concept is remarkable as well. The interaction with the 3D mouse is very smooth and fast, and there are no delays. The interaction by voice command is equally fast and there is only a short waiting time after the input of the voice command until the visible result appears in the VR environment. Therefore, it can be said in summary that the third prototype has a good performance.

Accuracy

At the point of accuracy, this concept is not as convincing as in the previous points. Although the interaction with the 3D mouse is extremely precise, the voice commands cannot always be interpreted correctly.

Most of the voice commands can be recognized without any problems on the first attempt. For example, creating objects or connections, as well as deleting connections or objects is possible without difficulty. However, as soon as words are used, which cannot be recognized as commands but must be recognized by the speech recognition software without any context, certain problems arise. For example, the command "set name to duck" may be interpreted differently under certain circumstances. Since on a semantic level no interpretations can be made by the speech recognition software, errors often occur. The word "duck" was only recognized with great difficulty in a test. Rather, the speech recognition software interpreted the word as "truck", "talk" or "stuck". Such errors can be reduced by an accurate and clear pronunciation and by using a microphone worn on the head of the user.

Thus, overall, the accuracy of prototype three is good but would need to be improved in certain areas of speech recognition to allow accurate modeling of conceptual models.

5.6 Extensions

The prototypes described above have all been implemented and are fully functional. The source code can be viewed in the Appendix. The prototypes are very minimalistic and not meant to work with it in daily life. In the following, some possible extensions are presented which could extend parts of the virtual modeling to a point where it becomes more imaginable to work with it daily.

Trackable Keyboard

As described in the first prototype, it can be tedious when you see an image of your keyboard in the VR environment, but this image is not visible at the actual keyboard position in the VR environment. It would make sense if the virtual image of the keyboard, be it a video image or a modeled replicate of the keyboard, would also be visible at the corresponding position in the VR environment. The user would then no longer be bound to a fixed workstation because the keyboard could be located in the VR environment at any time. This could be achieved, for example, by an external tracking device that is attached to the physical keyboard and can then be tracked in the VR environment. As visible in figure 5.21, such prototypes of virtually replicated keyboards already exist.

Figure 5.21: Example of a virtual replicated keyboard on basis of a physical keyboard. (<https://mixed.de/logitech-will-tastaturen-in-die-virtual-reality-bringen>, visited on 15.04.2020)

Virtual Operating System

One possibility to make VR experiences more pleasant for the user would be an environment where he could do all his tasks. The VR equipment would not only be used for a specific task, but all tasks could be done in a virtual environment. A prototype of such a virtual operating system was developed by Matthaeus Krenn.⁴ This prototype allows to work with the WIMP concept like on a conventional computer. The keyboard and the mouse can be used for this. At the same time, the interaction takes place in a virtual environment, which allows the user a 360-degree view and thus significantly expands the workspace. The keyboard and mouse are positioned correctly with the help of tracking devices and an image of the hands is also displayed above the keyboard (see figure 5.22).

⁴<https://matthaeuskrenn.com/vr-os/>, visited on 07.05.2020

Figure 5.22: Example of the operating system in the VR-OS by Matthaeus Krenn. (<https://matthaeuskrenn.com/vr-os/>, visited on 07.05.2020)

Figure 5.23: Example of 3D VR modeling in the VR-OS by Matthaeus Krenn. (<https://matthaeuskrenn.com/vr-os/>, visited on 07.05.2020)

Since the interaction already takes place in a VR environment, modeling environments could be implemented directly (see figure 5.23). This brings a considerable added value since two fundamentally different concepts such as working on a desktop computer and modeling in an immersive VR environment could be combined and integrated into one system. It is quite conceivable that in such an environment not only the mouse and the keyboard could be used, but also other VR input devices and interaction concepts as presented earlier.

Augmented Reality

The possibility of creating VR models has been discussed almost exclusively during this thesis so far. But there is also the possibility not to shut off the user completely from the outside world, but only to expand the reality. This AR approach is as much on the rise as VR applications and offers the advantage that the virtual and the real world merge together. It is conceivable that virtual modeling can take place in real environments and could be integrated into the real world. The question of whether this approach is better suited for the modeling of conceptual models cannot and will not be answered at this point.

6 Summarizing Evaluation

In this thesis, three prototypes were presented, which allow the creation of conceptual models, especially their attribution with text attributes, in VR environments. The three concepts were chosen by deriving interaction concepts of 2D modeling, i.e. WIMP interactions, and transferring them to VR modeling.

To achieve this derivation, some terms and sub-areas first had to be made understandable. The first step was to take a closer look at the existing concepts of Human Computer Interaction. This overview was followed by a part in which it was discussed what conceptual modeling and knowledge in relation to conceptual modeling are. From this, it could be deduced, which interaction concepts are necessary for 2D conceptual modeling to represent knowledge. Based on this analysis and the analysis of interaction concepts from conventional VR environments, it was possible to derive what interaction concepts would be possible for conceptual modeling in VR. This analysis showed that many interaction concepts can be transferred from two-dimensional space to three-dimensional space.

A big difference between 2D modeling and VR modeling of conceptual models is the immersion. This poses some challenges for the user, but even more so for the developers of a VR environment. For example, one of the most important and widespread interaction possibilities, namely keyboard interaction, is not easily implementable in VR. It was necessary to develop adapted or partially new concepts for these interactions. This was successfully done in the context of this thesis.

Generally, it can be said that the results of the evaluation of the three prototypes can also be transferred to other modeling languages. However, the standard use case for these three prototypes refers to a relatively simple scenario. This ignores the limitations and problems that would occur in more complex scenarios or modeling languages.

By developing a modeling tool based on the JavaScript library three.js, very complex and high-level environments can be created. These environments can always be displayed on a 2D screen or by a HMD. Thus, the portability of such an application is no problem and it would be accessible to a wide audience without expensive hardware. However, as soon as the modeling is to take place in immersive virtual environments, a HMD or other immersive output device is required. This is usually costly and not accessible to a wide audience at this stage.

Since this work is an exploratory work and no empirical study was done, it cannot be answered conclusively at this point whether such a virtual modeling environment is an equal or better option than conceptual modeling in 2D environments. However, the transfer of the interaction concepts from the two-dimensional environment to the three-dimensional environment opens up many new interaction possibilities that were not available so far.

7 Limitations and Outlook

Like most exploratory studies, this investigation has some limitations and gives direction for further research.

First, it should be mentioned that no empirical study has been carried out for the evaluation of the various prototypes. The goal of this exploratory investigation was to achieve analytical, rather than statistical derivations and generalizations. Furthermore, the selected prototypes are not conclusive and many other concepts could have been implemented.

Furthermore, it should be noted that the derivations and conclusions made in this thesis are based on literature from the field of *Human Computer Interaction* and *conceptual modeling*. It is quite conceivable that other possibilities could be derived in another way, which were not considered in this thesis. In addition, for the derivation of the concepts, the emphasis was often placed on the textual attribution of objects. It must be considered that there are many other important aspects of conceptual modeling that have to be considered for a final evaluation.

Based on the first evaluation of the prototypes presented in this thesis, it seems to be recommendable to conduct further investigations in the field of conceptual modeling for VR environments. The further development of virtual modeling environments could well create added value for certain research areas and the economy. Thereby, existing problems could be reduced or eliminated.

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A Code of Concept 1

```
1 <html>
2
3 <head>
4   <meta charset="utf-8">
5   <style>
6     body {
7       margin: 0;
8       overflow: hidden;
9     }
10  </style>
11 </head>
12
13 <body>
14   <div id="container"></div>
15   <script src="three/build/three.js"></script>
16   <script src="../../js/leap-1.0.0.js"></script>
17   <script src="../../js/leap-plugins-0.1.12.js"></script>
18   <script src="../../js/leap-widgets-0.1.0.js"></script>
19   <script src="../../js/VRKeyboard.js"></script>
20   <script src="../../js/keyboard.js"></script>
21   <script src="../../js/stats.min.js"></script>
22
23
24
25
26
27
28   <script type="module">
29
30     import * as THREE from '../three/build/three.module.js';
31     import { VRButton } from '../three/examples/jsm/webxr/VRButton.js';
32     import { GLTFLoader } from '../three/examples/jsm/loaders/GLTFLoader.js';
33     import { OrbitControls } from '../three/examples/jsm/controls/OrbitControls.js';
34     import { SVGLoader } from '../three/examples/jsm/loaders/SVGLoader.js';
35     import { XRControllerModelFactory } from '../three/examples/jsm/webxr/XRControllerModelFactory';
36
37     import "../../js/annyang.min.js";
38
39     //-----
40     //Global Variables
41     //-----
42
43     var camera, scene, renderer;
44     var geometry, material, mesh;
45     var controls;
46     var stats;
47     var user;
48     var raycaster;
49     var mouse = { x: 0, y: 0 };
50     var last = Date.now();
51     var keys = [];
52     const keyboard3d = new THREE.Object3D();
53     var log_plane;
54     var push_plane;
55     var push_plane_on;
56     var push_plane_next;
57     var push_plane_prev;
```

```

58     var keyboard_visible = true;
59     var allObjects = [];
60     var selectedObj = [];
61     var selectedObj_number = 0;
62     var textureLoader;
63
64
65     var HighlightColor = new THREE.Color('red');
66     var StandardColor = new THREE.Color('white');
67     var SecondColor = new THREE.Color('darkorchid');
68
69     //this is the string for one line in the log
70     var string = "";
71
72     //variable for the performance.now() time
73     var clock = 0;
74
75
76     //init Canvas
77     //get information
78     var canvas;
79     canvas = document.getElementById('myCanvas');
80     canvas.width = 2048;//horizontal resolution (?) - increase for better looking text
81     canvas.height = 2048;//vertical resolution (?) - increase for better looking text
82     canvas.style.width = canvas.width;//actual width of canvas
83     canvas.style.height = canvas.height;//actual height of canvas
84     var ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
85
86     //array with all log elements to draw
87     var canvasArray = [];
88
89     //array to store the values to update lines
90     var lines = [];
91     var points = [];
92     var line;
93
94
95     //-----
96     //end of global variables
97     //-----
98
99
100
101
102
103     initStandardScene();
104     init();
105
106     animate();
107     setTimeout(function () { printHelp(); }, 3000);
108
109     function resize() {
110         window.addEventListener('resize', onWindowResize, false);
111
112         function onWindowResize() {
113
114             camera.aspect = window.innerWidth / window.innerHeight;
115             camera.updateProjectionMatrix();
116
117             renderer.setSize(window.innerWidth, window.innerHeight);

```

```

118     }
119 }
120
121
122 //initialize specific project
123 function init() {
124
125
126     //add plane for log
127     geometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(0.5, 0.5);
128     material = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ side: THREE.DoubleSide });
129     log_plane = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
130
131     updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
132     camera.add(log_plane);
133     log_plane.position.set(0, 0.02, -0.4);
134     log_plane.scale.set(0.5, 0.5, 0.5);
135     //log_plane.rotation.x += 0.2;
136
137
138
139     //add stats window to ckeck performance
140     var container = document.getElementById('container');
141     container.appendChild(renderer.domElement);
142     stats = new Stats();
143     stats.domElement.style.position = 'absolute';
144     stats.domElement.style.top = '0px';
145     document.body.appendChild(stats.domElement);
146
147     resize();
148
149
150
151     // -----
152     //add webcam plane
153     //-----
154
155     var video = document.getElementById('video');
156     var videoTexture = new THREE.VideoTexture(video);
157
158     var webcamPlaneGeometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(8, 2.25);
159     var webcamPlaneMaterial = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ map: videoTexture });
160     var webcamPlane = new THREE.Mesh(webcamPlaneGeometry, webcamPlaneMaterial);
161     webcamPlane.rotateX(-0.44159);
162
163
164     camera.add(webcamPlane);
165     webcamPlane.position.set(0, -3, -6);
166
167     //streams the video with given size
168     if (navigator.mediaDevices && navigator.mediaDevices.getUserMedia) {
169         var constraints = { video: { width: 1280, height: 360, facingMode: 'user' } };
170         navigator.mediaDevices.getUserMedia(constraints).then(function (stream) {
171             // apply the stream to the video element used in the texture
172             video.srcObject = stream;
173             video.play();
174
175             }).catch(function (error) {
176                 console.error('Unable to access the camera/webcam.', error);
177             });

```

```

178
179     } else {
180         console.error('MediaDevices interface not available.');
```

```
181     }
```

```
182
```

```
183     // end of webcam plane -----
```

```
184
```

```
185 }
```

```
186
```

```
187
```

```
188 //initialize the standard for all projects
```

```
189 function initStandardScene() {
```

```
190
```

```
191     scene = new THREE.Scene();
```

```
192
```

```
193     // add milkyWay
```

```
194     var background = new THREE.CubeTextureLoader()
```

```
195         .setPath('../three/examples/textures/cube/MilkyWay/')
```

```
196         .load(['dark-s_px.jpg', 'dark-s_nx.jpg', 'dark-s_py.jpg', 'dark-s_ny.jpg', 'dark-s_pz
```

```
197
```

```
198     scene.background = background;
```

```
199
```

```
200
```

```
201     //user needed for VR Camera
```

```
202     user = new THREE.Group();
```

```
203     user.position.set(0, 8, 30);
```

```
204     camera = new THREE.PerspectiveCamera(75, window.innerWidth / window.innerHeight, 0.1, 100
```

```
205     camera.position.set(0, 8, 30);
```

```
206     camera.lookAt(scene.position);
```

```
207
```

```
208     //add camera to user and user to scene
```

```
209     user.add(camera);
```

```
210     scene.add(user);
```

```
211
```

```
212     //define renderer
```

```
213     renderer = new THREE.WebGLRenderer();
```

```
214     renderer.setSize(window.innerWidth, window.innerHeight);
```

```
215
```

```
216     //add webxr support
```

```
217     document.body.appendChild(VRButton.createButton(renderer));
```

```
218     renderer.xr.enabled = true;
```

```
219
```

```
220     //add orbitControls
```

```
221     //controls = new OrbitControls(camera, renderer.domElement);
```

```
222
```

```
223
```

```
224     //loads the floor
```

```
225     loadFloor();
```

```
226
```

```
227     //loads gltf objects
```

```
228     loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', 10, 5, 0, "Entity 1");
```

```
229     loadGLTFObject('models/relation.glb', 0, 5, 0, "Relation 1");
```

```
230     loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', -10, 5, 0, "Entity 2");
```

```
231     loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', -15, 5, 0, "Attribute 1");
```

```
232     loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', -10, 8, 0, "Attribute 2");
```

```
233
```

```
234
```

```
235
```

```
236     // -----
```

```
237     // lights
```

```

238 //-----
239 var light = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff);
240 light.position.set(0, 190, 80);
241 scene.add(light);
242
243 var light1 = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff, 2, 50);
244 light1.position.set(camera.position);
245 light1.position.z = light1.position.z + 3;
246 scene.add(light1);
247
248 var light2 = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff, 2, 50);
249 light2.position.x = 0;
250 light2.position.y = 0;
251 light2.position.z = 16;
252 scene.add(light2);
253
254 var ambience = new THREE.AmbientLight(0x666666);
255 scene.add(ambience);
256
257
258
259 }
260 // end of init -----
261
262
263
264
265
266
267
268 // -----
269 // floor loader
270 //-----
271
272 //function to initialize the floor
273 function loadFloor() {
274     var groundGeometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(40, 40, 10, 10);
275     var groundMaterial = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ color: 0xcccccc });
276     var ground = new THREE.Mesh(groundGeometry, groundMaterial);
277     ground.rotation.x = Math.PI * - 0.5;
278     ground.name = 'Ground';
279     scene.add(ground);
280
281     var textureLoader = new THREE.TextureLoader();
282     textureLoader.load('../three/examples/textures/floors/FloorsCheckerboard_S_Diffuse.jpg',
283
284         map.wrapS = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
285         map.wrapT = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
286         map.anisotropy = 16;
287         map.repeat.set(4, 4);
288         groundMaterial.map = map;
289         groundMaterial.needsUpdate = true;
290
291     });
292 }
293
294
295
296
297

```

```

298
299 // -----
300 // gltf loader
301 //-----
302
303 function loadGLTFObject(path, x, y, z, name) {
304     var GLTFloader = new GLTFLoader();
305
306     //GLTFloader.load('models/duck.gltf', handle_load);
307     GLTFloader.load(path, handle_load);
308
309
310     //GLTF loader function
311     function handle_load(gltf) {
312         var objects = gltf.scene.children;
313         var theObject;
314         for (var i = 0; i < objects.length; i++) {
315             theObject = objects[i];
316             console.log(theObject);
317
318             //add object to scene
319             theObject.position.x = x;
320             theObject.position.y = y;
321             theObject.position.z = z;
322
323             theObject.name = name;
324
325             scene.add(theObject);
326             theObject.lookAt(user.position);
327
328
329
330
331
332             //push to array
333             allObjects.push(theObject);
334             console.log('added obj: ' + theObject.name + 'to array allObjects[]');
335             console.log('added obj: ' + theObject.name + ' to scene');
336             //writeStringToCanvas('added obj: ' + theObject.name + ' to scene');
337
338             selectedObj[0] = theObject;
339             setName(theObject.name, theObject);
340
341
342             var box = new THREE.BoxHelper(theObject, 0xffff00);
343             //scene.add( box );
344
345
346         }
347     }
348 }
349
350
351
352 //-----
353 // function to load Entity-Object
354 //-----
355 function insertEntity() {
356     loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Entity");
357 }

```

```

358
359 //-----
360 // function to load Relation-Object
361 //-----
362 function insertRelation() {
363     loadGLTFObject('models/relation.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Relation");
364 }
365
366 //-----
367 // function to load Attribute-Object
368 //-----
369 function insertAttribute() {
370     loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Attribute");
371 }
372
373
374 function deleteObject() {
375     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
376
377         //if line with this object exists, delete it
378         if (lines[i][1] == selectedObj[0] || lines[i][2] == selectedObj[0]) {
379             //delete line
380             try {
381                 scene.remove(lines[i][0]);
382                 lines[i].pop(2);
383                 lines[i].pop(1);
384                 lines[i].pop(0);
385                 lines[i] = undefined;
386
387
388             }
389             catch{ }
390         }
391     }
392
393     //delete object from allObjects list
394     for (var j = 0; j < allObjects.length; j++) {
395         if (allObjects[j] == selectedObj[0]) {
396             allObjects.splice(j, 1);
397             j = 100;
398         }
399     }
400
401     //remove object from scene
402     scene.remove(selectedObj[0]);
403     selectedObj = [];
404     console.log(allObjects);
405 }
406
407
408
409
410 //-----
411 // LOG section  ////////////////////////////////////////
412 //-----
413
414 //-----
415 // function to update the texture for the canvas
416 //-----
417 function updateTextureOfElement(object) {

```

```

418
419 textureLoader = new THREE.TextureLoader();
420 textureLoader.load(document.getElementById('myCanvas').toDataURL("image/png", 1.0), funct
421
422     map.wrapS = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
423     map.wrapT = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
424
425     object.material.map = map;
426     object.material.needsUpdate = true;
427 });
428 }
429
430
431 //-----
432 // writes a string to the log canvas
433 //-----
434 function writeStringToCanvas(stringToWrite) {
435
436     // function init
437     ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
438     canvasArray.push(stringToWrite);
439     ctx.fillStyle = "red"; // set stroke color to red
440     ctx.font = "70px Unknown Font, sans-serif"; //"12px Georgia";
441
442     if (canvas.getContext) {
443         var y = 100;
444
445         //clear canvas
446         ctx.clearRect(0, 0, canvas.width, canvas.height);
447
448         //draw all elements if array is < 10
449         if (canvasArray.length < 10) {
450             for (var i = 0; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
451                 //write to canvas
452                 ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
453                 y = y + 150;
454             }
455         }
456         //draw last 10 elements if array >= 10
457         else if (canvasArray.length >= 10) {
458             for (var i = canvasArray.length - 10; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
459                 //write to canvas
460                 ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
461                 y = y + 150;
462             }
463         }
464     }
465
466     //update texture of plane
467     //takes the weburl of the canvas
468     updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
469 }
470
471
472 //-----
473 // function to add a character at the same line
474 //adds the character in argument to the line in the log
475 //this function is called when you press a key on the keyboard
476 //-----
477 function writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(charToAdd) {

```

```

478
479 //function init
480 ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
481 ctx.fillStyle = "red"; // set stroke color to red
482 ctx.font = "70px Unknown Font, sans-serif"; //"12px Georgia";
483
484 //if there is already a character in the element
485 if (canvasArray[canvasArray.length] != undefined) {
486     var lastElement = canvasArray[canvasArray.length] + charToAdd;
487 }
488 //if no character in element
489 else {
490     var lastElement = charToAdd;
491 }
492
493 //pop last element in array and pushes the new element with added character
494 canvasArray.pop(canvasArray[canvasArray.length]);
495 canvasArray.push(lastElement);
496
497
498 if (canvas.getContext) {
499     var y = 100;
500
501     //clear canvas
502     ctx.clearRect(0, 0, canvas.width, canvas.height);
503
504     //draw last 10 elements if array is >= 10
505     if (canvasArray.length >= 10) {
506         for (var i = canvasArray.length - 10; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
507             //write to canvas
508             ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
509             y = y + 150;
510         }
511     }
512
513     //draw canvas if array <10
514     else if (canvasArray.length < 10) {
515         for (var i = 0; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
516             //write to canvas
517             ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
518             y = y + 150;
519         }
520     }
521
522 }
523
524
525 //update texture of plane -- takes the weburl of the canvas
526 updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
527
528 }
529
530 //end of log section -----
531
532
533
534
535
536 //-----
537 // function to output a sound to the speaker

```

```

538 //-----
539 function beep() {
540     var snd = new Audio("data:audio/wav;base64,//uQRAAAWMSLwUIYAAAsYkXgoQwAEaYlWfkWgAI0wWs/It
541     snd.play();
542 }
543
544
545
546
547
548
549 //-----
550 // text label  //////////////////////////////////////
551 //-----
552
553 //-----
554 //function to set the name of the selected object
555 //-----
556
557 function setName(name, object) {
558
559     updateTextInGroup(object, name);
560
561     //reset color before empty
562     //resetColorOfObjects();
563
564     //selectedObj = [];
565     render();
566
567
568 }
569
570
571 //-----
572 //function update Text in Group used in SetName
573 //-----
574
575 function updateTextInGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd) {
576
577     //remove old text if one is there
578     try {
579         console.log(selectedObj);
580         selectedObj.children.forEach(element => {
581             selectedObj.remove(element);
582             element.dispose();
583             console.log("disposed");
584         });
585     }
586     catch { console.log('not text to delet'); }
587
588     //add new text
589     console.log(selectedObj.geometry.boundingSphere.radius);
590     addTextToGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd, 0.5, 0.11);
591
592     // emty list
593     selectedObj = [];
594
595 }
596
597

```

```

598 //-----
599 //function addTextToGroup used in updateTextInGroup
600 //-----
601
602 //function to add a text to an object
603 // args: an object to get the position of the text, a string which represents the text, a for
604 function addTextToGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd, givenSize, givenHeight) {
605
606     //set new name
607     selectedObj.name = textToAdd;
608
609     var fontLoader = new THREE.FontLoader();
610
611     fontLoader.load('three/examples/fonts/helvetiker_regular.typeface.json', function (font)
612
613         //define geometry
614         var geometry = new THREE.TextBufferGeometry(textToAdd, {
615             font: font,
616             size: givenSize,
617             height: givenHeight,
618             curveSegments: 12,
619             bevelEnabled: false,
620
621         });
622
623         //rotate by 180 degree
624         //geometry.rotateY(3.14159);
625
626         var color = new THREE.Color('black');
627
628         //define material
629         var matLite = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({
630             color: color,
631             transparent: false,
632             opacity: 0.4,
633             side: THREE.DoubleSide
634         });
635
636
637         geometry.computeBoundingBox();
638         geometry.computeVertexNormals();
639
640         selectedObj.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
641         selectedObj.geometry.computeVertexNormals();
642
643         var centerOffset = 0.5 * (geometry.boundingBox.max.x - geometry.boundingBox.min.x);
644         var centerOffsetSelectedObj = 0.5 * (selectedObj.geometry.boundingBox.max.z - selecte
645         var centerOffsetSelectedObjY = 0.5 * (geometry.boundingBox.max.y - geometry.boundingF
646         // add text to object
647         var text = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, matLite);
648
649
650         //add text to parent object
651         selectedObj.add(text);
652         console.log('added text to selected obj: ' + selectedObj.uuid);
653
654         // set position of text
655         text.position.x = - centerOffset;
656         text.position.z = centerOffsetSelectedObj + 0.01;
657         text.position.y = - centerOffsetSelectedObjY

```

```

658
659
660     });
661
662     console.log('name of object \'' + selectedObj.name + '\'' set to ' + textToAdd);
663     writeStringToCanvas(('name of object \'' + selectedObj.name + '\'' set to ' + textToAdd));
664
665     //reset color before empty
666     resetColorOfObjects();
667 }
668
669
670
671
672 //-----
673 //function to reset color of selected object
674 //-----
675 function resetColorOfObjects() {
676
677     //for each element in array 'selectedObj' reset the color to default
678     for (var i = 0; i < allObjects.length; i++) {
679
680         try {
681             allObjects[i].material.color = StandardColor;
682         }
683         catch{ console.log('error on color reset on object ' + allObjects[i]) }
684         finally { }
685
686     }
687 }
688
689 //end of text label section -----
690
691
692
693 //-----
694 //controls for keyboard
695 //-----
696 var string = "";
697 var counterForNextObject = 0;
698
699 let keysPressed = {};
700
701 //delete keysPressed on keyup
702 document.addEventListener('keyup', (event) => {
703     delete keysPressed[event.key];
704 });
705
706 //print key to console
707 document.addEventListener("keydown", function (event) {
708
709     keysPressed[event.key] = true;
710
711     //if enter
712     if (event.keyCode == 13) {
713         setName(string, selectedObj[0]);
714         string = "";
715         writeStringToCanvas('pressed enter');
716     }
717

```

```

718
719 //if TAB + arrow: move object 1 in direction of arrow
720 //Tab + arrow up
721 else if (keysPressed['Tab'] && event.keyCode == 38) {
722     selectedObj[0].position.y = selectedObj[0].position.y + 1;
723 }
724
725 //Tab + arrow down
726 else if (keysPressed['Tab'] && event.keyCode == 40) {
727     selectedObj[0].position.y = selectedObj[0].position.y - 1;
728 }
729
730 //Tab + arrow left
731 else if (keysPressed['Tab'] && event.keyCode == 37) {
732     selectedObj[0].position.x = selectedObj[0].position.x - 1;
733 }
734
735 //Tab + arrow right
736 else if (keysPressed['Tab'] && event.keyCode == 39) {
737     selectedObj[0].position.x = selectedObj[0].position.x + 1;
738 }
739
740 //if only tab, do nothing
741 else if (keysPressed['Tab']){
742
743 }
744
745
746
747
748 //if down then connect two objects
749 else if (event.keyCode == 40) {
750     try {
751         if (selectedObj[0] != selectedObj[1]) {
752             connect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
753         }
754     }
755     catch{ }
756 }
757
758 //if up then disconnect two elements
759 else if (event.keyCode == 38) {
760     if (selectedObj[0] != selectedObj[1])
761         disconnect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
762 }
763
764 //if backspace
765 else if (event.keyCode == 8) {
766     string = string.slice(0, -1);
767     writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(string);
768 }
769
770
771 //if control, just change second element
772 else if (event.keyCode == 17) {
773     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
774     if (counterForNextObject < allObjectsLength - 1) {
775         counterForNextObject = counterForNextObject + 1;
776     }
777     else {

```

```

778         counterForNextObject = 0;
779     }
780
781
782     selectedObj[1] = allObjects[counterForNextObject];
783     resetColorOfObjects();
784
785     selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
786
787     try {
788         selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
789     }
790     catch{ }
791
792
793 }
794
795 //if key is arrow right, select next element (or only element)
796 else if (event.keyCode == 39) {
797     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
798
799     resetColorOfObjects();
800
801     try {
802         selectedObj.unshift(allObjects[selectedObj_number]);
803         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
804     } catch {
805         selectedObj[0] = allObjects[0];
806         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
807     }
808
809     try {
810         selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
811     }
812     catch{ }
813
814     if (selectedObj_number != allObjectsLength - 1) {
815         selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number + 1;
816     }
817     else {
818         selectedObj_number = 0;
819     }
820 }
821
822 //if arrow left, go to previous element
823 else if (event.keyCode == 37) {
824
825     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
826
827     try {
828         selectedObj[0].material.color = StandardColor;
829         selectedObj.shift();
830         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
831     }
832     catch {}
833
834
835     try {
836         selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
837     }

```

```

838         catch{ }
839
840         if (selectedObj_number != 0) {
841             selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number - 1;
842         }
843         else {
844             selectedObj_number = allObjectsLength - 1;
845         }
846     }
847
848     //if delete key
849     else if (event.keyCode == 46) {
850         printHelp();
851     }
852
853     //if esc pressed, change visibility of logplane
854     else if (event.keyCode == 27) {
855         if (log_plane.visible == true) {
856             log_plane.visible = false;
857         }
858         else {
859             log_plane.visible = true;
860         }
861     }
862
863     //if Shift do nothing
864     else if (event.keyCode == 16) {
865
866     }
867
868     //if Alt + 1: delete object
869     else if (keysPressed['Alt'] && event.key == '1') {
870         deleteObject();
871     }
872
873
874     //if Alt + 2: add entity
875     else if (keysPressed['Alt'] && event.key == '2') {
876         insertEntity();
877     }
878
879     //if Alt + 3: add attribute
880     else if (keysPressed['Alt'] && event.key == '3') {
881         insertAttribute();
882     }
883
884     //if Alt + 4: add relation
885     else if (keysPressed['Alt'] && event.key == '4') {
886         insertRelation();
887     }
888
889
890
891     //if only Alt, do nothing
892     else if (keysPressed['Alt']) {
893     }
894
895     //else add char to string and write to canvas
896     else {
897         string = string + event.key.toString();

```

```

898         writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(string);
899     }
900 }
901
902 //-----
903
904
905 //-----
906 //function to print help text to log
907 //-----
908 function printHelp() {
909     //show help notes
910
911     writeStringToCanvas('Press ESC to hide/show log -- Delete to show Help');
912     writeStringToCanvas('right/left arrow: iterate over elements');
913     writeStringToCanvas('ctrl: change only pink object');
914     writeStringToCanvas('set name: type text and press enter to set name of red object');
915     writeStringToCanvas('connect: press down-arrow to connect two elements');
916     writeStringToCanvas('disconnect: press up-arrow to disconnect two elements');
917     writeStringToCanvas('ALT + 1: delete selected object');
918     writeStringToCanvas('ALT + 2, 3, 4: insert entity / attribute / relation');
919     writeStringToCanvas('Tab + Arrows: move object');
920
921
922 }
923
924
925 //-----
926 //function to connect two objects with a line-----
927 //-----
928
929 //requires two objects as input
930 function connect(obj1, obj2) {
931     //create a blue LineBasicMaterial
932     material = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({ color: 0x0000ff });
933
934
935     points.push(obj1.position);
936     points.push(obj2.postion);
937
938     //define Geometry
939     geometry = new THREE.Geometry();
940     geometry.vertices.push(obj1.position, obj2.position);
941
942     //define Line
943     line = new THREE.Line(geometry, material);
944     scene.add(line);
945     lines.push([line, obj1, obj2]);
946     writeStringToCanvas('connected objects ' + obj1.name + ' and ' + obj2.name);
947
948 }
949
950 //-----
951 //function to disconnect two objects with a line-----
952 //-----
953 function disconnect(obj1, obj2) {
954
955
956     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
957

```

```

958         if ((lines[i][1] == obj1 && lines[i][2] == obj2) || (lines[i][2] == obj1 && lines[i][
959             //delete line
960             try {
961                 scene.remove(lines[i][0]);
962                 lines[i].pop(2);
963                 lines[i].pop(1);
964                 lines[i].pop(0);
965                 lines.splice(i, 1);
966
967                 writeStringToCanvas('disconnected objects ' + obj1.name + ' and ' + obj2.name
968                 break;
969             }
970             catch{ }
971         }
972     }
973 }
974
975 //this function updates all the lines in the global array "lines"
976 //the function removes the old line and adds a new line with the new position
977 //called in update function
978 function updateLines() {
979     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
980
981         //if a array entry is undefined, delete it
982         if (lines[i] == undefined) {
983             lines.splice(i, 1);
984             i = 0;
985             break;
986         }
987
988         //console.log(lines);
989         var line = lines[i][0];
990         var obj1 = lines[i][1];
991         var obj2 = lines[i][2];
992         //var vertices = [obj1.position, obj2.position];
993         //line.vertices = vertices;
994
995         scene.remove(line);
996
997         //define new material
998         material = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({ color: 0x0000ff });
999
1000
1001         //define Geometry
1002         geometry = new THREE.Geometry();
1003         geometry.vertices.push(obj1.position, obj2.position);
1004
1005         //define Line
1006         lines[i][0] = new THREE.Line(geometry, material);
1007         scene.add(lines[i][0]);
1008
1009     }
1010 }
1011
1012 //-----
1013 // definition of game logic////////////////////////////////////
1014 //-----
1015
1016 //run GameLoop (update, render, repeat) -----
1017 var GameLoop = function () {

```

```

1018         requestAnimationFrame(GameLoop);
1019
1020         update();
1021         render();
1022
1023     };
1024
1025
1026     //-----
1027     // UPDATE function
1028     //-----
1029     var update = function () {
1030
1031         //keypress just checked after every 200 ms
1032         if (performance.now() > clock && performance.now() > 2000) {
1033             clock = clock + 200;
1034
1035             allObjects.forEach(element => {
1036                 element.lookAt(user.position);
1037             });
1038         }
1039
1040         updateLines();
1041
1042     };
1043
1044
1045     //-----
1046     // ANIMATE function
1047     //-----
1048     function animate() {
1049         renderer.setAnimationLoop(render);
1050     }
1051
1052
1053     //-----
1054     // RENDER function
1055     //-----
1056     var render = function () {
1057         renderer.render(scene, camera);
1058     };
1059     //-----
1060
1061
1062     // call
1063     animate();
1064     GameLoop();
1065
1066
1067 </script>
1068
1069 <!--canvas for log to image function-->
1070 <canvas id="myCanvas" width="578" height="200"></canvas>
1071 <!--video object for keyboard stream-->
1072 <video id="video" width="1280" height="360" autoplay style="display:none"></video>
1073
1074
1075 </body>
1076
1077

```


B Code of Concept 2

```
1 <html>
2
3 <head>
4   <meta charset="utf-8">
5   <style>
6     body {
7       margin: 0;
8       overflow: hidden;
9     }
10
11     #container {}
12   </style>
13 </head>
14
15 <body>
16   <div id="container"></div>
17   <script src="three/build/three.js"></script>
18   <script src="../../js/leap-1.0.0.js"></script>
19   <script src="../../js/leap-plugins-0.1.12.js"></script>
20   <script src="../../js/leap-widgets-0.1.0.js"></script>
21   <script src="../../js/VRKeyboard.js"></script>
22   <script src="../../js/keyboard.js"></script>
23   <script src="../../js/stats.min.js"></script>
24
25
26
27
28
29
30   <script type="module">
31
32     import * as THREE from '../three/build/three.module.js';
33     import { VRButton } from '../three/examples/jsm/webxr/VRButton.js';
34     import { GLTFLoader } from '../three/examples/jsm/loaders/GLTFLoader.js';
35     import { OrbitControls } from '../three/examples/jsm/controls/OrbitControls.js';
36     import { SVGLoader } from '../three/examples/jsm/loaders/SVGLoader.js';
37     import { XRControllerModelFactory } from '../three/examples/jsm/webxr/XRControllerModelFactor
38
39     import "../js/annyang.min.js";
40
41     //-----
42     //Global Variables
43     //-----
44
45     var camera, scene, renderer;
46     var geometry, material, mesh;
47     var controls;
48     var stats;
49     var user;
50     var raycaster;
51     var mouse = { x: 0, y: 0 };
52     var last = Date.now();
53     var keys = [];
54     const keyboard3d = new THREE.Object3D();
55     var log_plane;
56     var push_plane;
57     var push_plane_on;
```

```

58     var push_plane_next;
59     var push_plane_prev;
60     var push_plane_up;
61     var push_plane_right;
62     var push_plane_left;
63     var push_plane_down;
64     var push_plane_second_obj;
65
66     var push_plane_connect ;
67     var push_plane_disconnect ;
68     var push_plane_addEntity ;
69     var push_plane_addRelation ;
70     var push_plane_addAttribute ;
71     var push_plane_delete;
72
73
74     var keyboard_visible = true;
75     var allObjects = [];
76     var selectedObj = [];
77     var selectedObj_number = 0;
78     var textureLoader;
79
80     var HighlightColor = new THREE.Color('red');
81     var StandardColor = new THREE.Color('white');
82     var SecondColor = new THREE.Color('darkorchid');
83
84     //this is the string for one line in the log
85     var string = "";
86
87     //variable for the performance.now() time
88     var clock = 0;
89
90
91     //init Canvas
92     //get information
93     var canvas;
94     canvas = document.getElementById('myCanvas');
95     canvas.width = 2048;//horizontal resolution (?) - increase for better looking text
96     canvas.height = 2048;//vertical resolution (?) - increase for better looking text
97     canvas.style.width = canvas.width;//actual width of canvas
98     canvas.style.height = canvas.height;//actual height of canvas
99     var ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
100
101     //array with all log elements to draw
102     var canvasArray = [];
103
104     //array to store the values to update lines
105     var lines = [];
106     var points = [];
107     var line;
108
109
110     //-----
111     //end of global variables
112     //-----
113
114
115     //-----
116     //functions for keyboard
117     //-----

```

```

118     const wireframeMaterial = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({
119         color: 0xffffff,
120         wireframe: true,
121         side: THREE.DoubleSide
122     });
123
124     const keyMaterial = new THREE.MeshPhongMaterial({
125         color: 0x333333,
126     });
127
128     const grey_material = new THREE.MeshPhongMaterial({
129         color: 0x999999,
130     });
131
132     const lineMaterial = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({
133         color: 0x9CCCF, // 0x0000ff,
134     });
135
136     function roundedRect(ctx, x, y, width, height, radius) {
137         ctx.moveTo(x, y + radius);
138         ctx.lineTo(x, y + height - radius);
139         ctx.quadraticCurveTo(x, y + height, x + radius, y + height);
140         ctx.lineTo(x + width - radius, y + height);
141         ctx.quadraticCurveTo(x + width, y + height, x + width, y + height - radius);
142         ctx.lineTo(x + width, y + radius);
143         ctx.quadraticCurveTo(x + width, y, x + width - radius, y);
144         ctx.lineTo(x + radius, y);
145         ctx.quadraticCurveTo(x, y, x, y + radius);
146     }
147
148     var maxWidth = 0, maxHeight = 0;
149     var opts = { amount: 2, bevelEnabled: true, bevelSegments: 2, steps: 2, bevelSize: 1, bevelTl
150
151     class Cache {
152         constructor() {
153             this.cache = {};
154         }
155
156         get(key) {
157             return this.cache[key];
158         }
159
160         set(key, item) {
161             this.cache[key] = item;
162         }
163
164         getOrMake(key, func) {
165             if (key in this.cache) {
166                 return this.get(key);
167             }
168
169             const item = func();
170             this.set(key, item);
171             return item;
172         }
173     }
174
175     var geometryCache = new Cache();
176
177     var info = () => console.log('info', '\n',

```

```

178         'geometries\t', renderer.info.memory.geometries, '\n',
179         'textures\t', renderer.info.memory.textures, '\n',
180         'vertices\t', renderer.info.render.vertices, '\n',
181         'calls\t', renderer.info.render.calls, '\n',
182         'faces\t', renderer.info.render.faces, '\n',
183         'points\t', renderer.info.render.points, '\n'
184     );
185
186     // create and cache ExtrudeGeometry;
187     function getExtrudeGeometry(w, h) {
188         const key = `e${w}.${h}`;
189
190         return geometryCache.getOrMake(key, () => {
191             const shape = new THREE.Shape();
192             roundedRect(shape, 0, 0, w, h, 7);
193             const geometry = new THREE.ExtrudeGeometry(shape, opts);
194             alignCenter(geometry);
195             return geometry;
196         });
197     }
198
199     function alignCenter(geometry) {
200         geometry.computeBoundingBox();
201         var max = geometry.boundingBox.max;
202         var m = (new THREE.Matrix4()).makeTranslation(-max.x / 2, -max.y / 2, -max.z / 2);
203         geometry.applyMatrix(m);
204     }
205
206     function getLineGeometry(w, h) {
207         const key = `l${w}.${h}`;
208
209         return geometryCache.getOrMake(key, () => {
210             const shape = new THREE.Shape();
211             roundedRect(shape, 0, 0, w, h, 7);
212             const geometry = new THREE.Geometry();
213             geometry.vertices = shape.getPoints().map(p => new THREE.Vector3(p.x, p.y, 0));
214             alignCenter(geometry);
215
216             return geometry;
217         });
218     }
219
220     function plane() {
221         return geometryCache.getOrMake('plane',
222             () => new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(14, 14, 1, 1)
223         );
224     }
225
226     // function getText(char) {
227     //     return geometryCache.getOrMake('text:' + char, () => makeText(char));
228     // }
229
230     function makeText(char) {
231         // 64 good quality, 16 minimal readable
232         // zoom in high quality 128, 256 (60fps), 512 (40fps), 1024 (20fps)
233         // 1024 texture - 16 * 16 = 256 of 64x64
234         // 128 * 64 = 8192
235         const canvasSize = 64;
236         const canvas = document.createElement('canvas');
237         const ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');

```

```

238     ctx.font = canvasSize / 4 * 3 + 'px helvetica'
239     const c = ctx.measureText(char);
240     const mul = (Math.ceil(c.width / canvasSize) | 0);
241     canvas.width = mul * canvasSize;
242     canvas.height = canvasSize;
243
244     ctx.font = canvasSize / 4 * 3 + 'px helvetica'
245     ctx.textAlign = 'center';
246     ctx.textBaseline = 'middle';
247     ctx.fillStyle = '#fff';
248     ctx.fillText(char, canvas.width / 2, canvas.height / 2);
249     // document.body.append(canvas); // debug
250
251     const texture = new THREE.Texture(canvas);
252     texture.flipY = false
253     texture.needsUpdate = true;
254
255     const letterShader = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({
256         color: 0xffffffff, // 0x60B8DB
257         // wireframe: true,
258         side: THREE.DoubleSide,
259         map: texture,
260         transparent: true
261     });
262
263     const letter = new THREE.Mesh(plane(), letterShader);
264     letter.scale.x = mul;
265
266     return letter;
267 }
268
269 function makeMacKeyboard() {
270     keyboard_keys.forEach(key => {
271         const { x, y, w, h, char } = key;
272
273         const geometry = getExtrudeGeometry(w, h);
274         var mesh = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, keyMaterial);
275         mesh.position.set(x + w / 2, y + h / 2, 0);
276
277
278         //do not write the character as name but the keycode
279
280         //mesh.name = key.char;
281         //mesh.geometry.name = key.char;
282         mesh.name = key.keycode;
283         mesh.geometry.name = key.keycode;
284
285         //Add the mesh to the keyboard and pushes the mesh to the key array
286         keyboard3d.add(mesh);
287         keys.push(mesh);
288
289         let txt = char.length > 2 ? char.toLowerCase() : key.char;
290         // if (char.length === 1 && !txt.match(/^[AZ]$/i)) {
291         //     console.log(char, key.shift, txt.match(/^[AZ]$/i));
292         //     txt = char + '\n' + key.shift;
293         // }
294         const letter = makeText(txt);
295         letter.position.z = -5.01;
296         mesh.add(letter);
297

```

```

298
299         maxWidth = Math.max(maxWidth, w + x);
300         maxHeight = Math.max(maxHeight, h + y);
301     });
302
303     var shape = new THREE.Shape();
304     var PADDING = 5;
305     roundedRect(shape, -PADDING, -PADDING, maxWidth + PADDING * 2, maxHeight + PADDING * 2, 7);
306     var geometry = new THREE.ExtrudeGeometry(shape, Object.assign({}, opts, { amount: 8 }));
307     var base = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, grey_material);
308     base.position.z = 4;
309
310     keyboard3d.add(base);
311 }
312
313 function makeLineKeyboard() {
314     keyboard_keys.forEach(key => {
315         const { x, y, w, h, char } = key;
316         const geometry = getLineGeometry(w, h);
317         const outline = new THREE.Line(geometry, lineMaterial);
318         outline.position.set(x + w / 2, y + h / 2, 0);
319
320         //added by fabian
321
322         outline.name = key.keycode;
323         outline.geometry.name = key.keycode;
324
325         keys.push(outline);
326
327         const letter = makeText(char);
328         outline.add(letter);
329
330         keyboard3d.add(outline);
331
332         maxWidth = Math.max(maxWidth, w + x);
333         maxHeight = Math.max(maxHeight, h + y);
334     });
335 }
336
337 //-----
338 //end of functions for keyboard
339 //-----
340
341
342
343
344
345
346 //-----
347 //draw keyboard.
348 //you can choose the design
349 //-----
350
351 makeMacKeyboard();
352 //makeLineKeyboard();
353
354 setTimeout(info, 500);
355
356 keyboard3d.position.x = -maxWidth / 2;
357 //keyboard3d.rotation.x = Math.PI / 2;

```

```

358
359 //disabled
360 //'use strict';
361
362
363 initStandardScene();
364 init();
365 animate();
366
367 setTimeout(function () { printHelp(); }, 3000);
368
369 function resize() {
370     window.addEventListener('resize', onWindowResize, false);
371
372     function onWindowResize() {
373
374         camera.aspect = window.innerWidth / window.innerHeight;
375         camera.updateProjectionMatrix();
376
377         renderer.setSize(window.innerWidth, window.innerHeight);
378     }
379 }
380
381
382 //initialize specific project
383 function init() {
384
385
386     //add plane for log
387     geometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(0.5, 0.5);
388     material = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ side: THREE.DoubleSide });
389     log_plane = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
390
391     updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
392     camera.add(log_plane);
393     log_plane.position.set(0, 0.05, -0.4);
394     log_plane.scale.set(0.5, 0.5, 0.5);
395     //log_plane.rotation.x += 0.2;
396     //-----
397
398     //scale and place keyboard
399     keyboard3d.scale.set(0.0007, 0.0007, 0.0007);
400     camera.add(keyboard3d);
401     keyboard3d.rotation.x = 2.96893;
402     keyboard3d.position.set(-0.2, -0.05125, -0.4);
403     //-----
404
405     //create button off
406     geometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(0.02, 0.02);
407     material = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ color: 'grey', side: THREE.DoubleSide });
408     push_plane = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
409     camera.add(push_plane);
410     push_plane.position.set(0.15, 0.07, -0.36);
411     push_plane.name = "button";
412     keys.push(push_plane);
413
414     //add label off for button
415     const letter_for_push_plane = makeText("off");
416     letter_for_push_plane.rotation.x = 3.14159;
417     letter_for_push_plane.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);

```

```

418     push_plane.add(letter_for_push_plane);
419
420
421     //-----
422
423     //create button on
424     push_plane_on = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
425     camera.add(push_plane_on);
426     push_plane_on.position.set(0.15, 0.04, -0.36);
427     push_plane_on.name = "button_on";
428     //do not push to keys, because default is off
429
430     //add label on for button
431     const letter_for_push_plane_on = makeText("on");
432     letter_for_push_plane_on.rotation.x = 3.14159;
433     letter_for_push_plane_on.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
434     push_plane_on.add(letter_for_push_plane_on);
435     //-----
436
437     //create button next
438     push_plane_next = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
439     camera.add(push_plane_next);
440     push_plane_next.scale.set(2, 1, 1);
441     push_plane_next.position.set(0.15, 0.01, -0.36);
442     push_plane_next.name = "next";
443     keys.push(push_plane_next);
444
445     //add label next for button
446     const letter_for_push_plane_next = makeText("next");
447     letter_for_push_plane_next.rotation.x = 3.14159;
448     letter_for_push_plane_next.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
449     push_plane_next.add(letter_for_push_plane_next);
450     //-----
451
452     //create button push_plane_prev
453     push_plane_prev = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
454     camera.add(push_plane_prev);
455     push_plane_prev.scale.set(2, 1, 1);
456     push_plane_prev.position.set(0.15, -0.02, -0.36);
457     push_plane_prev.name = "prev";
458     keys.push(push_plane_prev);
459
460     //add label prev for push_plane_prev
461     const letter_for_push_plane_prev = makeText("prev");
462     letter_for_push_plane_prev.rotation.x = 3.14159;
463     letter_for_push_plane_prev.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
464     push_plane_prev.add(letter_for_push_plane_prev);
465
466     //-----
467
468     //create button push_plane_second_obj
469     push_plane_second_obj = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
470     camera.add(push_plane_second_obj);
471     push_plane_second_obj.scale.set(2, 1, 1);
472     push_plane_second_obj.position.set(0.2, 0.01, -0.36);
473     push_plane_second_obj.name = "2. obj";
474     keys.push(push_plane_second_obj);
475
476     //add label prev for push_plane_second_obj
477     const letter_for_push_plane_second_obj = makeText("2. obj");

```

```

478     letter_for_push_plane_second_obj.rotation.x = 3.14159;
479     letter_for_push_plane_second_obj.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
480     push_plane_second_obj.add(letter_for_push_plane_second_obj);
481
482     //-----
483
484
485
486     //create button push_plane_up ;
487     push_plane_up = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
488     camera.add(push_plane_up);
489     push_plane_up.scale.set(2, 2, 2);
490     push_plane_up.position.set(0, -0.1, -0.46);
491     push_plane_up.name = "up";
492     keys.push(push_plane_up);
493
494     //add label up for push_plane_up
495     const letter_for_push_plane_up = makeText("up");
496     letter_for_push_plane_up.rotation.x = 3.14159;
497     letter_for_push_plane_up.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
498     push_plane_up.add(letter_for_push_plane_up);
499
500
501     //create button push_plane_right ;
502     push_plane_right = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
503     camera.add(push_plane_right);
504     push_plane_right.scale.set(2, 2, 2);
505     push_plane_right.position.set(0.05, -0.125, -0.46);
506     push_plane_right.name = "right";
507     keys.push(push_plane_right);
508
509     //add label up for push_plane_right
510     const letter_for_push_plane_right = makeText("right");
511     letter_for_push_plane_right.rotation.x = 3.14159;
512     letter_for_push_plane_right.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
513     push_plane_right.add(letter_for_push_plane_right);
514
515
516     //create button push_plane_down ;
517     push_plane_down = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
518     camera.add(push_plane_down);
519     push_plane_down.scale.set(2, 2, 2);
520     push_plane_down.position.set(0, -0.15, -0.46);
521     push_plane_down.name = "down";
522     keys.push(push_plane_down);
523
524     //add label down for push_plane_down
525     const letter_for_push_plane_down = makeText("down");
526     letter_for_push_plane_down.rotation.x = 3.14159;
527     letter_for_push_plane_down.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
528     push_plane_down.add(letter_for_push_plane_down);
529
530     //create button push_plane_left ;
531     push_plane_left = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
532     camera.add(push_plane_left);
533     push_plane_left.scale.set(2, 2, 2);
534     push_plane_left.position.set(-0.05, -0.125, -0.46);
535     push_plane_left.name = "left";
536     keys.push(push_plane_left);
537

```

```

538 //add label left for push_plane_left
539 const letter_for_push_plane_left = makeText("left");
540 letter_for_push_plane_left.rotation.x = 3.14159;
541 letter_for_push_plane_left.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
542 push_plane_left.add(letter_for_push_plane_left);
543 //-----
544
545
546 createButton(-0.2, -0.2, -0.46, 3.14159, 3.5, 2, 1, 'connect', push_plane_connect);
547 createButton(-0.1, -0.2, -0.46, 3.14159, 3.5, 2, 1, 'disconnect', push_plane_disconnect);
548 createButton(-0.0, -0.2, -0.46, 3.14159, 3.5, 2, 1, 'add entity', push_plane_addEntity);
549 createButton(0.1, -0.2, -0.46, 3.14159, 3.5, 2, 1, 'add attribute', push_plane_addAttribu);
550 createButton(0.2, -0.2, -0.46, 3.14159, 3.5, 2, 1, 'add relation', push_plane_addRelatior);
551 createButton(0.3, -0.2, -0.46, 3.14159, 3.5, 2, 1, 'delete', push_plane_delete);
552
553
554 //create arrow buttons-----
555
556
557
558 //add stats window to ckeck performance
559 var container = document.getElementById('container');
560 container.appendChild(renderer.domElement);
561 stats = new Stats();
562 stats.domElement.style.position = 'absolute';
563 stats.domElement.style.top = '0px';
564 document.body.appendChild(stats.domElement);
565
566 resize();
567 }
568
569 function createButton(posx, posy, posz, rotx, scalex, scaley, scalez, name, varToStore) {
570     geometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(0.02, 0.02);
571     material = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ color: 'grey', side: THREE.DoubleSide });
572     var tempVar = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
573     camera.add(tempVar);
574     tempVar.scale.set(scalex, scaley, scalez);
575     tempVar.position.set(posx, posy, posz);
576     tempVar.name = name;
577     keys.push(tempVar);
578
579     //add label off for button
580     const letter_for_plane = makeText(name);
581     letter_for_plane.rotation.x = rotx;
582     letter_for_plane.scale.set(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
583     tempVar.add(letter_for_plane);
584
585     varToStore = tempVar.clone();
586
587
588 }
589
590
591
592
593 //initialize the standard for all projects
594 function initStandardScene() {
595
596     scene = new THREE.Scene();
597

```

```

598 // add milkyWay
599 var background = new THREE.CubeTextureLoader()
600     .setPath('../three/examples/textures/cube/MilkyWay/')
601     .load(['dark-s_px.jpg', 'dark-s_nx.jpg', 'dark-s_py.jpg', 'dark-s_ny.jpg', 'dark-s_pz
602
603 scene.background = background;
604
605
606 //user needed for VR Camera
607 user = new THREE.Group();
608 user.position.set(0, 8, 30);
609 camera = new THREE.PerspectiveCamera(75, window.innerWidth / window.innerHeight, 0.1, 100
610 camera.position.set(0, 8, 30);
611 camera.lookAt(scene.position);
612
613 //add camera to user and user to scene
614 user.add(camera);
615 scene.add(user);
616
617 //define renderer
618 renderer = new THREE.WebGLRenderer();
619 renderer.setSize(window.innerWidth, window.innerHeight);
620
621 //add webxr support
622 document.body.appendChild(VRButton.createButton(renderer));
623 renderer.xr.enabled = true;
624
625 //add orbitControls
626 controls = new OrbitControls(camera, renderer.domElement);
627
628
629 //loads the floor
630 loadFloor();
631
632 //loads gltf objects
633 loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', 10, 5, 0, "Entity 1");
634 loadGLTFObject('models/relation.glb', 0, 5, 0, "Relation 1");
635 loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', -10, 5, 0, "Entity 2");
636 loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', -15, 5, 0, "Attribute 1");
637 loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', -10, 8, 0, "Attribute 2");
638
639
640
641
642
643
644 // -----
645 // lights
646 //-----
647 var light = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff);
648 light.position.set(0, 190, 80);
649 scene.add(light);
650
651 var light1 = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff, 2, 50);
652 light1.position.set(camera.position);
653 light1.position.z = light1.position.z + 3;
654 scene.add(light1);
655
656 var light2 = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff, 2, 50);
657 light2.position.x = 0;

```

```

658         light2.position.y = 0
659         light2.position.z = 16;
660         scene.add(light2);
661
662         var ambience = new THREE.AmbientLight(0x666666);
663         scene.add(ambience);
664
665
666     }
667     // end of init -----
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676     // -----
677     // floor loader
678     //-----
679
680     //function to initialize the floor
681     function loadFloor() {
682         var groundGeometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(40, 40, 10, 10);
683         var groundMaterial = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ color: 0xcccccc });
684         var ground = new THREE.Mesh(groundGeometry, groundMaterial);
685         ground.rotation.x = Math.PI * - 0.5;
686         ground.name = 'Ground';
687         scene.add(ground);
688
689         //push to array
690         allObjects.push(ground);
691
692         var textureLoader = new THREE.TextureLoader();
693         textureLoader.load('../three/examples/textures/floors/FloorsCheckerboard_S_Diffuse.jpg',
694
695             map.wrapS = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
696             map.wrapT = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
697             map.anisotropy = 16;
698             map.repeat.set(4, 4);
699             groundMaterial.map = map;
700             groundMaterial.needsUpdate = true;
701
702
703         });
704     }
705
706     // -----
707     // gltf loader
708     //-----
709
710     function loadGLTFObject(path, x, y, z, name) {
711         var GLTFloader = new GLTFLoader();
712
713         //GLTFloader.load('models/duck.gltf', handle_load);
714         GLTFloader.load(path, handle_load);
715
716
717         //GLTF loader function

```

```

718     function handle_load(gltf) {
719         var objects = gltf.scene.children;
720         var theObject;
721         for (var i = 0; i < objects.length; i++) {
722             theObject = objects[i];
723             console.log(theObject);
724
725             //add object to scene
726             theObject.position.x = x;
727             theObject.position.y = y;
728             theObject.position.z = z;
729
730             theObject.name = name;
731
732             scene.add(theObject);
733
734
735
736
737
738             //push to array
739             allObjects.push(theObject);
740             console.log('added obj: ' + theObject.name + 'to array allObjects[]');
741             console.log('added obj: ' + theObject.name + ' to scene');
742             //writeStringToCanvas('added obj: ' + theObject.name + ' to scene');
743
744             selectedObj[0] = theObject;
745             setName(theObject.name, theObject);
746
747
748             var box = new THREE.BoxHelper(theObject, 0xffff00);
749             //scene.add( box );
750
751
752
753         }
754     }
755 }
756
757 //-----
758 // function to load Entity-Object
759 //-----
760 function insertEntity() {
761     loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Entity");
762 }
763
764 //-----
765 // function to load Relation-Object
766 //-----
767 function insertRelation() {
768     loadGLTFObject('models/relation.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Relation");
769 }
770
771 //-----
772 // function to load Attribute-Object
773 //-----
774 function insertAttribute() {
775     loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Attribute");
776 }
777

```

```

778 //-----
779 // function to delete object
780 //-----
781 function deleteObject() {
782     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
783
784         //if line with this object exists, delete it
785         if (lines[i][1] == selectedObj[0] || lines[i][2] == selectedObj[0]) {
786             //delete line
787             try {
788                 scene.remove(lines[i][0]);
789                 lines[i].pop(2);
790                 lines[i].pop(1);
791                 lines[i].pop(0);
792                 lines[i] = undefined;
793
794
795             }
796             catch{ }
797         }
798     }
799
800     //delete object from allObjects list
801     for (var j = 0; j < allObjects.length; j++) {
802         if (allObjects[j] == selectedObj[0]) {
803             allObjects.splice(j, 1);
804             j = 100;
805         }
806     }
807
808     //remove object from scene
809     scene.remove(selectedObj[0]);
810     selectedObj = [];
811     console.log(allObjects);
812 }
813
814
815 //-----
816 // mouse event
817 //-----
818
819
820 raycaster = new THREE.Raycaster();
821 renderer.domElement.addEventListener('click', raycast, false);
822
823 //-----
824 // raycast function to interact with the keyboard with mouse
825 //-----
826 function raycast(e) {
827
828
829     // Step 2: Detect normal objects
830     //1. sets the mouse position with a coordinate system where the center
831     //   of the screen is the origin
832
833     //console.log("Click");
834
835     mouse.x = (e.clientX / window.innerWidth) * 2 - 1;
836     mouse.y = - (e.clientY / window.innerHeight) * 2 + 1;
837

```

```

838 //2. set the picking ray from the camera position and mouse coordinates
839 raycaster.setFromCamera(mouse, camera);
840
841 //3. compute intersections (no 2nd parameter true anymore)
842 var intersects = raycaster.intersectObjects(keys, true);
843
844
845 //for ( var i = 0; i < intersects.length; i++ ) {
846 for (var i = 0; i < 1; i++) {
847     console.log(intersects[i].object.name);
848 }
849
850 }
851
852
853 //-----
854 // LOG section  //////////////////////////////////////
855 //-----
856
857 //-----
858 // function to update the texture for the canvas
859 //-----
860 function updateTextureOfElement(object) {
861
862     textureLoader = new THREE.TextureLoader();
863     textureLoader.load(document.getElementById('myCanvas').toDataURL("image/png", 1.0), funct
864
865     map.wrapS = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
866     map.wrapT = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
867
868     object.material.map = map;
869     object.material.needsUpdate = true;
870 });
871 }
872
873
874 //-----
875 // writes a string to the log canvas
876 //-----
877 function writeStringToCanvas(stringToWrite) {
878
879     // function init
880     ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
881     canvasArray.push(stringToWrite);
882     ctx.fillStyle = "red"; // set stroke color to red
883     ctx.font = "70px Unknown Font, sans-serif"; //"12px Georgia";
884
885     if (canvas.getContext) {
886         var y = 100;
887
888         //clear canvas
889         ctx.clearRect(0, 0, canvas.width, canvas.height);
890
891         //draw all elements if array is < 10
892         if (canvasArray.length < 10) {
893             for (var i = 0; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
894                 //write to canvas
895                 ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
896                 y = y + 150;
897             }

```

```

898     }
899     //draw last 10 elements if array >= 10
900     else if (canvasArray.length >= 10) {
901         for (var i = canvasArray.length - 10; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
902             //write to canvas
903             ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
904             y = y + 150;
905         }
906     }
907 }
908
909 //update texture of plane
910 //takes the webur1 of the canvas
911 updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
912 }
913
914
915 //-----
916 // function to add a character at the same line
917 //adds the character in argument to the line in the log
918 //this function is called when you press a key on the keyboard
919 //-----
920 function writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(charToAdd) {
921
922     //function init
923     ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
924     ctx.fillStyle = "red"; // set stroke color to red
925     ctx.font = "70px Unknown Font, sans-serif"; //"12px Georgia";
926
927     //if there is already a character in the element
928     if (canvasArray[canvasArray.length] != undefined) {
929         var lastElement = canvasArray[canvasArray.length] + charToAdd;
930     }
931     //if no character in element
932     else {
933         var lastElement = charToAdd;
934     }
935
936     //pop last element in array and pushes the new element with added character
937     canvasArray.pop(canvasArray[canvasArray.length]);
938     canvasArray.push(lastElement);
939
940
941     if (canvas.getContext) {
942         var y = 100;
943
944         //clear canvas
945         ctx.clearRect(0, 0, canvas.width, canvas.height);
946
947         //draw last 10 elements if array is >= 10
948         if (canvasArray.length >= 10) {
949             for (var i = canvasArray.length - 10; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
950                 //write to canvas
951                 ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
952                 y = y + 150;
953             }
954         }
955
956         //draw canvas if array <10
957         else if (canvasArray.length < 10) {

```

```

958         for (var i = 0; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
959             //write to canvas
960             ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
961             y = y + 150;
962         }
963     }
964
965
966 }
967
968 //update texture of plane -- takes the weburl of the canvas
969 updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
970
971 }
972
973 //end of log section -----
974
975
976
977
978 //-----
979 // LEAP MOTION section //////////////////////////////////////
980 //-----
981
982 //variables for positions of fingers
983 var leftTip;
984 var leftDistal;
985 var rightTip;
986 var rightDistal;
987
988
989 //create Group for Hand
990 var GroupForHand = new THREE.Group();
991
992 //add ad first element of scene
993 scene.children.unshift(GroupForHand);
994
995 // Connect to localhost and start getting frames
996 Leap.loop(
997     {
998         hand: function (hand) {
999
1000             //here we set the position of the tips of the index fingers
1001
1002             //updates the information of the left hand
1003             if (hand.type == "left") {
1004                 //console.log("left " + hand.indexFinger.tipPosition);
1005                 leftTip = hand.indexFinger.tipPosition;
1006                 leftDistal = hand.indexFinger.distal;
1007             }
1008
1009             //updates the information of the right hand
1010             if (hand.type == "right") {
1011                 //console.log("right " + hand.indexFinger.tipPosition);
1012                 rightTip = hand.indexFinger.tipPosition;
1013                 rightDistal = hand.indexFinger.distal;
1014             }
1015         }
1016     }
1017 );

```

```

1018
1019 // Docs: http://leapmotion.github.io/leapjs-plugins/main/transform/
1020 Leap.loopController.use('transform', {
1021
1022     // This matrix flips the x, y, and z axis, scales to meters, and offsets the hands by -8c
1023     vr: true,
1024
1025     // This causes the camera's matrix transforms (position, rotation, scale) to be applied t
1026     // The parent of the bones remain the scene, allowing the data to remain in easy-to-work-
1027     // (As the hands will usually interact with multiple objects in the scene.)
1028     effectiveParent: camera
1029
1030 });
1031 // Docs: http://leapmotion.github.io/leapjs-plugins/main/bone-hand/
1032 Leap.loopController.use('boneHand', {
1033
1034     // If you already have a scene or want to create it yourself, you can pass it in here
1035     // Alternatively, you can pass it in whenever you want by doing
1036     // Leap.loopController.plugins.boneHand.scene = myScene.
1037
1038     //takes the group (GroupForHand)
1039     scene: GroupForHand,
1040
1041     // Display the arm
1042     arm: true
1043
1044 });
1045
1046 //end of leap section-----
1047
1048
1049
1050
1051
1052 //-----
1053 // function to output a sound to the speaker
1054 //-----
1055 function beep() {
1056     var snd = new Audio("data:audio/wav;base64,//uQRAAAWMSLwUIYAA5YkXgoQwAEaYlWfkWgAI0wWs/It
1057     snd.play();
1058 }
1059
1060
1061
1062 //defines two boxes which are always at the tip of the index fingers
1063 var cubeGeometry = new THREE.BoxBufferGeometry(0.001, 0.001, 0.001);
1064 var cubeMaterial = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ color: 'red' });
1065 var cubeLeft = new THREE.Mesh(cubeGeometry, cubeMaterial);
1066 var cubeRight = new THREE.Mesh(cubeGeometry, cubeMaterial);
1067 var pressedKey;
1068 scene.add(cubeLeft);
1069 scene.add(cubeRight);
1070 cubeRight.visible = false;
1071 cubeLeft.visible = false;
1072
1073 //copy of the keys array
1074 var keysCopy = keys.slice();
1075
1076 var counterForNextObject = 0;
1077

```

```

1078
1079 //-----
1080 // function to check for intersection with keyboard
1081 //-----
1082
1083 //takes an object to check for an intersection with one of the fingertips of the leapMotion h
1084 //creates for each fingertip a THREE.BoxBufferGeometry(0.001, 0.001, 0.001); to check for int
1085 //the postion of the box is set from the postion of the fingertip which is updated in the Le
1086 function detectCollisionCubes(object1) {
1087
1088
1089     //add stuff for fingers
1090     cubeLeft.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
1091     cubeLeft.updateMatrixWorld();
1092
1093
1094     //add left finger tip
1095     try {
1096         cubeLeft.position.x = leftTip[0];
1097         cubeLeft.position.y = leftTip[1];
1098         cubeLeft.position.z = leftTip[2];
1099     } catch { }
1100
1101     var box2 = cubeLeft.geometry.boundingBox.clone();
1102     box2.applyMatrix4(cubeLeft.matrixWorld);
1103
1104     cubeRight.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
1105     cubeRight.updateMatrixWorld();
1106
1107
1108     //add right finger tip
1109     try {
1110         cubeRight.position.x = rightTip[0];
1111         cubeRight.position.y = rightTip[1];
1112         cubeRight.position.z = rightTip[2];
1113     } catch { }
1114
1115
1116
1117     var box3 = cubeRight.geometry.boundingBox.clone();
1118     box3.applyMatrix4(cubeRight.matrixWorld);
1119
1120
1121     //shows bounding boxes
1122     /*
1123         var helper1 = new THREE.Box3Helper( box1, 0xffff00 );
1124         scene.add( helper1 );
1125
1126         var helper2 = new THREE.Box3Helper( box2, 0xffff00 );
1127         scene.add( helper2 );
1128
1129         var helper3 = new THREE.Box3Helper( box3, 0xffff00 );
1130         scene.add( helper3 );
1131
1132     */
1133
1134
1135
1136
1137     if (keyboard3d.visible == true) {

```

```

1138
1139
1140 //add box for object one
1141 object1.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
1142 object1.updateMatrixWorld();
1143 var box1 = object1.geometry.boundingBox.clone();
1144 box1.applyMatrix4(object1.matrixWorld);
1145
1146 //if one hand intersects
1147 if (box1.intersectsBox(box2)) {
1148     console.log("touched " + object1.name + " box2");
1149     beep();
1150
1151     //set variable to name
1152     pressedKey = object1.name;
1153
1154     //color the pressed button
1155     keys.forEach(key => key.children[0].material.color = StandardColor);
1156     object1.children[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1157
1158     //if enter pushed
1159     if (pressedKey == 13) {
1160         writeStringToCanvas(string);
1161         if (selectedObj[0] != undefined) {
1162             setName(string, selectedObj[0]);
1163             string = "";
1164             selectedObj = [];
1165         }
1166     }
1167
1168     //if button 'off' pushed
1169     else if (pressedKey == "button") {
1170         keyboard3d.visible = false;
1171         log_plane.visible = false;
1172         keys = [];
1173         keys.push(push_plane_on);
1174         keys.push(push_plane_next);
1175         keys.push(push_plane_prev);
1176         keys.push(push_plane_up);
1177         keys.push(push_plane_down);
1178         keys.push(push_plane_right);
1179         keys.push(push_plane_left);
1180         keys.push(push_plane_second_obj);
1181
1182         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('connect'));
1183         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('disconnect'));
1184         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('add entity'));
1185         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('add attribute'));
1186         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('add relation'));
1187         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('delete'));
1188
1189
1190         pressedKey = "button_on";
1191     }
1192
1193     //if delete char
1194     else if (pressedKey == 8) {
1195         string = string.slice(0, -1);
1196         writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(string);
1197     }

```

```

1198
1199 //if key next
1200 else if (pressedKey == "next") {
1201     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1202
1203     selectedObj.unshift(allObjects[selectedObj_number]);
1204     selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1205
1206     try {
1207         selectedObj[1].material.color = StandardColor;
1208     }
1209     catch{ }
1210
1211
1212
1213
1214     console.log("selectedobjnr = " + selectedObj_number);
1215     console.log("allobjlength = " + allObjectsLength);
1216     console.log(allObjects);
1217     console.log(selectedObj);
1218
1219     if (selectedObj_number != allObjectsLength - 1) {
1220         selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number + 1;
1221     }
1222     else {
1223         selectedObj_number = 0;
1224     }
1225 }
1226
1227 //if key prev
1228 else if (pressedKey == "prev") {
1229
1230     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1231
1232     selectedObj[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1233     selectedObj.shift();
1234     selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1235
1236
1237     if (selectedObj_number != 0) {
1238         selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number - 1;
1239     }
1240     else {
1241         selectedObj_number = allObjectsLength - 1;
1242     }
1243 }
1244
1245 //if 2. obj button
1246 else if (pressedKey == "2. obj") {
1247     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1248     if (counterForNextObject < allObjectsLength - 1) {
1249         counterForNextObject = counterForNextObject + 1;
1250     }
1251     else {
1252         counterForNextObject = 0;
1253     }
1254
1255
1256     selectedObj[1] = allObjects[counterForNextObject];
1257     resetColorOfObjects();

```

```

1258
1259         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1260
1261         try {
1262             selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
1263         }
1264         catch{ }
1265
1266     }
1267
1268     //if F12 (123) show help
1269     else if (pressedKey == 123) {
1270         printHelp();
1271     }
1272
1273     //add char to line
1274     else {
1275
1276         //takes the charcode and adds the according char to the string an writes it t
1277         string = string + String.fromCharCode(object1.name);
1278         writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(string);
1279     }
1280 }
1281
1282
1283 //if other hand intersects
1284 if (box1.intersectsBox(box3)) {
1285     console.log("touched " + object1.name + " box3");
1286     beep();
1287
1288     //set variable to name
1289     pressedKey = object1.name;
1290
1291     //color the pressed button
1292     keys.forEach(key => key.children[0].material.color = StandardColor);
1293     object1.children[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1294
1295     //if enter pushed
1296     if (pressedKey == 13) {
1297         writeStringToCanvas(string);
1298         if (selectedObj[0] != undefined) {
1299             setName(string, selectedObj[0]);
1300             string = "";
1301             selectedObj = [];
1302         }
1303     }
1304
1305     //if button 'off' pushed
1306     else if (pressedKey == "button") {
1307         keyboard3d.visible = false;
1308         log_plane.visible = false;
1309         keys = [];
1310         keys.push(push_plane_on);
1311         keys.push(push_plane_next);
1312         keys.push(push_plane_prev);
1313         keys.push(push_plane_up);
1314         keys.push(push_plane_down);
1315         keys.push(push_plane_right);
1316         keys.push(push_plane_left);
1317         keys.push(push_plane_second_obj);

```

```

1318
1319         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('connect'));
1320         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('disconnect'));
1321         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('add entity'));
1322         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('add attribute'));
1323         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('add relation'));
1324         keys.push(scene.getObjectByName('delete'));
1325
1326
1327
1328         pressedKey = "button_on";
1329     }
1330
1331     //delete char
1332     else if (pressedKey == 8) {
1333         string = string.slice(0, -1);
1334         writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(string);
1335     }
1336
1337     //if key next
1338     else if (pressedKey == "next") {
1339         var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1340
1341         selectedObj.unshift(allObjects[selectedObj_number]);
1342         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1343
1344         try {
1345             selectedObj[1].material.color = StandardColor;
1346         }
1347         catch{ }
1348
1349
1350
1351         console.log("selectedobjnr = " + selectedObj_number);
1352         console.log("allobjlength = " + allObjectsLength);
1353         console.log(allObjects);
1354         console.log(selectedObj);
1355
1356         if (selectedObj_number != allObjectsLength - 1) {
1357             selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number + 1;
1358         }
1359         else {
1360             selectedObj_number = 0;
1361         }
1362     }
1363
1364     //if key prev
1365     else if (pressedKey == "prev") {
1366
1367         var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1368
1369         selectedObj[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1370         selectedObj.shift();
1371         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1372
1373
1374         if (selectedObj_number != 0) {
1375             selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number - 1;
1376         }
1377         else {

```

```

1378         selectedObj_number = allObjectsLength - 1;
1379     }
1380 }
1381
1382 //if 2. obj button
1383 else if (pressedKey == "2. obj") {
1384     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1385     if (counterForNextObject < allObjectsLength - 1) {
1386         counterForNextObject = counterForNextObject + 1;
1387     }
1388     else {
1389         counterForNextObject = 0;
1390     }
1391
1392
1393     selectedObj[1] = allObjects[counterForNextObject];
1394     resetColorOfObjects();
1395
1396     selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1397
1398     try {
1399         selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
1400     }
1401     catch{ }
1402
1403 }
1404
1405 //if F12 (123) show help
1406 else if (pressedKey == 123) {
1407     printHelp();
1408 }
1409
1410 //add char to line
1411 else {
1412     //takes the charcode and adds the according char to the string an writes it t
1413     string = string + String.fromCharCode(object1.name);
1414     writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(string);
1415 }
1416 }
1417
1418 //color the pressed button
1419 push_plane.children[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1420 push_plane_on.children[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1421
1422 }
1423
1424 // if keyboard is not visible
1425 else if (keyboard3d.visible == false) {
1426
1427     //add box for object one
1428     object1.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
1429     object1.updateMatrixWorld();
1430     var box1 = object1.geometry.boundingBox.clone();
1431     box1.applyMatrix4(object1.matrixWorld);
1432
1433     //if one hand intersects
1434     if (box1.intersectsBox(box2)) {
1435
1436         //set variable to name
1437         pressedKey = object1.name;

```

```

1438
1439 //if key next
1440 if (pressedKey == "next") {
1441     beep();
1442     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1443
1444     selectedObj.unshift(allObjects[selectedObj_number]);
1445     selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1446
1447     try {
1448         selectedObj[1].material.color = StandardColor;
1449     }
1450     catch{ }
1451
1452
1453
1454
1455     console.log("selectedobjnr = " + selectedObj_number);
1456     console.log("allobjlength = " + allObjectsLength);
1457     console.log(allObjects);
1458     console.log(selectedObj);
1459
1460     if (selectedObj_number != allObjectsLength - 1) {
1461         selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number + 1;
1462     }
1463     else {
1464         selectedObj_number = 0;
1465     }
1466 }
1467
1468 //if key prev
1469 else if (pressedKey == "prev") {
1470     beep();
1471     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1472
1473     selectedObj[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1474     selectedObj.shift();
1475     selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1476
1477
1478     if (selectedObj_number != 0) {
1479         selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number - 1;
1480     }
1481     else {
1482         selectedObj_number = allObjectsLength - 1;
1483     }
1484 }
1485
1486 //if 2. obj button
1487 else if (pressedKey == "2. obj") {
1488     var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1489     if (counterForNextObject < allObjectsLength - 1) {
1490         counterForNextObject = counterForNextObject + 1;
1491     }
1492     else {
1493         counterForNextObject = 0;
1494     }
1495
1496
1497     selectedObj[1] = allObjects[counterForNextObject];

```

```

1498         resetColorOfObjects();
1499
1500         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1501
1502         try {
1503             selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
1504         }
1505         catch{ }
1506
1507     }
1508
1509     //-----
1510     //if arrow: move object 1 in direction of arrow
1511     //-----
1512
1513     //arrow up
1514     else if (pressedKey == "up") {
1515         beep();
1516         selectedObj[0].position.y = selectedObj[0].position.y + 1;
1517     }
1518
1519     //arrow down
1520     else if (pressedKey == "down") {
1521         beep();
1522         selectedObj[0].position.y = selectedObj[0].position.y - 1;
1523     }
1524
1525     //arrow left
1526     else if (pressedKey == "left") {
1527         beep();
1528         selectedObj[0].position.x = selectedObj[0].position.x - 1;
1529     }
1530
1531     //arrow right
1532     else if (pressedKey == "right") {
1533         beep();
1534         selectedObj[0].position.x = selectedObj[0].position.x + 1;
1535     }
1536
1537     //-----
1538     //to add elements and connect/disconnect
1539     //-----
1540
1541     else if (pressedKey == "connect") {
1542         beep();
1543         connect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
1544     }
1545
1546     else if (pressedKey == "disconnect") {
1547         beep();
1548         disconnect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
1549     }
1550
1551     else if (pressedKey == "add entity") {
1552         beep();
1553         insertEntity();
1554     }
1555
1556     else if (pressedKey == "add attribute") {
1557         beep();

```

```

1558         insertAttribute();
1559     }
1560
1561     else if (pressedKey == "add relation") {
1562         beep();
1563         insertRelation();
1564     }
1565
1566     else if (pressedKey == "delete") {
1567         beep();
1568         deleteObject();
1569     }
1570
1571
1572     else {
1573
1574         keyboard3d.visible = true;
1575         log_plane.visible = true;
1576         beep();
1577         keyboard_visible = true;
1578
1579         //reset keys array to original
1580         keys = keysCopy.slice();
1581
1582         //color the pressed button
1583         push_plane.children[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1584         push_plane_on.children[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1585     }
1586 }
1587
1588 //if one hand intersects
1589 if (box1.intersectsBox(box3)) {
1590
1591     //set variable to name
1592     pressedKey = object1.name;
1593
1594     //if key next
1595     if (pressedKey == "next") {
1596         beep();
1597         var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1598
1599         selectedObj.unshift(allObjects[selectedObj_number]);
1600         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1601
1602         try {
1603             selectedObj[1].material.color = StandardColor;
1604         }
1605         catch{ }
1606
1607
1608
1609
1610         console.log("selectedobjnr = " + selectedObj_number);
1611         console.log("allobjlength = " + allObjectsLength);
1612         console.log(allObjects);
1613         console.log(selectedObj);
1614
1615         if (selectedObj_number != allObjectsLength - 1) {
1616             selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number + 1;
1617         }

```

```

1618         else {
1619             selectedObj_number = 0;
1620         }
1621     }
1622
1623     //if key prev
1624     else if (pressedKey == "prev") {
1625         beep();
1626         var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1627
1628         selectedObj[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1629         selectedObj.shift();
1630         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1631
1632
1633         if (selectedObj_number != 0) {
1634             selectedObj_number = selectedObj_number - 1;
1635         }
1636         else {
1637             selectedObj_number = allObjectsLength - 1;
1638         }
1639     }
1640
1641     //if 2. obj button
1642     else if (pressedKey == "2. obj") {
1643         var allObjectsLength = allObjects.length;
1644         if (counterForNextObject < allObjectsLength - 1) {
1645             counterForNextObject = counterForNextObject + 1;
1646         }
1647         else {
1648             counterForNextObject = 0;
1649         }
1650
1651
1652         selectedObj[1] = allObjects[counterForNextObject];
1653         resetColorOfObjects();
1654
1655         selectedObj[0].material.color = HighlightColor;
1656
1657         try {
1658             selectedObj[1].material.color = SecondColor;
1659         }
1660         catch{ }
1661
1662     }
1663
1664     //-----
1665     //if arrow: move object 1 in direction of arrow
1666     //-----
1667
1668     //arrow up
1669     else if (pressedKey == "up") {
1670         beep();
1671         selectedObj[0].position.y = selectedObj[0].position.y + 1;
1672     }
1673
1674     //arrow down
1675     else if (pressedKey == "down") {
1676         beep();
1677         selectedObj[0].position.y = selectedObj[0].position.y - 1;

```

```

1678     }
1679
1680     //arrow left
1681     else if (pressedKey == "left") {
1682         beep();
1683         selectedObj[0].position.x = selectedObj[0].position.x - 1;
1684     }
1685
1686     //arrow right
1687     else if (pressedKey == "right") {
1688         beep();
1689         selectedObj[0].position.x = selectedObj[0].position.x + 1;
1690     }
1691
1692     //-----
1693     //to add elements and connect/disconnect
1694     //-----
1695
1696     else if (pressedKey == "connect") {
1697         beep();
1698         connect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
1699     }
1700
1701     else if (pressedKey == "disconnect") {
1702         beep();
1703         disconnect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
1704     }
1705
1706     else if (pressedKey == "add entity") {
1707         beep();
1708         insertEntity();
1709     }
1710
1711     else if (pressedKey == "add attribute") {
1712         beep();
1713         insertAttribute();
1714     }
1715
1716     else if (pressedKey == "add relation") {
1717         beep();
1718         insertRelation();
1719     }
1720
1721     else if (pressedKey == "delete") {
1722         beep();
1723         deleteObject();
1724     }
1725
1726     else {
1727
1728         keyboard3d.visible = true;
1729         log_plane.visible = true;
1730         beep();
1731         keyboard_visible = true;
1732
1733         //reset keys array to original
1734         keys = keysCopy.slice();
1735
1736         //color the pressed button
1737         push_plane.children[0].material.color = HighlightColor;

```

```

1738         push_plane_on.children[0].material.color = StandardColor;
1739     }
1740 }
1741 }
1742 }
1743
1744
1745 //-----
1746 // text label  //////////////////////////////////////
1747 //-----
1748
1749 //-----
1750 //function to set the name of the selected object
1751 //-----
1752
1753 function setName(name, object) {
1754
1755     updateTextInGroup(object, name);
1756
1757     //reset color before empty
1758     resetColorOfObjects();
1759
1760     //selectedObj = [];
1761     render();
1762
1763 }
1764
1765
1766
1767 //-----
1768 //function update Text in Group used in SetName
1769 //-----
1770
1771 function updateTextInGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd) {
1772
1773     //remove old text if one is there
1774     try {
1775         console.log(selectedObj);
1776         selectedObj.children.forEach(element => {
1777             selectedObj.remove(element);
1778             element.dispose();
1779             console.log("disposed");
1780         });
1781     }
1782     catch { console.log('not text to delet'); }
1783
1784     //add new text
1785     console.log(selectedObj.geometry.boundingSphere.radius);
1786     addTextToGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd, 0.5, 0.11);
1787
1788     // emty list
1789     selectedObj = [];
1790
1791 }
1792
1793
1794 //-----
1795 //function addTextToGroup used in updateTextInGroup
1796 //-----
1797

```

```

1798 //function to add a text to an object
1799 // args: an object to get the position of the text, a string which represents the text, a for
1800 function addTextToGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd, givenSize, givenHeight) {
1801
1802     //set new name
1803     selectedObj.name = textToAdd;
1804
1805     var fontLoader = new THREE.FontLoader();
1806
1807     fontLoader.load('three/examples/fonts/helvetiker_regular.typeface.json', function (font)
1808
1809         //define geometry
1810         var geometry = new THREE.TextBufferGeometry(textToAdd, {
1811             font: font,
1812             size: givenSize,
1813             height: givenHeight,
1814             curveSegments: 12,
1815             bevelEnabled: false,
1816
1817         });
1818
1819         //rotate by 180 degree
1820         //geometry.rotateY(3.14159);
1821
1822         var color = new THREE.Color('black');
1823
1824         //define material
1825         var matLite = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({
1826             color: color,
1827             transparent: false,
1828             opacity: 0.4,
1829             side: THREE.DoubleSide
1830         });
1831
1832
1833         geometry.computeBoundingBox();
1834         geometry.computeVertexNormals();
1835
1836         selectedObj.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
1837         selectedObj.geometry.computeVertexNormals();
1838
1839         var centerOffset = 0.5 * (geometry.boundingBox.max.x - geometry.boundingBox.min.x);
1840         var centerOffsetSelectedObj = 0.5 * (selectedObj.geometry.boundingBox.max.z - selectedObj.geometry.boundingBox.min.z);
1841         var centerOffsetSelectedObjY = 0.5 * (geometry.boundingBox.max.y - geometry.boundingBox.min.y);
1842         // add text to object
1843         var text = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, matLite);
1844
1845
1846         //add text to parent object
1847         selectedObj.add(text);
1848         console.log('added text to selected obj: ' + selectedObj.uuid);
1849
1850         // set position of text
1851         text.position.x = - centerOffset;
1852         text.position.z = centerOffsetSelectedObj + 0.01;
1853         text.position.y = - centerOffsetSelectedObjY
1854
1855     });
1856
1857

```

```

1858     console.log('name of object \'' + selectedObj.name + '\' set to ' + textToAdd);
1859     writeStringToCanvas(('name of object \'' + selectedObj.name + '\' set to ' + textToAdd));
1860
1861     //reset color before empty
1862     resetColorOfObjects();
1863 }
1864
1865
1866 //-----
1867 //function to reset color of selected object
1868 //-----
1869 function resetColorOfObjects() {
1870
1871     //for each element in array 'selectedObj' reset the color to default
1872     for (var i = 0; i < allObjects.length; i++) {
1873
1874         try {
1875             allObjects[i].material.color = StandardColor;
1876         }
1877         catch{ console.log('error on color reset on object ' + allObjects[i]) }
1878         finally { }
1879
1880     }
1881 }
1882
1883 //end of text label section -----
1884
1885 //function to print help to log
1886 function printHelp() {
1887     //show help notes
1888     writeStringToCanvas('-----');
1889     writeStringToCanvas('Help: press F12');
1890     writeStringToCanvas('selection 1. object (red) : click on next / prev to change element');
1891     writeStringToCanvas('selection 2. object (pink): click on 2. obj');
1892     writeStringToCanvas('on / off: to show / hide keyboard');
1893     writeStringToCanvas('connect / disconnect: to connect / disconnect objects');
1894     writeStringToCanvas('insert buttons: to insert objects');
1895     writeStringToCanvas('delete button: to delete red object');
1896     writeStringToCanvas('up / down / left / right: to move red object');
1897     writeStringToCanvas('-----');
1898 }
1899
1900 //-----
1901 //function to connect two objects with a line-----
1902 //-----
1903
1904 //requires two objects as input
1905 function connect(obj1, obj2) {
1906     //create a blue LineBasicMaterial
1907     material = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({ color: 0x0000ff });
1908
1909
1910     points.push(obj1.position);
1911     points.push(obj2.position);
1912
1913     //define Geometry
1914     geometry = new THREE.Geometry();
1915     geometry.vertices.push(obj1.position, obj2.position);
1916
1917     //define Line

```

```

1918         line = new THREE.Line(geometry, material);
1919         scene.add(line);
1920         lines.push([line, obj1, obj2]);
1921         writeStringToCanvas('connected objects ' + obj1.name + ' and ' + obj2.name);
1922
1923     }
1924
1925     //-----
1926     //function to disconnect two objects with a line-----
1927     //-----
1928     function disconnect(obj1, obj2) {
1929
1930
1931         for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
1932
1933             if ((lines[i][1] == obj1 && lines[i][2] == obj2) || (lines[i][2] == obj1 && lines[i][1]
1934                 //delete line
1935                 try {
1936                     scene.remove(lines[i][0]);
1937                     lines[i].pop(2);
1938                     lines[i].pop(1);
1939                     lines[i].pop(0);
1940                     lines.splice(i, 1);
1941
1942                     writeStringToCanvas('disconnected objects ' + obj1.name + ' and ' + obj2.name);
1943                     break;
1944                 }
1945                 catch{ }
1946             }
1947         }
1948     }
1949
1950     //this function updates all the lines in the global array "lines"
1951     //the function removes the old line and adds a new line with the new position
1952     //called in update function
1953     function updateLines() {
1954         for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
1955
1956             //if a array entry is undefined, delete it
1957             if (lines[i] == undefined) {
1958                 lines.splice(i, 1);
1959                 i = 0;
1960                 break;
1961             }
1962
1963             //console.log(lines);
1964             var line = lines[i][0];
1965             var obj1 = lines[i][1];
1966             var obj2 = lines[i][2];
1967             //var vertices = [obj1.position, obj2.position];
1968             //line.vertices = vertices;
1969
1970             scene.remove(line);
1971
1972             //define new material
1973             material = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({ color: 0x0000ff });
1974
1975
1976             //define Geometry
1977             geometry = new THREE.Geometry();

```

```

1978         geometry.vertices.push(obj1.position, obj2.position);
1979
1980         //define Line
1981         lines[i][0] = new THREE.Line(geometry, material);
1982         scene.add(lines[i][0]);
1983
1984     }
1985 }
1986
1987
1988 //-----
1989 // definition of game logic////////////////////////////////////
1990 //-----
1991
1992 //run GameLoop (update, render, repeat) -----
1993 var GameLoop = function () {
1994     requestAnimationFrame(GameLoop);
1995
1996     update();
1997     render();
1998
1999 };
2000
2001
2002 //-----
2003 // UPDATE function
2004 //-----
2005 var update = function () {
2006
2007     //keypress just checked after every 200 ms
2008     if (performance.now() > clock && performance.now() > 2000) {
2009         keys.forEach(key => detectCollisionCubes(key));
2010         clock = clock + 200;
2011     }
2012
2013     updatelines();
2014
2015 };
2016
2017
2018 //-----
2019 // ANIMATE function
2020 //-----
2021 function animate() {
2022     renderer.setAnimationLoop(render);
2023 }
2024
2025
2026 //-----
2027 // RENDER function
2028 //-----
2029 var render = function () {
2030     renderer.render(scene, camera);
2031 };
2032 //-----
2033
2034
2035
2036 // call
2037 animate();

```

```
2038     GameLoop();
2039
2040
2041 </script>
2042
2043 <!--canvas for log to image function-->
2044 <canvas id="myCanvas" width="578" height="200"></canvas>
2045
2046
2047 </body>
2048
2049 </html>
```

C Code of Concept 3

```

1 <html>
2
3 <head>
4   <meta charset="utf-8">
5   <style>
6     body {
7       margin: 0;
8       overflow: hidden;
9     }
10
11     #container {}
12   </style>
13 </head>
14
15 <body>
16   <div id="container"></div>
17   <script src="three/build/three.js"></script>
18   <script src="../js/leap-1.0.0.js"></script>
19   <script src="../js/leap-plugins-0.1.12.js"></script>
20   <script src="../js/leap-widgets-0.1.0.js"></script>
21   <script src="../js/VRKeyboard.js"></script>
22   <script src="../js/keyboard.js"></script>
23   <script src="../js/stats.min.js"></script>
24
25
26
27
28
29
30   <script type="module">
31
32     import * as THREE from '../three/build/three.module.js';
33     import { VRButton } from '../three/examples/jsm/webxr/VRButton.js';
34     import { GLTFLoader } from '../three/examples/jsm/loaders/GLTFLoader.js';
35     import { OrbitControls } from '../three/examples/jsm/controls/OrbitControls.js';
36     import { SVGLoader } from '../three/examples/jsm/loaders/SVGLoader.js';
37     import { XRControllerModelFactory } from '../three/examples/jsm/webxr/XRControllerModelFactor
38
39     import "../js/annyang.min.js";
40
41     //-----
42     //Global Variables
43     //-----
44
45     var camera, scene, renderer;
46     var geometry, material, mesh;
47     var controls;
48     var stats;
49     var user;
50     var raycaster;
51     var mouse = { x: 0, y: 0 };
52     var last = Date.now();
53     var keys = [];
54     const keyboard3d = new THREE.Object3D();
55     var log_plane;
56     var push_plane;
57     var push_plane_on;

```

```

58     var push_plane_next;
59     var push_plane_prev;
60     var keyboard_visible = true;
61     var allObjects = [];
62     var selectedObj = [];
63     var selectedObj_number = 0;
64     var textureLoader;
65     var objects;
66
67     var HighlightColor = new THREE.Color(0xff0000);
68     var StandardColor = new THREE.Color('white');
69
70     //this is the string for one line in the log
71     var string = "";
72
73     //variable for the performance.now() time
74     var clock = 0;
75
76     //controller variables
77     var raycasterForController;
78     var tempMatrix;
79     var controller, controller1, controller2;
80     var controllerGrip1, controllerGrip2;
81     var intersected = [];
82     var group;
83     var controllerModelFactory;
84     var line;
85     var intersection, intersections;
86     var object;
87
88     //array to store the values to update lines
89     var lines = [];
90     var points = [];
91
92     //init Canvas
93     //get information
94     var canvas;
95     canvas = document.getElementById('myCanvas');
96     canvas.width = 2048;//horizontal resolution (?) - increase for better looking text
97     canvas.height = 2048;//vertical resolution (?) - increase for better looking text
98     canvas.style.width = canvas.width;//actual width of canvas
99     canvas.style.height = canvas.height;//actual height of canvas
100    var ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
101
102    //array with all log elements to draw
103    var canvasArray = [];
104
105
106    //-----
107    //end of global variables
108    //-----
109
110
111
112
113
114    initStandardScene();
115    init();
116    animate();
117

```

```

118     setTimeout(function () { printHelp(); }, 3000);
119
120
121
122
123
124     //initialize specific project
125     function init() {
126
127
128         //add plane for log
129         geometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(0.5, 0.5);
130         material = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ side: THREE.DoubleSide });
131         log_plane = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, material);
132
133         updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
134         camera.add(log_plane);
135         log_plane.position.set(0.20, 0.02, -0.4);
136         log_plane.scale.set(0.5, 0.5, 0.5);
137         //log_plane.rotation.x += 0.2;
138         //-----
139
140
141
142
143         //add stats window to ckeck performance
144         var container = document.getElementById('container');
145         container.appendChild(renderer.domElement);
146         stats = new Stats();
147         stats.domElement.style.position = 'absolute';
148         stats.domElement.style.top = '0px';
149         document.body.appendChild(stats.domElement);
150
151         resize();
152
153
154         //init controllers-----
155
156         group = new THREE.Group();
157         user.add(group);
158
159         //init controller1 and add to user
160         controller1 = renderer.xr.getController(0);
161         controller1.addEventListener('selectstart', onSelectStart);
162         controller1.addEventListener('selectend', onSelectEnd);
163         user.add(controller1);
164
165         //init controller2 and add to user
166         controller2 = renderer.xr.getController(1);
167         controller2.addEventListener('selectstart', onSelectStart);
168         controller2.addEventListener('selectend', onSelectEnd);
169         user.add(controller2);
170
171         controllerModelFactory = new XRControllerModelFactory();
172
173         //add visual representation of controller 1 to scene
174         controllerGrip1 = renderer.xr.getControllerGrip(0);
175         controllerGrip1.add(controllerModelFactory.createControllerModel(controllerGrip1));
176         user.add(controllerGrip1);
177

```

```

178 //add visual representation of controller 2 to scene
179 controllerGrip2 = renderer.xr.getControllerGrip(1);
180 controllerGrip2.add(controllerModelFactory.createControllerModel(controllerGrip2));
181 user.add(controllerGrip2);
182
183 //create vector for raycaster line
184 geometry = new THREE.BufferGeometry().setFromPoints([new THREE.Vector3(0, 0, 0), new THREE
185 line = new THREE.Line(geometry);
186 line.name = 'line';
187 line.scale.z = 5;
188
189 //add raycaster lines to controllers
190 controller1.add(line.clone());
191 controller2.add(line.clone());
192
193 raycasterForController = new THREE.Raycaster();
194 tempMatrix = new THREE.Matrix4();
195
196
197 //end of controller init-----
198
199 }
200
201
202 //initialize the standard for all projects
203 function initStandardScene() {
204
205     scene = new THREE.Scene();
206
207     // add milkyWay
208     var background = new THREE.CubeTextureLoader()
209         .setPath('../three/examples/textures/cube/MilkyWay/')
210         .load(['dark-s_px.jpg', 'dark-s_nx.jpg', 'dark-s_py.jpg', 'dark-s_ny.jpg', 'dark-s_pz
211
212     scene.background = background;
213
214
215     //user needed for VR Camera
216     user = new THREE.Group();
217     user.position.set(0, 8, 30);
218     camera = new THREE.PerspectiveCamera(75, window.innerWidth / window.innerHeight, 0.1, 100
219     camera.position.set(0, 8, 30);
220     camera.lookAt(scene.position);
221
222     //add camera to user and user to scene
223     user.add(camera);
224     scene.add(user);
225
226     //define renderer
227     renderer = new THREE.WebGLRenderer();
228     renderer.setSize(window.innerWidth, window.innerHeight);
229
230     //add webxr support
231     document.body.appendChild(VRButton.createButton(renderer));
232     renderer.xr.enabled = true;
233
234     //add orbitControls
235     controls = new OrbitControls(camera, renderer.domElement);
236
237

```

```

238         //loads the floor
239         loadFloor();
240
241         //loads gltf objects
242         loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', 10, 5, 0, "Entity 1");
243         loadGLTFObject('models/relation.glb', 0, 5, 0, "Relation 1");
244         loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', -10, 5, 0, "Entity 2");
245         loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', -17, 5, 0, "Attribute 1");
246         loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', -10, 8, 0, "Attribute 2");
247
248
249
250
251
252
253         // -----
254         // lights
255         //-----
256         var light = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff);
257         light.position.set(0, 190, 80);
258         scene.add(light);
259
260         var light1 = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff, 2, 50);
261         light1.position.set(camera.position);
262         light1.position.z = light1.position.z + 3;
263         scene.add(light1);
264
265         var light2 = new THREE.PointLight(0xffffff, 2, 50);
266         light2.position.x = 0;
267         light2.position.y = 0
268         light2.position.z = 16;
269         scene.add(light2);
270
271         var ambience = new THREE.AmbientLight(0x666666);
272         scene.add(ambience);
273
274
275     }
276     // end of init -----
277
278
279
280     // -----
281     // function for resize
282     //-----
283     function resize() {
284         window.addEventListener('resize', onWindowResize, false);
285
286         function onWindowResize() {
287
288             camera.aspect = window.innerWidth / window.innerHeight;
289             camera.updateProjectionMatrix();
290
291             renderer.setSize(window.innerWidth, window.innerHeight);
292         }
293     }
294
295
296     // -----
297     // floor loader

```

```

298 //-----
299
300 //function to initialize the floor
301 function loadFloor() {
302     var groundGeometry = new THREE.PlaneBufferGeometry(40, 40, 10, 10);
303     var groundMaterial = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({ color: 0xcccccc });
304     var ground = new THREE.Mesh(groundGeometry, groundMaterial);
305     ground.rotation.x = Math.PI * - 0.5;
306     ground.name = 'Ground';
307     scene.add(ground);
308
309     var textureLoader = new THREE.TextureLoader();
310     textureLoader.load('./three/examples/textures/floors/FloorsCheckerboard_S_Diffuse.jpg',
311
312         map.wrapS = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
313         map.wrapT = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
314         map.anisotropy = 16;
315         map.repeat.set(4, 4);
316         groundMaterial.map = map;
317         groundMaterial.needsUpdate = true;
318
319
320     });
321 }
322
323
324 // -----
325 // gltf loader
326 //-----
327
328 function loadGLTFObject(path, x, y, z, name) {
329     var GLTFloader = new GLTFLoader();
330
331     //GLTFloader.load('models/duck.gltf', handle_load);
332     GLTFloader.load(path, handle_load);
333
334
335     //GLTF loader function
336     function handle_load(gltf) {
337         var objects = gltf.scene.children;
338         var theObject;
339         for (var i = 0; i < objects.length; i++) {
340             theObject = objects[i];
341             console.log(theObject);
342
343             //add object to scene
344             theObject.position.x = x;
345             theObject.position.y = y;
346             theObject.position.z = z;
347
348             theObject.name = name;
349
350             scene.add(theObject);
351             theObject.lookAt(user.position);
352
353
354
355
356
357             //push to array

```

```

358         allObjects.push(theObject);
359         console.log('added obj: ' + theObject.name + 'to array allObjects[]');
360         console.log('added obj: ' + theObject.name + ' to scene');
361         //writeStringToCanvas('added obj: ' + theObject.name + ' to scene');
362
363         selectedObj[0] = theObject;
364         setName(theObject.name, theObject);
365
366
367         var box = new THREE.BoxHelper(theObject, 0xffff00);
368         //scene.add( box );
369
370
371     }
372 }
373 }
374 }
375
376
377 //-----
378 // function to load Entity-Object
379 //-----
380 function insertEntity() {
381     loadGLTFObject('models/entity.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Entity");
382 }
383
384 //-----
385 // function to load Relation-Object
386 //-----
387 function insertRelation() {
388     loadGLTFObject('models/relation.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Relation");
389 }
390
391 //-----
392 // function to load Attribute-Object
393 //-----
394 function insertAttribute() {
395     loadGLTFObject('models/attribute.glb', 0, 10, 0, "Attribute");
396 }
397
398 //-----
399 // function to delete an object
400 //-----
401 function deleteObject() {
402     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
403
404         //if line with this object exists, delete it
405         if (lines[i][1] == selectedObj[0] || lines[i][2] == selectedObj[0]) {
406             //delete line
407             try {
408                 scene.remove(lines[i][0]);
409                 lines[i].pop(2);
410                 lines[i].pop(1);
411                 lines[i].pop(0);
412                 lines[i] = undefined;
413
414             }
415             catch{ }
416         }
417     }

```

```

418     }
419
420     //delete object from allObjects list
421     for (var j = 0; j < allObjects.length; j++) {
422         if (allObjects[j] == selectedObj[0]) {
423             allObjects.splice(j, 1);
424             j = 100;
425         }
426     }
427
428     //remove object from scene
429     scene.remove(selectedObj[0]);
430     selectedObj = [];
431     console.log(allObjects);
432 }
433
434 //-----
435 // LOG section
436 //-----
437
438 //-----
439 // function to update the texture for the canvas
440 //-----
441 function updateTextureOfElement(object) {
442
443     textureLoader = new THREE.TextureLoader();
444     textureLoader.load(document.getElementById('myCanvas').toDataURL("image/png", 1.0), funct
445
446     map.wrapS = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
447     map.wrapT = THREE.RepeatWrapping;
448
449     object.material.map = map;
450     object.material.needsUpdate = true;
451 });
452 }
453
454
455 //-----
456 // writes a string to the log canvas
457 //-----
458 function writeStringToCanvas(stringToWrite) {
459
460     // function init
461     ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
462     canvasArray.push(stringToWrite);
463     ctx.fillStyle = "red"; // set stroke color to red
464     ctx.font = "70px Unknown Font, sans-serif"; //"12px Georgia";
465
466     if (canvas.getContext) {
467         var y = 100;
468
469         //clear canvas
470         ctx.clearRect(0, 0, canvas.width, canvas.height);
471
472         //draw all elements if array is < 10
473         if (canvasArray.length < 10) {
474             for (var i = 0; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
475                 //write to canvas
476                 ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
477                 y = y + 150;

```

```

478     }
479   }
480   //draw last 10 elements if array >= 10
481   else if (canvasArray.length >= 10) {
482     for (var i = canvasArray.length - 10; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
483       //write to canvas
484       ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
485       y = y + 150;
486     }
487   }
488 }
489
490 //update texture of plane
491 //takes the webur1 of the canvas
492 updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
493 }
494
495
496 //-----
497 // function to add a character at the same line
498 //adds the character in argument to the line in the log
499 //this function is called when you press a key on the keyboard
500 //-----
501 function writeStringToCanvasOnSameLine(charToAdd) {
502
503   //function init
504   ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
505   ctx.fillStyle = "red"; // set stroke color to red
506   ctx.font = "70px Unknown Font, sans-serif"; //"12px Georgia";
507
508   //if there is already a character in the element
509   if (canvasArray[canvasArray.length] != undefined) {
510     var lastElement = canvasArray[canvasArray.length] + charToAdd;
511   }
512   //if no character in element
513   else {
514     var lastElement = charToAdd;
515   }
516
517   //pop last element in array and pushes the new element with added character
518   canvasArray.pop(canvasArray[canvasArray.length]);
519   canvasArray.push(lastElement);
520
521
522   if (canvas.getContext) {
523     var y = 100;
524
525     //clear canvas
526     ctx.clearRect(0, 0, canvas.width, canvas.height);
527
528     //draw last 10 elements if array is >= 10
529     if (canvasArray.length >= 10) {
530       for (var i = canvasArray.length - 10; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
531         //write to canvas
532         ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
533         y = y + 150;
534       }
535     }
536
537     //draw canvas if array <10

```

```

538         else if (canvasArray.length < 10) {
539             for (var i = 0; i < canvasArray.length; i++) {
540                 //write to canvas
541                 ctx.fillText(canvasArray[i], 10, y);
542                 y = y + 150;
543             }
544         }
545
546
547     }
548
549     //update texture of plane -- takes the webur1 of the canvas
550     updateTextureOfElement(log_plane);
551
552 }
553
554 //end of log section -----
555
556
557
558
559
560
561 //-----
562 // function to output a sound to the speaker
563 //-----
564 function beep() {
565     var snd = new Audio("data:audio/wav;base64,//uQRAAAWMSLwUIYAsYkXgoQwAEaYlWfkWgAI0wWs/It
566     snd.play();
567 }
568
569
570
571
572 //-----
573 // text label
574 //-----
575
576 //-----
577 //function to set the name of the selected object
578 //-----
579
580 function setName(name, object) {
581     console.log("object = " + object)
582     updateTextInGroup(object, name);
583
584     //reset color before empty
585     resetColorOfObjects();
586
587     //selectedObj = [];
588     render();
589
590
591 }
592
593
594 //-----
595 //function update Text in Group used in SetName
596 //-----
597

```

```

598     function updateTextInGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd) {
599
600         //remove old text if one is there
601         try {
602             console.log(selectedObj);
603             selectedObj.children.forEach(element => {
604                 selectedObj.remove(element);
605                 element.dispose();
606                 console.log("disposed");
607             });
608         }
609         catch { console.log('not text to delet'); }
610
611         //add new text
612         console.log(selectedObj.geometry.boundingSphere.radius);
613         addTextToGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd, 0.5, 0.11);
614
615         // emty list
616         selectedObj = [];
617
618     }
619
620
621     //-----
622     //function addTextToGroup used in updateTextInGroup
623     //-----
624
625     //function to add a text to an object
626     // args: an object to get the position of the text, a string which represents the text, a for
627     function addTextToGroup(selectedObj, textToAdd, givenSize, givenHeight) {
628
629         //set new name
630         selectedObj.name = textToAdd;
631
632         var fontLoader = new THREE.FontLoader();
633
634         fontLoader.load('three/examples/fonts/helvetiker_regular.typeface.json', function (font)
635
636             //define geometry
637             var geometry = new THREE.TextBufferGeometry(textToAdd, {
638                 font: font,
639                 size: givenSize,
640                 height: givenHeight,
641                 curveSegments: 12,
642                 bevelEnabled: false,
643
644             });
645
646             //rotate by 180 degree
647             //geometry.rotateY(3.14159);
648
649             var color = new THREE.Color('black');
650
651             //define material
652             var matLite = new THREE.MeshBasicMaterial({
653                 color: color,
654                 transparent: false,
655                 opacity: 0.4,
656                 side: THREE.DoubleSide
657             });

```

```

658
659
660     geometry.computeBoundingBox();
661     geometry.computeVertexNormals();
662
663     selectedObj.geometry.computeBoundingBox();
664     selectedObj.geometry.computeVertexNormals();
665
666     var centerOffset = 0.5 * (geometry.boundingBox.max.x - geometry.boundingBox.min.x);
667     var centerOffsetSelectedObj = 0.5 * (selectedObj.geometry.boundingBox.max.z - selectedObj.geometry.boundingBox.min.z);
668     var centerOffsetSelectedObjY = 0.5 * (geometry.boundingBox.max.y - geometry.boundingBox.min.y);
669     // add text to object
670     var text = new THREE.Mesh(geometry, matLite);
671
672
673     //add text to parent object
674     selectedObj.add(text);
675     console.log('added text to selected obj: ' + selectedObj.uuid);
676
677     // set position of text
678     text.position.x = - centerOffset;
679     text.position.z = centerOffsetSelectedObj + 0.01;
680     text.position.y = - centerOffsetSelectedObjY
681
682
683 });
684
685 console.log('name of object \'' + selectedObj.name + '\' set to ' + textToAdd);
686 writeStringToCanvas(('name of object \'' + selectedObj.name + '\' set to ' + textToAdd));
687
688 //reset color before empty
689 resetColorOfObjects();
690 }
691
692
693 //-----
694 //function to reset color of selected object
695 //-----
696 function resetColorOfObjects() {
697
698     //for each element in array 'selectedObj' reset the color to default
699     for (var i = 0; i < allObjects.length; i++) {
700
701         try {
702             allObjects[i].material.color = StandardColor;
703         }
704         catch{ console.log('error on color reset on object ' + allObjects[i]) }
705         finally { }
706
707     }
708 }
709 //end of text label section -----
710
711
712 //-----
713 //controller functions
714 //-----
715
716 function onSelectStart(event) {
717

```

```

718     controller = event.target;
719
720     intersections = getIntersections(controller);
721
722     if (intersections.length > 0) {
723
724         intersection = intersections[0];
725
726         //add to list with selected objects -- at beginning
727         selectedObj.unshift(scene.getObjectById(intersections[0].object.id, true));
728         console.log(scene.getObjectById(intersections[0].object.id, true));
729
730         //update color of selected
731         updateColorOfSelectedObject();
732
733         tempMatrix.getInverse(controller.matrixWorld);
734
735         object = intersection.object;
736         object.matrix.premultiply(tempMatrix);
737         object.matrix.decompose(object.position, object.quaternion, object.scale);
738         object.material.emissive.b = 1;
739         controller.add(object);
740
741         controller.userData.selected = object;
742
743     }
744 }
745
746 function onSelectEnd(event) {
747
748     controller = event.target;
749
750
751     if (controller.userData.selected !== undefined) {
752
753         object = controller.userData.selected;
754         object.matrix.premultiply(controller.matrixWorld);
755         object.matrix.decompose(object.position, object.quaternion, object.scale);
756
757
758         object.material.emissive.b = 0;
759         scene.add(object);
760         //push to array
761         allObjects.push(object);
762
763         controller.userData.selected = undefined;
764
765     }
766 }
767
768 function getIntersections(controller) {
769
770     tempMatrix.identity().extractRotation(controller.matrixWorld);
771
772     raycasterForController.ray.origin.setFromMatrixPosition(controller.matrixWorld);
773     raycasterForController.ray.direction.set(0, 0, - 1).applyMatrix4(tempMatrix);
774
775     return raycasterForController.intersectObjects(allObjects);
776
777

```

```

778     }
779
780
781     function intersectObjects(controller) {
782
783         // Do not highlight when already selected
784
785         if (controller.userData.selected !== undefined) return;
786
787         var line = controller.getObjectByName('line');
788         intersections = getIntersections(controller);
789
790         if (intersections.length > 1) {
791
792             intersection = intersections[1];
793
794             object = intersection.object;
795             //object.material.emissive.r = 1;
796             intersected.push(object);
797             //console.log(object);
798
799             line.scale.z = intersection.distance;
800
801         } else {
802
803             line.scale.z = 5;
804
805         }
806     }
807 }
808
809 function cleanIntersected() {
810
811     try {
812
813         while (intersected.length) {
814
815             object = intersected.pop();
816             object.material.emissive.r = 0;
817
818         }
819     } catch{ }
820     finally { }
821 }
822
823
824
825 //highlight the two selected objects
826 function updateColorOfSelectedObject() {
827
828     //reset all colors
829     resetColorOfObjects();
830
831     //set new color to selected object 1 + 2
832     for (var i = 0; i < selectedObj.length; i++) {
833
834         //for element 1 + 2 in array set color
835         if (i < 2) {
836             selectedObj[i].material.color = HighlightColor;
837         }

```

```

838     }
839
840     // cut selectedObj to two objects
841     if (selectedObj.length >= 2) {
842         var slice = []
843         slice = selectedObj.slice(0, 2)
844         selectedObj = slice;
845     }
846 }
847
848
849 //-----
850 //function to connect two objects with a line-----
851 //-----
852
853 //requires two objects as input
854 function connect(obj1, obj2) {
855     //create a blue LineBasicMaterial
856     material = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({ color: 0x0000ff });
857
858
859     points.push(obj1.position);
860     points.push(obj2.postion);
861
862     //define Geometry
863     geometry = new THREE.Geometry();
864     geometry.vertices.push(obj1.position, obj2.position);
865
866     //define Line
867     line = new THREE.Line(geometry, material);
868     scene.add(line);
869     lines.push([line, obj1, obj2]);
870     writeStringToCanvas('connected objects ' + obj1.name + ' and ' + obj2.name);
871
872 }
873
874 //-----
875 //function to disconnect two objects with a line-----
876 //-----
877 function disconnect(obj1, obj2) {
878
879
880     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
881
882         if ((lines[i][1] == obj1 && lines[i][2] == obj2) || (lines[i][2] == obj1 && lines[i][1]
883             //delete line
884             try {
885                 scene.remove(lines[i][0]);
886                 lines[i].pop(2);
887                 lines[i].pop(1);
888                 lines[i].pop(0);
889                 lines.splice(i, 1);
890
891                 writeStringToCanvas('disconnected objects ' + obj1.name + ' and ' + obj2.name);
892                 break;
893             }
894             catch{ }
895         }
896     }
897 }

```

```

898
899 //this function updates all the lines in the global array "lines"
900 //the function removes the old line and adds a new line with the new position
901 //called in update function
902 function updateLines() {
903     for (var i = 0; i < lines.length; i++) {
904
905         //if a array entry is undefined, delete it
906         if (lines[i] == undefined) {
907             lines.splice(i, 1);
908             i = 0;
909             break;
910         }
911
912         //console.log(lines);
913         var line = lines[i][0];
914         var obj1 = lines[i][1];
915         var obj2 = lines[i][2];
916         //var vertices = [obj1.position, obj2.position];
917         //line.vertices = vertices;
918
919         scene.remove(line);
920
921         //define new material
922         material = new THREE.LineBasicMaterial({ color: 0x0000ff });
923
924
925         //define Geometry
926         geometry = new THREE.Geometry();
927         geometry.vertices.push(obj1.position, obj2.position);
928
929         //define Line
930         lines[i][0] = new THREE.Line(geometry, material);
931         scene.add(lines[i][0]);
932
933     }
934 }
935
936 //function to print help to log
937 function printHelp() {
938     //show help notes
939     writeStringToCanvas('-----');
940     writeStringToCanvas('Help: say help');
941     writeStringToCanvas('selection: click on element to select it');
942     writeStringToCanvas('set name: say: set name to *');
943     writeStringToCanvas('connect: select two elements and say: connect');
944     writeStringToCanvas('disconnect: select two elements and say: disconnect');
945     writeStringToCanvas('insert: say: insert entity/relation/attribute');
946     writeStringToCanvas('delete: select object and say delete');
947     writeStringToCanvas('-----');
948 }
949
950
951
952 //-----
953 //set up anyyang
954 //-----
955
956 if (anyyang) {
957

```

```

958 // define the functions our commands will run.
959
960 var setNameTo = function (tag) {
961     writeStringToCanvas('command was: set name to ' + tag);
962     setName(tag, selectedObj[0]);
963 };
964
965
966 var connectWithLine = function () {
967     //console.log(selectedObj);
968
969     writeStringToCanvas('command was: Connect');
970     connect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
971
972
973     //reset color before empty
974     resetColorOfObjects();
975
976     selectedObj = [];
977 };
978
979
980 var disconnectObj = function () {
981     //console.log(selectedObj);
982
983     writeStringToCanvas('command was: Disconnect');
984     disconnect(selectedObj[0], selectedObj[1]);
985
986     //reset color before empty
987     resetColorOfObjects();
988
989     selectedObj = [];
990 };
991
992 var help = function () {
993     printHelp();
994 }
995
996 var AnyyangInsertAttribute = function () {
997     insertAttribute();
998     writeStringToCanvas('command was: insert attribute');
999 }
1000
1001 var AnyyangInsertEntity = function () {
1002     insertEntity();
1003     writeStringToCanvas('command was: insert entity');
1004 }
1005
1006 var AnyyangInsertRelation = function () {
1007     insertRelation();
1008     writeStringToCanvas('command was: insert relation');
1009 }
1010
1011 var AnyyangDeleteObject = function () {
1012     deleteObject();
1013     writeStringToCanvas('command was: delete');
1014 }
1015
1016 // define our commands.
1017 // * The key is the phrase you want your users to say.

```

```

1018 // * The value is the action to do.
1019 // You can pass a function, a function name (as a string), or write your function as pa
1020 var commands = {
1021     'set name to *search': setNameTo,
1022     'connect': connectWithLine,
1023     'disconnect': disconnectObj,
1024     'help': help,
1025     'insert attribute': AnnyangInsertAttribute,
1026     'insert entity': AnnyangInsertEntity,
1027     'insert relation': AnnyangInsertRelation,
1028     'delete': AnnyangDeleteObject
1029 };
1030
1031 // OPTIONAL: activate debug mode for detailed logging in the console
1032 //annyang.debug();
1033
1034 // Add voice commands to respond to
1035 annyang.addCommands(commands);
1036
1037 // OPTIONAL: Set a language for speech recognition (defaults to English)
1038 // For a full list of language codes, see the documentation:
1039 // https://github.com/TalAter/annyang/blob/master/docs/FAQ.md#what-languages-are-supporte
1040 annyang.setLanguage('en');
1041
1042 // Start listening. You can call this here, or attach this call to an event, button, etc.
1043 annyang.start();
1044
1045 } else {
1046     $(document).ready(function () {
1047         $('#unsupported').fadeIn('fast');
1048     });
1049 }
1050
1051 //function to log to canvas the different possibilities when speech recognized
1052 annyang.addCallback('result', function (phrases) {
1053
1054     var splitArray = phrases.toString().split(",");
1055     writeStringToCanvas('-----');
1056     writeStringToCanvas('Speech recognized. Possible sentences said:');
1057     for (var i = 0; i < splitArray.length; i++) {
1058         writeStringToCanvas(splitArray[i]);
1059     }
1060     writeStringToCanvas('-----');
1061 });
1062
1063 // end of annyang set up -----
1064
1065
1066
1067
1068 //-----
1069 // definition of game logic////////////////////////////////////
1070 //-----
1071
1072 //run GameLoop (update, render, repeat) -----
1073 var GameLoop = function () {
1074     requestAnimationFrame(GameLoop);
1075
1076     update();
1077     render();

```

```

1078
1079     };
1080
1081
1082     //-----
1083     // UPDATE function
1084     //-----
1085     var update = function () {
1086
1087         //checke after every 200 ms
1088         if (performance.now() > clock && performance.now() > 2000) {
1089             console.table(lines);
1090             clock = clock + 800;
1091         }
1092
1093         updateLines();
1094
1095     };
1096
1097
1098     //-----
1099     // ANIMATE function
1100     //-----
1101     function animate() {
1102         renderer.setAnimationLoop(renderer);
1103     }
1104
1105
1106     //-----
1107     // RENDER function
1108     //-----
1109     var render = function () {
1110         renderer.render(scene, camera);
1111     };
1112     //-----
1113
1114
1115
1116     // call
1117     animate();
1118     GameLoop();
1119
1120
1121 </script>
1122
1123 <!--canvas for log to image function-->
1124 <canvas id="myCanvas" width="578" height="200"></canvas>
1125
1126
1127 </body>
1128
1129 </html>

```

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ERKLÄRUNG

Ich bestätige mit meiner Unterschrift, dass ich die Arbeit persönlich erstellt und dabei nur die aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel verwendet sowie wörtliche Zitate und Paraphrasen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Es ist mir bekannt, dass andernfalls die Fakultät gemäss der Entscheidung des Fakultätsrats vom 09.11.2004 das Recht hat, den auf Grund dieser Arbeit verliehenen Titel zu entziehen.

Ich erkläre hiermit weiterhin, dass diese Arbeit bzw. Teile daraus noch nicht in dieser Form an anderer Stelle als Prüfungsleistung eingereicht worden sind, gemäss der Entscheidung des Fakultätsrats vom 18.11.2013.

..... Bern, den 15.05. 2020

.....
(Unterschrift)